

ADDIS ABABA UNIVERSITY
ADDIS ABABA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY
SCHOOL OF CIVIL AND ENVIRONMENTAL
ENGINEERING

STRUCTURAL DESIGN OF A G+4 RESIDENTIAL BUILDING
AT ADDIS ABABA USING THE REVISED ETHIOPIAN
BUILDING
CODE OF STANDARDS(ES EN 2004:2015)

A Thesis in Structural Engineering

By

Daniel Adamu	ATR/4569/05
Isa Hussein	ATR/3974/05
Dawit Mekrie	ATR/2718/05
Dawit Kibru	ATR/3533/05
Jafer Usmael	ATR/1341/05

June, 2017

Addis Ababa

A Thesis

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of Bachelor of Science

The undersigned have examined the thesis entitled ‘structural design of a G+4 residential building at Ababa using the revised Ethiopian building code of standards’ presented by

Daniel Adamu	ATR/4569/05
Isa Hussein	ATR/3974/05
Dawit Mekrie	ATR/2718/05
Dawit Kibru	ATR/3533/05
Jafer Usmael	ATR/1341/05

Candidates for the degree of **Bachelor of Science** and hereby certify that it is worthy of acceptance.

INS.Mekdes Tadesse	_____	_____
Advisor	Signature	Date
_____	_____	_____
Internal Examiner	Signature	Date
_____	_____	_____
External Examiner	Signature	Date
_____	_____	_____
Chair person	Signature	Date

UNDERTAKING

We certify that research work titled “structural design of a G+4 residential building at Ababa using the revised Ethiopian building code of standards” is our own work. The work has not been presented elsewhere for assessment. Where material has been used from other sources it has been properly acknowledged / referred.

Name of student	signature
Daniel Adamu	
Isa Hussein	
Dawit Mekrie	
Dawit Kibru	
Jafer Usmael	

ABSTRACT

This thesis presents structural analysis and design of a G+4 Residential building using revised (New) Ethiopian Building Code of Practice (ES EN 2004:2015) at Addis Ababa. It has a purpose of developing the skills and capacities required in structural engineering arena.

The paper contains nine chapters; the first one is general introduction. The second chapter deals with analysis of wind load and design of roof. The next two chapters are concerned about analysis design of structural members, i.e. Slab and staircase. Chapter five, six and seven are about lateral load and stability analysis, analysis and design of beam and column respectively. Chapter eight is concerned about detailing of structural elements. The last chapter is dedicated to conclusions drawn and recommendations.

Structural analysis and design of the building is based on the newly revised Ethiopian building code, ES EN 2004:2015 which follows Limit State design approach. Analysis was done using structural design soft wares like ETABS and SAP2000.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

First and foremost we would like to express our sincere gratitude to INS.Mekdes for her willingness and cooperation to be part of the thesis being an advisor. The school of civil and environmental engineering should also be praised for the productive effort they displayed that helped us much in gaining knowledge of civil engineering.

Above all, the almighty God, the creator and author of every wisdom, for his endless love and help.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	IV
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	V
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	VI
LIST OF TABLES.....	X
LIST OF FIGURES.....	XII
CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 General Introduction.....	1
1.2 Site conditions and basis of design.....	2
1.2.1 General data and preliminary overview.....	2
1.2.2 Assumptions made on code used.....	6
1.2.3 Limit State Design method.....	6
1.2.4 Partial factors for materials.....	6
1.3 Design strength and material property.....	7
1.3.1 Design compressive and tensile strengths of concrete according to ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1-section-3.1.6.....	7
1.3.2 Design strength of steel according to ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1-section-37.....	7
1.4 Durability and cover to reinforcement.....	9
1.4.1 Definition and importance of Concrete Cover.....	9
1.4.2 Basic Assumptions.....	9
1.4.3 Designing of concrete cover according to ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1-section 9.....	9
CHAPTER 2 WIND LOAD ANALYSIS AND ROOF DEISGN.....	14
2.1 Wind load on roof.....	14
2.1.1 Roof characteristics and wind pressure determination.....	14
2.2 Roof Design.....	17
2.2.1 EGA sheet design.....	17
2.2.2 Purlin design.....	19

2.2.3	Truss design	22
CHAPTER 3 ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF SOLID SLAB (COEFFICIENT METHOD) 26		
3.1	Introduction	26
3.2	Procedures for analysis and design of solid slab.....	26
3.2.1	Depth determination	26
3.2.2	Loading	27
3.2.3	Moment and shear Computation.....	29
3.2.4	Redistribution of support moments and adjustment of span moments.....	31
3.2.5	Design for flexure	32
3.2.6	Check shear capacity of the slab.....	34
3.3	Design of Ground floor slab.....	39
3.4	Water tanker slab analysis and Design	39
CHAPTER 4 ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF STAIR –CASE44		
4.1	Introduction	44
4.2	Analysis and Design of typical floor stair.....	45
4.3	Analysis and Design of ground floor stair	51
CHAPTER 5 LATERAL LOAD AND STABILITY ANALYSIS53		
5.1	Wind load determination.....	53
5.1.1	Method of Analysis.....	53
5.1.2	Wind Analysis	54
5.1.3	Wall division.....	55
5.1.4	Wind force	57
5.1.5	Internal wind pressure determination	57
5.1.6	Net wind force determination	58
5.2	Earth quake analysis and design	58
5.2.1	Description of the building	58
5.2.2	Earthquake Loading.....	59
5.2.3	Procedure for lateral force method	60

5.2.4	Earthquake Loading.....	60
5.2.5	Horizontal seismic action	60
5.2.6	Horizontal seismic action	61
5.2.7	Vertical actions	63
5.2.8	Determination of earth quake force	63
	Distribution of the horizontal seismic force	64
5.3	Geometric imperfections.....	64
5.4	Modeling and stability analysis.....	66
5.4.1	Analysis inputs and cases	66
5.4.1.1	Analysis and load combinations	68
5.5	Structural system.....	71
5.5.1	Centre of mass (CM) and Centre of rigidity (CR).....	71
5.6	Lateral stability of the structure in ultimate limit state	74
5.6.1	Inter-story Drift Sensitivity Coefficient.....	74
5.6.2	Damage limitation Requirement.....	79
CHAPTER 6	ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF BEAM	81
6.1	Introduction.....	81
6.1.1	Basic Principles and Assumptions in Flexure Theory of Reinforced.....	81
6.2	Load on beam.....	83
6.2.1	Dead load from walls directly supported on beam	84
6.2.2	Load transferred to beam from slab.....	85
6.2.3	Load transfer from stair-case	90
6.3	Design of Beam.....	94
6.3.1	Design of RC Section for flexure	94
6.3.2	Design for Shear	100
CHAPTER 7	DESIGN OF COLUMNS.....	103
7.1	Introduction.....	103
7.2	Slenderness.....	104
7.2.1	Limits of slenderness	104

7.3	Example on design and analysis of columns	105
7.4	Design data and analysis results for central column (C10).....	112
7.5	Design of columns for shear	115
7.5.1	Diameter of stirrups	116
7.5.2	Spacing of stirrups	116
CHAPTER 8	DETAILING OF DESIGNED MEMBERS	117
8.1	SLAB DETAILING	117
8.2	STAIR DETAILING.....	118
8.3	BEAM DETAILING.....	119
8.4	Column detailing.....	120
CHAPTER 9	CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION.....	121
9.1	Conclusion	121
9.2	Recommendation	122
REFERENCES	123
APPENDICES	124

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1 : Partial safety factors for materials in according to ES EN 2004:2015-2004; 2014	6
Table 1.2: Material properties for concrete grades to be used for the building.....	8
Table 1.3: Modulus of elasticity of steel and concrete for concrete and for steel).....	8
Table 1.4: Exposure Classes of super and sub structures corresponding to environmental conditions of the site.....	10
Table 1.5: Indicative strength Classes for durability	10
Table 1.6: Environmental Requirements	10
Table 1.7: Minimum cover, $C_{min, b}$, requirements with regard to bond	11
Table 1.8: Minimum slab concrete cover for fire resistance	12
Table 1.9: minimum beam concrete cover for fire resistance	13
Table 2.1: Area coverage for respective roof zone for $\Theta=0, 180^0$	15
Table 2.2: Area coverage for respective roof zone for $\Theta= 90^0$	15
Table 2.3: external pressure coefficients for $\theta=0^0$ and all -ve	15
Table 2.4: external pressure coefficients $\theta=0^0$ and all +ve.....	15
Table 2.5: external pressure coefficients for $\theta=180^0$	15
Table 2.6: external pressure coefficients for $\theta=90^0$	16
Table 2.7: positive external pressure values	16
Table 2.8: negative external pressure values	16
Table 2.9: Imperfection factors.....	25
Table 3.1:- Basic ratios of span/effective depth for reinforced concrete members without axial compression.	27
Table 3.2: Unit weight and thickness of building materials used on the building.....	27
Table 3.3: Live load for category A buildings.....	28
Table 3.4: sample of shear computation	36
Table 3.5: Load and coefficients on Panel-1' (on roof) left tanker	41
Table 3.6: load and coefficients on Panel-2' (on roof) Right tanker	42
Table 4.1: Dead load of slopping portion	46
Table 4.2: Dead load of landing portion.....	46
Table 4.3: Loading summary	46
Table 4.4: Design Moment (Msd) result for corresponding span loading.....	49
Table 4.5: Reinforcement calculation (Flight A form the ground to landing (G to l)	51

Table 4.6: Reinforcement calculation (Flight B from the Landing to flight (L to F)).....	51
Table 4.7: Moment result for ground stair.....	51
Table 4.8: Reinforcement calculation (Flight A form the ground to landing (G to l)).....	52
Table 5.1: The respective area of zones.....	56
Table 5.2: External wind pressure coefficients on walls	56
Table 5.3: External wind pressure on walls.....	57
Table 5.4: wind force.....	57
Table 5.5: internal pressure on walls	58
Table 5.6 Base shear distribution over the height of the structure	64
Table 5.7: calculation of longitudinal forces (imperfection load)	66
Table 5.8: comparison between modeling with and with out diaphragms	67
Table 5.9: Load combinations	69
Table 5.10: Dimensions used in the building	72
Table 5.11: Roof center of mass	72
Table 5.12: First floor center of mass.....	73
Table 5.13: Ground floor center of mass	73
Table 5.14: Centre of Mass and Centre of Stiffness of the structure.....	73
Table 5.15: Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination	75
Table 5.16: Checking Damage limitation c	80
Table: 6.1 Sample shear calculation	86
Table 6.2: summary of design of beams.....	99
Table 6.3: Central column (C10) end moments.....	112
Table 6.4 : Compressive axial forces for central column corresponding to load combinations.....	113
Table 6.5: summary of slenderness ratio for central column.....	113
Table 6.6: Slenderness checking in the x-direction	114
Table 6.7: Slenderness checking in the y-direction	114
Table 6.8: Reinforcement provision	115
Table 7.1: Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination	184
Table 7.2: Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination	187
Table 7.3: Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination	191

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1 : Ground floor architectural drawing.....	2
Figure 1.2 : Typical floor architectural drawing.....	3
Figure 1.3: Ground floor layout.....	4
Figure 1.4: Typical floor layout.....	5
Figure 2.1: Wind directions for elevation.....	14
Figure 2.2: Wind directions for plan.....	14
Figure 2.3: RT-64 cross-section	19
Figure 2.4: Roof (top view)	21
Figure 2.5: parametric properties of Pratt truss	22
Figure 2.6: Cross-section of RT-128	23
Figure 3.1: Plan view of panel-1.....	29
Figure 3.2:- Plan view and loading on panel-7.....	30
Figure 3.3: cantilever -7.....	31
Figure 3.4: Load distribution pattern of slabs.....	35
Figure 3.5: plan view of panel-1	36
Figure 3.6 : top view for panel -7	37
Figure 3.7: shear force from dead loading for panel -7	37
Figure 3.8: shear force from live loading for panel - 7.....	37
Figure 3.9: plan view for cantilever -8	38
Figure 3.10: Shear force from dead loading for cantilever-8	38
Figure 3.11:-tanker slab top view	39
Figure 3.12: Moment computation	42
Figure 4.1: Plan view of the stair.....	44
Figure 4.2: Sectional view of stair A-A.....	44
Figure 4.3: Section view of stair B-B	45
Figure 4.4: Dead loading	47
Figure 4.5: Shear force diagram form dead load	47
Figure 4.6: Bending moment diagram for dead load.....	47
Figure 4.7: Live loading	48
Figure 4.8: Shear force from live load.....	48
Figure 4.9: Bending moment from live loading	48
Figure 4.10: Depths d_1 and d_2 in section view.....	49

Figure 5.1: Wind direction for elevation	56
Figure 5.2: Effects of geometric imperfections	65
Figure 5.3: Structural model of the building on ETABS -2015	71
Figure 6.1: Stress-Strain diagram for reinforcing steel	82
Figure 6.2: wall load (kN/m) on beam.....	85
Figure 6.3 : Sample Two way slab	86
Figure 6.4: one way slab	87
Figure 6.5 : dead loading	87
Figure 6.6 : live loading	87
Figure 6.7 : cantilever -8.....	88
Figure 6.8: Summary of un factored live Load (KN/m) from slab to beam.....	89
Figure 6.9 : Summary of un factored Dead load (KN/m) from slab to beam.....	90
Figure 6.10: Dead loading	91
Figure 6.11: shear force diagram for dead load	91
Figure 6.12: Live loading	91
Figure 6.13: shear force diagram	91
Figure 6.14: Shear force diagram(SFD)	93
Figure 6.15: Bending moment diagram (BMD)	94
Figure 6.16: Typical crossection.....	94
Figure 6.17: Critical moments at beams	95

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 General Introduction

Building Structures are assemblage of members that are designed to resist self-weight and actions expected to apply on it. By considering the load resisting behavior, these members could either be structural or non-structural. The structural members are those that protect the whole building against failure or collapse. By this thesis it is desired to analyze and design structural members of a G+4 residential building in accordance with the revised Ethiopian building code of standards ES EN 2004:2015:2014, which was adopted from European building code of standards. As this code is a modern day one, it follows limit state approach of design. Limit state is a state beyond which a structure is no longer able to satisfy the design performance requirements and has two components, ultimate and serviceability limit states.

Ultimate limit states are conditions related to collapse or states prior to collapse or structural failure. The major concern of this limit state is the safety of users and the structure itself. Serviceability limit state is those associated to conditions beyond which a structure no longer satisfies its intended purpose. In simple words, it's related to appearance, comfort, and other parameters.

Structural frame is composed of elements like beams, slabs, stairs, columns and foundation. If it is required to analyze or design the frame, criteria of limit state should be applied to every single structural element. Floors and soffit of stairs on this building are of solid slab type and loadings like dead, live, wind and others are selected according to ES EN 2004:2015. The slab is designed for partition load, floor finish, slab's self-weight and live load as well. Typical floor slab is found on this project and were analyzed using the coefficient method of analysis.

Ductility is another key parameter that has to be considered in designing a structure. If the structure fails, it must be in such a way it will minimize risks. The minimization of risks is ensured by providing sufficient evacuation time for people and goods inside it. In short, ductility is a principle by which minimum damage is recorded if failure happens.

1.2 Site conditions and basis of design

This sub-chapter presents general properties of the site, principles of limit state design and properties of materials to be used for constructing the building.

1.2.1 General data and preliminary overview

The building is of residential type having four stories without roof access and is to be constructed in Addis Ababa. The dimensions of the slab in plan are (27.2m X 24.1m) making the plan area to be 655.52 m². Most of the rooms will be used as bedrooms having small shower rooms inside it. Height h, measured from ground level is equal to 18.18m. A conventional life of 50 years is assumed for design.

Figure 1.1 : Ground floor architectural drawing

Figure 1.2 : Typical floor architectural drawing

Figure 1.3: Ground floor layout

Figure 1.4: Typical floor layout

1.2.2 Assumptions made on code used

The following assumptions were applied:

- The choice of structural system and design of a structure are made by appropriately qualified and experienced personnel.
- The construction materials and products used are as specified in ES EN 2004:2015, i.e. ES EN 2004:2015-2004; 2014.
- The structure will be used in accordance with the design assumptions.
- Design procedures are valid only when the requirements for materials, execution and workmanship given in ES EN 2004:2015-2004; 2014 are satisfied.

1.2.3 Limit State Design method

Limit state design shall be carried out by:

- Setting up structural and load models for relevant ultimate and serviceability limit states to be considered in various design situations and load cases.
- Verifying that the limit states are not exceeded when design values for actions, material properties and geometrical data are used in the models.

1.2.4 Partial factors for materials

Recommended values for γ_c and γ_s for fatigue verification of materials in ultimate limit states, in table 2.1 N of ES EN 2004:2015 should be used. For further information refer, table 2.1N of ES EN 2004:2015-2004; 2014 -part-1-section-2.4.2.4.

**Table 1.1 : Partial safety factors for materials in according to ES EN 2004:2015-2004;
2014**

Design situations	γ_c for concrete	γ_s for reinforcing steel	γ_c for concrete of foundation
Persistent & Transient	1.5	1.15	1.65
Accidental	1.2	1.0	1.32

Note: - Partial factors for concrete γ_c given in table-1.1 for foundations should be multiplied by factors of k_f and the recommended value is 1.1.

For building structures, the partial safety factors used for ultimate limit states are of persistent and transient. The partial safety factors for serviceability limit state are equal to 1.0 and for ultimate limit state, the following are the values:-

Permanent action $\gamma_G = 1.35$, Variable action $\gamma_Q = 1.5$

1.3 Design strength and material property

1.3.1 Design compressive and tensile strengths of concrete according to ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1-section-3.1.6

The design compressive strength is defined as

$$f_{cd} = \alpha_{cc} f_{ck} / \gamma_c, \text{ the recommended value of } \alpha_{cc} \text{ is } 0.85. \text{ Therefore, } f_{cd} = 0.85 f_{ck} / \gamma_c$$

The design tensile strength, f_{ctd} is defined as

$$f_{ctd} = a_{ct} * f_{ctk} / \gamma_c \quad \text{While, } f_{ctk} = 0.7 f_{ctm} \text{ and } f_{ctm} = 0.3 f_{ck}^{2/3}$$

$$f_{ctd} = a_{ct} 0.21 f_{ck}^{2/3} / \gamma_c$$

1.3.2 Design strength of steel according to ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1-section- 3

The application rules for design and detailing in this code of practice are valid for a specified yield strength range, $f_{yk} = 400$ to 600 Mpa. The design strength of steel in tension and compression is defined by:

$$f_{yd} = f_{yk} / \gamma_s \quad \text{For S-400, } f_{yd} = f_{yk} / \gamma_s = 400 / 1.15 = 347.83 \text{ MPa}$$

Concrete and steel of grades C-30/37 and S-400 are used for substructure and column. Whereas, concrete and steel of grades C- 25/30 and S-400 are used for slab, beam and stair.

Table 1.2: Material properties for concrete grades to be used for the building

C-25/30 concrete		C-30/37 concrete	In tension
In compression	In tension	In compression	
$f_{cd} = 0.85 * f_{ck} / \gamma_c$	$f_{ctd} = f_{ck} / \gamma_s$	$f_{cd} = 0.85 * f_{ck} / \gamma_c$	$f_{ctd} = f_{ck} / \gamma_s$ $f_{ctk} = 0.21 f_{ck} (2/3)$ $= 2.0 Mpa$
$f_{cd} = 0.85 * 25 / 1.5$ $= 14.17 Mpa$	$f_{ctk} = 0.21 f_{ck} (2/3)$ $= 1.747 Mpa$	$f_{cd} = 0.85 * 25 / 1.5$ $= 17 Mpa$	$f_{ctm} = 0.3 f_{ck}^{2/3}$
	$f_{ctm} = 0.3 f_{ck}^{2/3}$		$f_{ctm} = 2.49 Mpa$
	$f_{ctm} = 2.21 Mpa$		

Modulus of elasticity (E_{cm}):

$$E_{cm} = 22 \left[(f_{ctm}) / 10 \right]^{0.3} \quad , \quad (f_{cm} \text{ in } Mpa) = f_{ck} + 8 \text{ (Mpa)}$$

For details see table 3 ES EN 2004:2015. -2-part-1-section-3.2

Table 1.3: Modulus of elasticity of steel and concrete for concrete and for steel

f _{ck} (Mpa)	f _{ck} (Mpa)	F _{cm} (Mpa)	Modulus of elasticity (E _{cm})
C-20/25	25	33	31.47Gpa
C-25/30	30	38	32.83Gpa
Steel grade			200 Gpa

Poisson's ratio may be taken equal to 0.2 for un-cracked concrete and 0 for cracked concrete as per ES EN 2004:2015-part-1-section-3.1.3.

Unless more accurate information is available, the linear coefficient of thermal expansion may be taken as $10^{-6} K^{-1}$ as per ES EN 2004:2015-part-2-section-3.1.3.

Density of reinforced concrete is taken as $25KN/m^3$ as per ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1-section-3.1.3. The mean value of density of steel may be assumed to be $7850kg/m^3$ as per ES EN 2004:2015 -2-part-1-section-3.2.7.

Design value of modulus for elasticity of steel, E_s may be taken 200 Gpa as per ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1-section-3.2.7.

1.4 Durability and cover to reinforcement

1.4.1 Definition and importance of Concrete Cover

Concrete cover is the distance between the surface of the reinforcement closest to the nearest concrete surface (including links, stirrups, and surface reinforcement where relevant) and the nearest concrete surface. Therefore, it is necessary to provide concrete cover between the surface of the structural element and reinforcing bar for the following purposes;

- To ensure bonding forces between reinforcement and concrete so that the two element act together.
- To protect of reinforcement from corrosion.
- To protect the reinforcement from fire.

1.4.2 Basic Assumptions

Location of the Project is at Addis Ababa having environmental condition of dry for super-structure, and permanently wet for sub structure.

Corrosion is induced by carbonation. For details refer ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1-section-4.2.

Structural class is 4 for indicative concrete strengths given in Annex- A and the recommended modifications to the structural class are given in Table 4.3N. See ES EN 2004:2015-1-1.

Maximum aggregate size: $d_2=20\text{mm}$ and Concrete type are cast in-situ.

Design life of the structure is 50 years.

Diameter of Stirrups used is 8mm ($\phi 8$) and longitudinal bar are 20mm ($\phi 20$).

1.4.3 Designing of concrete cover according to ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1-section

Steps to determine concrete cover

- **Step-1:** Determine exposure class of structure corresponding to its environmental condition. Environmental conditions are classified according to EBCS EN 2004; 2014-part-2-section-4.2 table 4.1N ANNEX-B.

From environmental conditions of the site, exposure classes will be XC1 and XC2 for both super and sub structures respectively.

Table 1.4: Exposure Classes of super and sub structures corresponding to environmental conditions of the site

Class Designation	Description of the environment	Informative examples where exposure classes may occur
Corrosion induced by carbonation		
XC1	Dry or permanently wet	Concrete inside buildings with low air humidity Concrete permanently submerged in water
XC2	Wet, rarely dry	Concrete surface subjected to long term water contact Many foundations

- **Step-2:** Determine Indicative strength classes for durability of super and sub structure separately corresponding to their class of designation.

Table 1.5: Indicative strength Classes for durability

Corrosion	Carbonation-induced corrosion				Chloride-induced corrosion from sea-water			
Indicative Strength Class	XC1	XC2	XC3	XC4	XD1	XD3	XS1	XS2
	C20/25	C25/30	C30/37		C30/37	C35/45		

Therefore, Indicative minimum strength classes for durability of super -structures are C-20/25 and for Sub-structures use C-25/30.

- **Step-3:** Calculate and compare C_{min} for bonding, stirrup and longitudinal bar,

$$C_{min} = \max \{ C_{min, b}; C_{min, dur}; 10 \text{ mm} \}$$

The greater value for C_{min} satisfying the requirements for both bond and environmental conditions shall govern. The recommended value, for $\Delta C_{dur, add}$, $\Delta C_{dur, st.}$, without further specification, and $\Delta C_{dur, \gamma}$ are zero respectively.

$$C_{min} = \max \{ C_{min, b}; C_{min, dur}; 10 \text{ mm} \}$$

Minimum cover for durability requirement

Value of minimum cover, $C_{min, dur}$, with regards to durability of reinforcement steel is selected based on exposure classes selected above. The details of selection requirements are found on Table 4.4N: ES EN 2004:2015 -2-part-1.

Table 1.6: Environmental Requirements

Environmental Requirement for $C_{min, dur}$ (mm)	
Structural Class	Exposure Class according to Table 4.1

	X0	XC1	XC2	XC4	XD1	XD2	XD3
S4	10	15	25	30	35	40	45

Minimum cover due to bond requirement

Cover requirement for durability $C_{min, dur}$ (mm) =15mm for super-structure and 25mm for sub-structure.

Minimum bond cover for stirrup.

Minimum cover for stirrup, ($\phi 8$): in order to transmit bond forces safely and to ensure adequate compaction of the concrete, the minimum cover should not be less than $C_{min, b}$ given in ES EN 2004:2015-2-part-1section-4.4.1.

Table 1.7: Minimum cover, $C_{min, b}$, requirements with regard to bond

Bond Requirement Arrangement of bars	Minimum cover $C_{min, b}$ *
Separated	Diameter of bar
*: If the nominal maximum aggregate size is greater than 32 mm, $C_{min, b}$, should be increased by 5 mm.	

From the above table, $C_{min, b}$ =8mm for stirrup

Thus, $C_{min} = \max \{C_{min, b}; C_{min, dur}; 10 \text{ mm}\} = \max \{8\text{mm}; 15\text{mm}; 10 \text{ mm}\} = 15\text{mm}$, for stirrups.

Thus, minimum cover for stirrup =8mm+15mm=23mm.

Minimum cover for longitudinal reinforcement (ϕ_{20}) $C_{min, b}$ =16mm

$C_{min} = \max \{C_{min, b}; C_{min, dur}; 10 \text{ mm}\} = \max \{20; 15\text{mm}; 10 \text{ mm}\} = 20\text{mm}$ for longitudinal bar. Generally, greater value for C_{min} satisfying the requirements for both bond and environmental conditions shall govern.

For super-structure

$C_{min} = \max \{\text{case -2; case-3; step-4}\} = \max \{25\text{mm}; 23\text{mm}; 20\text{mm}\} = C_{min} = 25\text{mm}$

For sub-structure

$$C_{min} = \max \{ \text{case -2; case-3; step-4} \} = \max \{ 25\text{mm; } 23\text{mm; } 20\text{mm} \} = 25\text{mm}$$

- **Step-4:** Determine appropriate cover allowance in design for deviation (ΔC_{dev}).

(ΔC_{dev}) is between 5mm to 10mm. Refer ES EN 2004:2015 2-part-1 section-4.4.1: table 4.4.1.3.

Thus, since cast-in situ concrete assumed, value of (ΔC_{dev}) are 10mm for both super and sub-structure in order to ensure quality control.

- **Step-5:** Determine nominal concrete cover specified on drawing

It is defined as a minimum cover, C_{min} plus an allowance in design for deviation, ΔC_{dev}

Mathematically; $C_{nom} = C_{min} + \Delta C_{dev}$

- Case 1-for super-structure like beam, slab and column: $C_{nom} = 20 + 10 = 30\text{mm}$
- Case-2: for sub-structure (foundation): $C_{nom} = 25 + 10 = 35\text{mm}$
- **Step-6:** Determine concrete cover for fire According to EBCS EN 2004; 2014 -2-part-1.2
- Case -1: Minimum slab concrete cover for fire resistance

Table 5.8 provides minimum values of axis distance to the soffit of simply supported slabs for standard fire resistances of R 30 to R 240, Therefore, assume standard fire resistances R240 Because slab depth 170mm thus In two-way spanning slabs a denotes the axis distance of the reinforcement in the lower layer.

Table 1.8: Minimum slab concrete cover for fire resistance

Standard fire resistance	Minimum dimensions Slab thickness	Axis distance; a		
		Two way		One way
		$l_y/l_x \leq 1,5$	$l_y/l_x \leq 2$	
1	2	3	4	5
REI 240	170	65	40	50

The axis distance in Column 4 and 5 for two-way slabs relate to slabs supported at all four edges. Otherwise, they should be treated as one-way spanning slab.

Therefore: $a=65\text{mm} < 127\text{mm}$ SAFE

Where 127mm is effective depth of slab and provided concrete Cover is safe against fire.

- Case -2: minimum beam concrete cover for fire resistance

Beam cross- section are 400mm by 450mm. Minimum dimensions(b_{\min}) and axis distance (a) for simply supported beams made with reinforced and pre-stressed concrete are shown in the table below. For further information refer table 5.5, ES EN 2004:2015.

Table 1.9: minimum beam concrete cover for fire resistance

Standard fire resistance	Minimum dimensions (mm)
REI 180	$b_{\min}= 240 \text{ mm}$ and $a = 80\text{mm}$

Since d' or effective depth= $353\text{mm} > a=80\text{mm}$ concrete cover provided is enough

Therefore, concrete cover for super and sub structure are 35mm, 35mm respectively.

CHAPTER 2 WIND LOAD ANALYSIS AND ROOF DESIGN

2.1 Wind load on roof

2.1.1 Roof characteristics and wind pressure determination

According to ES EN 2004:2015 part 1-4 prEN1991 1-4 2004 article 7.2.4, the roof type for this particular project falls into mono-pitch category. The following are roof characteristics and zones on mono-pitch roof.

Pitch angle = 19° ,

EGA sheet roof, steel purlin and steel truss

Figure 2.1: Wind directions for elevation

Figure 2.2: Wind directions for plan

For this particular project, $Z_e=18.18\text{m}$, $b =27.20$

$e=\min (b=27.20, 2h=36.36) =27.20\text{m}$, $e/4=6.80\text{m}$, $b-e/4=27.20-6.80$, $e/10=2.720$
 $e/2=13.6$ to determine pressure coefficients, the area coverage for the roof sections must

- Case -1 $\Theta=0, 180^\circ$

Table 2.1: Area coverage for respective roof zone for $\Theta=0, 180^\circ$

Sharp eaves	F_{up} and F_{low}	G	H
Area (m^2)	18.5	37	427.988

- Case-2 $\theta=90^\circ$

Table 2.2: Area coverage for respective roof zone for $\Theta= 90^\circ$

Sharp eaves	F_{up} and F_{low}	G	H	I
Area (m^2)	18.5	37	181.218	246.77

Select external pressure coefficients

- Case -1 ($\theta=0^\circ$ and all -ve)

Table 2.3: external pressure coefficients for $\theta=0^\circ$ and all -ve

Sharp eaves	F	G	H
$C_{pe,10}$	-0.79	-0.72	-0.273

- Case-2 ($\theta=0^\circ$ and all +ve)

Table 2.4: external pressure coefficients $\theta=0^\circ$ and all +ve

Sharp eaves	F	G	H
$C_{pe,10}$	0.33	0.33	0.253

- Case -3 ($\theta=180^\circ$)

Table 2.5: external pressure coefficients for $\theta=180^\circ$

Sharp eaves	F	G	H
$C_{pe,10}$	-2.127	-1.17	-0.873

- Case -4($\theta=90^0$)

Table 2.6: external pressure coefficients for $\theta=90^0$

Sharp eaves	Fup	Flow	G	H	I
Cpe,10	-2.32	-1.52	-1.793	-0.853	-0.727

External wind pressure = $q_p * C_{pe}$, where

$$q_p = 484\text{N/m}^2$$

The maximum positive value of external pressure is determined by comparing the results obtained above and are summarized in the following table.

Table 2.7: positive external pressure values

Zone	Cpe	We(kN/m ²)
F	0.33	0.15972
G	0.33	0.15972
H	0.253	0.1224

The Minimum negative value of external pressure is determined by comparing the results obtained above and are summarized in the following table.

Table 2.8: negative external pressure values

zone	C _{pe}	W _e (kN/m ²)
F	-2.127	- 1.0295
G	-1.17	-0.567
H	-0.873	-0.422532
I		

Internal pressure (suction pressure): where, it is not possible, or not considered justified, to estimate μ for a particular case , then C_{pi} should be taken as the more onerous of +0.2 and -0.3.....ES EN 2004:2015-2014 part 1-4 section 7.29 note 2.

$$W_i = C_i * q_{pi}$$

$$=0.2*0.484\text{KN/m}^2=0.0968\text{kN/m}^2 \text{ and } -0.3*0.484 \text{ kN/m}^2=-0.1452\text{kN/m}^2$$

Net pressure = external pressure- internal pressure

$$=0.15972\text{KN/m}^2-(-0.1452\text{KN/m}^2)=0.30492\text{KN/m}^2\text{.....maximum} \quad (+\text{ve})$$

and Minimum negative pressure = $-1.0295-0.0968\text{KN/m}^2 = -1.1263\text{KN/m}^2$

2.2 Roof Design

The procedures for analysis and design of roof and its supporting elements are listed and described as follows;

2.2.1 EGA sheet design

- **Step -1:** Determine the roof cover type to be used

The roof cover to be used is EGA-500

- **Step -2:** Determine the thickness of the sheet (usually obtained from architectural drawings or manufacturer's manuals)

Select EGA-500 with thickness of 0.5mm and length of 1.75m, from KALITY metals products factory manual for cold formed galvanized steel sheet.

The following are its properties.

$$\text{Area}=500\text{mm}^2, \quad \text{Weight (Kg/m)} = 3.92, \quad \text{Moment of inertia (mm}^4) = 99,966$$

$$\text{Width}=0.782\text{m}, \quad \text{Effective width}= 0.712\text{m}$$

- **Step -3:** Determine the load per unit area of the sheet

γ_{steel} is assumed between 77.0- 78.5KN/m³ES EN 2004:2015 part 1-1 table A4

$$\text{Take } 78\text{KN/m}^3, \quad \text{Weight per meter length} = 78\text{KN/m}^3 * 0.5\text{mm} = 0.039\text{KN/m}^2$$

- **Step -4:** Assume the load per unit length or area of coating

Assume coating material weight of 0.7Kg per meter.

$$(0.7\text{Kg/m})/0.782\text{m} = 0.895\text{Kg/m}^2 * 10\text{m/s}^2 = 8.95\text{N/m}^2 = 0.00895\text{KN/m}^2$$

- **Step-5:** Determine the combined load of the sheet and coating per effective width of the sheet

$$0.00895\text{KN/m}^2 + 0.0039\text{KN/m}^2 = 0.048\text{KN/m}^2$$

- **Step -6:** Convert the value obtained at step five to horizontal projection

$$\text{Pitch angle of the roof} = 19^\circ$$

$$0.048\text{KN/m}^2 * \cos 19^\circ = 0.0454\text{KN/m}^2$$

- **Step -7:** Determine the live load on the roof and convert it to horizontal projection

From table 6.9 of ES EN 2004:2015 -1 part 1-1, the roof falls under category H.

ES EN 2004:2015 also suggests a live load of 0.4KN/m^2 , for this specific roof category.

The horizontal projection of this load will be equal to $0.4 * \cos 19^\circ$

- **Step -8:** Determine the positive and negative value of wind loads

*from wind load analysis, the maximum positive pressure = 0.30492KN/m^2

The maximum suction wind pressure = -1.1263KN/m^2

Step -9: Load combo and computation of design loads.

$$P_d = 1.35DL + 1.5LL + 1.6WL_{comp} \quad (1)$$

$$= 1.35 * 0.0454\text{KN/m}^2 + 1.5 * 0.378\text{KN/m}^2 + 1.6 * 0.30492\text{KN/m}^2 \\ = 1.467\text{KN/m}^2$$

Or

$$P_d = 1.35DL + 1.5LL + 1.6WL_{suc} \quad (2)$$

$$= 1.35 * 0.0454\text{KN/m}^2 + 1.5 * 0.378\text{KN/m}^2 + 1.6 * -1.1263\text{KN/m}^2 \\ = 0.4905\text{KN/m}^2$$

The governing design load will be $\max(1.467, -0.4905) = 1.467\text{KN/m}^2$.

- **Step -10:** Compare with section capacity

According to Kality metals products factory manual for cold formed galvanized steel sheet, the uniform load carrying capacity of 1.75m EGA-500 sheet will be = 2.50 Kpa based on strength criteria

= 1.89 Kpa based on deflection criteria

Therefore, the selected sheet satisfies both requirements and is safe to be installed.

- **Step -11:** Return to step -2 if capacity is lower than action effect and iterate until it's greater.

The capacity is greater than the action effect so there will not be a need to return to step-2.

2.2.2 Purlin design

- **Step- 1:** select section to be used

Trail -1: Assume purlin to be used is RT-42, and it has the following properties

Figure 2.3: RT-64 cross-section

Weight per meter =1.68Kg/m, Minimum yield strength =2.4 ton/cm²=240,000Kpa,
Minimum tensile strength =3.2 ton/cm²=320,000Kpa

- **Step -2:** Determine wind load
=0.30492KN/m² maximum positive pressure (obtained previously)
=-1.1447KN/m² maximum negative pressure (obtained previously)
- **Step -3:** Determine dead load supported by purlin

$$\text{EGA sheet load} = 0.0454 \text{KN/m}^2$$

$$W_{\text{RHS}} = 1.68 \text{Kg/m} * 10 \text{m/s}^2 = 0.0168 \text{KN/m}$$

$$\text{Decompose this load in to horizontal projection} = 0.0168 \text{KN/m} * \cos 19^\circ = 0.0159 \text{KN/m}$$

$$\text{Total load supported by the purlin} = 0.0613$$

- **Step -4:** Determine live load

$$0.378 \text{KN/m}^2 \quad \text{obtained previously (i.e. distributed)}$$

$$1 \text{KN} * \cos 19^\circ = 0.945 \text{KN} \quad \text{(i.e. concentrated)}$$

- **Step -5:** Load combination

$$\text{Combo}_1 = 1.35 * DL + 1.5 * LL$$

$$= 1.35 * (W_{\text{RHS}} + W_{\text{EGA}}) + 1.5 * (LL_{\text{distributed}} + LL_{\text{concentrated}})$$

$$= 0.6283 \text{KN} / \text{m}^2 + 0.0215 \text{KN} / \text{m} + 1.4175 \text{KN}$$

$$\text{Combo}_2 = \text{Combo}_1 + 0.9WL_{\text{comp}}$$

$$= 0.9424 \text{KN} / \text{m}^2 + 0.0215 \text{KN} / \text{m} + 1.475 \text{K}$$

$$\text{Combo}_3 = \text{Combo}_1 + 0.9WL_{\text{suc}}$$

$$= 0.6283 \text{KN} / \text{m}^2 + 0.0215 \text{KN} / \text{m} + 1.4175 \text{KN}$$

$$\text{Combo}_4 = 1.35 * DL + 1.5LL_{\text{dist}}$$

$$\text{Combo}_5 = 0.9 * \text{Combo}_4 + 1.5wind_{\text{suc}}$$

$$\text{Combo}_6 = 0.9 * \text{Combo}_4 + 1.5wind_{\text{comp}}$$

- **Step -6:** Determine the load per meter length of purlin

Figure 2.4: Roof (top view)

Middle purlin

The load coming per meter length of purlin

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Line load (W}_1\text{)} &= 1.445 \cdot (0.9424 \text{KN/m}^2) + 0.0215 \text{KN/m} + 1.475 \text{K} \\ &= 1.3352 \text{KN}\end{aligned}$$

- **Step -7:** Analyze the purlin

After modeling and running analysis, stress /capacity ratio exceeds 1.0

Thus, try RT-64 purlin.

Trial -2: RT-64 purlin

Properties; Weight per meter =4.24Kg/m, Minimum yield strength =2.4 ton/cm²=240,000Kpa, Minimum tensile strength =3.2 ton/cm²=320,000Kpa.

After modeling and running analysis on sap-2000, stress /capacity ratio does not exceeds 1.0 and is equal to 0.945. Therefore, one can conclude that the selected purlin section is safe and economical.

2.2.3 Truss design

- **Step -1:** Determine reactions from purlin on the truss joint

From dead load = 0.30kN

From live load = 1.80kN

From wind load (suction) = 2.58kN

From wind load (compression) = 0.69kN

- **Step -2:** Selection of truss type

Due to arrangement and pitch direction, Pratt truss type is suited for this particular roof.

Parametric properties

Figure 2.5: parametric properties of Pratt truss

Top chord length=13.41m height=2.88m

Bottom chord length=13.10m

- **Step -4:** Assume dead load from chip wood and ceiling battens

Dead load of chip wood is 0.256kN/m and dead load of battens is 10% of chip wood load

Total load of chip-wood and ceiling battens= 0.281kN/m

- **Step -5:** Determine section properties for truss elements

Take, RT-128 with thickness of 4 mm for chord and RT-64 for brace. Here are the section properties for RT-128 section

Figure 2.6: Cross-section of RT-128

- **Step -6:** Assign loads on truss joint and check whether the section is adequate (strong) and economical.

The analysis result is attached in the Appendix –A. Since truss cannot transfer moment, the bending moment for all elements appears to be zero.

- **Step -7:** Check for adequacy of the section

Compression resistance of compression elements

$$N_{C,RD} = A f_y / \gamma_{m0}$$

for class 1,2 and 3

$$N_{C,RD} = A_{eff} f_y / \gamma_{m0}$$

for class 4

$$e = \sqrt{(235 / f_y)} = 0.989$$

Classification of compression parts:

$$\text{Web: } C_w / t_w = \frac{120 - (2 * 4) - (2 * 0.1)}{4 \text{ mm}} = 28 \text{ mm}$$

$$28 < 33 * 0.989 = 32.64$$

Class -1

$$\text{Flange: } \frac{C_f}{t_f} = \frac{(80 - 2 * 4 - 2 * 0.1)}{4 \text{ mm}} = 17.95 \text{ mm}$$

$$17.95 < 33 * 0.989 = 32.64$$

Class -1

Therefore, the overall section is class -1

$$N_{C, RD} = Af_y / \gamma_{mo} = \frac{(14.95 * 10^{-4} m^2) * (240 * 10^6 N / m^2)}{1.1} = 326.18 KN$$

$$N_{ED} < N_{C, RD} \quad \text{OK!}$$

b) Check for axial tensile force

For members in tension the design value of axial tension force N_{ED} at each cross-section shall satisfy,

$N_{ED} / N_{t, RD} \leq 1.0$, The design plastic resistance of the cross-section is given by

$$N_{t, RD} = Af_y / \gamma_{mo}, \gamma_{mo} = 1.0 = \frac{(14.95 * 10^{-4}) * (240 * 10^6)}{1.0}$$

$$= 358.8 KN$$

$$N_{ED} / N_{t, RD} = 179.03 KN / 358.8 KN < 1.0 \quad \text{OK!}$$

c) Check for shear

The design value of the shear force V_{Ed} at each cross-section shall satisfy

$$V_{Ed} / V_{c, RD} < 1.0$$

$$V_{c, RD} = \frac{A_v * (f_y * \sqrt{3})}{\gamma_{mo}} \quad A_v = \frac{Ah}{(b+h)}, \text{ for hollow sections}$$

$$= \frac{(14.95 * 10^{-4}) * (0.120)}{(0.08 + 0.120)} = 8.97 * 10^{-4} m^2$$

$$= 17.491 KN / 372.88 KN = 0.047 KN < 1.0 \quad \text{OK!}$$

d) Check against buckling for compression members

Any compression member shall be verified against buckling as follows

$$\frac{N_{Ed}}{N_{b, RD}} \leq 1.0$$

$$N_{b, RD} = X A f_y / \gamma_{m1} \quad \text{for class 1, 2 and 3}$$

$$X A_{eff} f_y / \gamma_{m1} \quad \text{for class 4}$$

$$X = 1 / (\phi + \sqrt{\phi^2 - \lambda^2}) \quad , \text{ Where } \phi = 0.5 * (1 + \alpha (\lambda - 0.2 + \lambda^2))$$

$$\lambda = \sqrt{(A f_y / N_{cr})} \quad \text{for class 1, 2 and 3}$$

$$= \sqrt{A_{eff} * f_y / N_{cr}} \quad \text{for class 4}$$

Table 2.9: Imperfection factors

Buckling curve	ao	a	b	c	d
Imperfection factor a	0.13	0.21	0.34	0.49	0.76

$$\lambda = \sqrt{(A_{fy} / N_{cr})} = \lambda / \lambda \sqrt{(A_{eff} / A)}$$

$$\lambda_1 = 93.9e$$

$$= L_e / i$$

$$\lambda = \sqrt{(14.95 * 10^{-4} \text{m}^2) * (240 * 10^6 \text{N/m}^2) / 180.308 \text{KN}}$$

$$= 1.410$$

In addition, the buckling curve is selected to be a and its corresponding imperfection factor is equal to 0.13. From interpolation the reduction factor will be 0.4165.

After inserting all the values obtained the cross section selected is safe against buckling.

CHAPTER 3 ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF SOLID SLAB (COEFFICIENT METHOD)

3.1 Introduction

Slabs are horizontal structural elements, which transfer service loads to frame elements. There are two types of slabs based on load transferring mechanism. These are one way and two-way slabs. One-way slabs transmit load in one direction while two-way slabs transfer applied load in two directions.

3.2 Procedures for analysis and design of solid slab

The following Basic assumptions are made while a slab is analyzed and designed

Concrete is lightly stressed ($\rho=0.5\%$)

Required steel reinforcement is assumed to be 85% of steel reinforcement provided.

For panel with no partition wall, it has been assumed 1.5KN/m².

3.2.1 Depth determination

The depth “d” of slabs is determined from deflection requirement equation or table as per ES EN 2004:2015-1-1.

- Method-1: formula: $\frac{l}{d} = K \left[11 + 1.5\sqrt{f_{ck}} \frac{\rho_o}{\rho} + 3.2\sqrt{f_{ck}} \left(\frac{\rho_o}{\rho} - 1 \right)^{3/2} \right]$ if $\rho \leq \rho_o$

When other steel grades are used rather than S-500, the values obtained using above expression should be modified by $310/\sigma_s$. It will normally be conservative to assume that:

$$310 / \sigma_s = 500 / (f_{yk} (A_{s,req} / A_{s,prov}))$$

- Method-2: using Table 3.1 of ES EN 2004:2015-1-1

**Table 3.1:- Basic ratios of span/effective depth for reinforced concrete members
without axial compression.**

Structural System	K	Concrete lightly stressed $\rho = 0.5\%$
End span of continuous beam or one-way continuous slab or two-way spanning slab continuous over one long side	1.3	26
Interior span of beam or one-way or two-way spanning slab	1.5	30
Cantilever	0.4	8

Minimum cover requirement for concrete members interior of building for normal habitation or office is 35mm. Use ϕ 10 reinforcement for slab.

For slab: $Total\ depth(D1) = Cover + d2 + \phi / 2 = 117 + 33 + 5 = 164mm$

For cantilever slab: $Total\ depth(D2) = Cover + d1 + \phi / 2 = 191 + 33 + 5 = 226.3mm$

Therefore, it is concluded that depth of a slab and cantilever are 170 mm and 230 mm for ease of construction respectively. The detailed computation is attached in the APPENDIX-B part of this document

3.2.2 Loading

Dead load is composed of the self-weight of the slab itself, weights of partition walls, weight of the finishing and other considerable permanent loads.

Material properties

Table 3.2: Unit weight and thickness of building materials used on the building

Material	Unit weight	Thickness(mm)	Material	Unit weight	Thickness(mm)
Ceramic tile	21	20	HCB	14	20
PVC	16	20	porcelain	23	20
Cement screed	23	30	plastering	23	30

For panels with different finishing material and unit weight, it is better to use average value of unit weight of materials to prevent large reinforcement variation.

$$\gamma_{avg} = \frac{(\gamma_{pvc} \times A_{pvc} + \gamma_{ceramic} \times A_{ceramic})}{A_{pvc} + A_{ceramic}} = \frac{16 \times 15 + 21 \times 3}{15 + 3} = 17.23 \text{ KN / m}^3$$

Slab dead load and live load estimation

Slab dead load estimation

Dead load is the summation of the load that comes from floor finish, cement screed, RC slab and plastering.

$$DL_{slab} = DL_{floor\ finish} + DL_{cement\ screed} + DL_{slab} + DL_{plastering}$$

$$DL_{slab} = (\gamma^*_{t})_{floor\ finish} + (\gamma^*_{t})_{cement\ screed} + (\gamma^*_{t})_{RC\ slab} + (\gamma^*_{t})_{plastering}$$

Live load analysis

Since the building is residential, live load is selected as shown below on table. Details of live load determination are shown in table 6.2 ES EN 2004:2015 -1-1.

Table 3.3: Live load for category A buildings

Categories of loaded areas	Qk(kN/m ²)	Assumed value(kN/m ²)
	Category A	
Floors	1.5 to 2.0	2.0
Balconies	2.5 to 4.0	2.5
Stairs	2.0 to 4.0	2.0

Partition loads are calculated as follows:

$$\text{Wall load (KN / m}^2) = \frac{\sum (L * h * t_{HCB})}{\text{area of panel}}$$

Sample calculation

Where, $\sum L$ - summation of perimeter of wall Partition around the panel

Panel -1

$$: \left((1.03 + 0.8 + 0.325 + 0.98) * 3.06 * 0.2 * 14 \right) / (4 * 4.5) = 1.59 \text{ KN} / \text{m}^2$$

The design load is the total sum of factored live load and dead load from the partition walls and finishing.

According to ES EN 2004:2015, it is recommended to use 1.5KN/m² for panels having wall load less than 1.5 KN/m². The remaining panels have been analyzed with the same procedure to panel-1.

The detailed computation is attached in the Appendix -C part of this document.

3.2.3 Moment and shear Computation

Coefficient method is preferable when:

Shape of slab is rectangular and two way -slab

Four sides supported and Load is assumed to be uniformly distributed

Moment Computation

$$M_{sx} = (\beta_{sx}) * n * l_x^2 \quad \text{and} \quad M_{sy} = (\beta_{sy}) * n * l_y^2$$

- **Case-1:** Two-way slab

Moment computation for panel -1 is illustrated here as a sample computation.

Figure 3.1: Plan view of panel-1

$$Pd = 1.35Gk + 1.5Qk = 1.35 * 7.4446 + 1.5 * 2 = 13.05 \text{ kN} / \text{m}^2$$

Using the coefficient table, bending moment coefficients for rectangular panels supported on four sides with provision for torsion at corners can be determined.

$$\beta_{sx} = 0.057; M_{sx} = \beta_{sx} * Pd * Lx^2 = 0.057 * 13.05 * 4^2 = 11.9 \text{ KNm}$$

$$\beta_{sx} = 0.043; M_{fx} = \beta_{sx} * P_d * L_x^2; = 0.043 * 13.05 * 4^2 = 8.97 \text{ KNm}$$

$$\beta_{sy} = 0.034; M_{fy} = \beta_{sy} * P_d * L_y^2; = 0.034 * 13.05 * 4^2 = 7.09 \text{ KNm}$$

- **Case-2:** One-way slab:

Analysis of one-way slab is done by taking one-meter strip along the load transferring direction (i.e. along the shortest direction). Computations are shown here under for panel-7 which is one of the one way panels on the slab.

Figure 3.2:- Plan view and loading on panel-7

$$P_d = 1.35DL + 1.5LL = 12.882 \text{ KNm} / m,$$

$$M_f = 9p_d l^2 / 128 = 9 * 12.882 * 1.85^2 / 128 = 3.31 \text{ KNm} / m$$

And $M_s = P_d l^2 / 8 = 12.882 * 1.85^2 / 8 = 5.51 \text{ KNm} / m$

$$M_f = 9p_d l^2 / 128 = 9 * 12.882 * 1.85^2 / 128 = 3.31 \text{ KNm} / m$$

The same procedure is followed to determine all remaining panels moments.

The detailed calculation for moment computation is carried out and is attached in the Appendix-d₁ part of this document.

- **Case-3:** Cantilever

Similar to the analysis of one-way slab, the analysis of the cantilever is done by taking 1m strip and analyzing by computing the moment.

For instance computation for cantilever-7

$$Pd = 1.35DL + 1.5LL = 1.35 * 8.82 + 1.5 * 2 = 15.657 \text{ KN} / m$$

a) Plan view of cantilever -7 b) loading on cantilever -7

Figure 3.3: cantilever -7

Taking a 1-m strip and analyzing the structure looks like the following:

Therefore taking a section somewhere and analyze the cantilever.

$$M = wl^2 / 2 = 15.657 * 2.08^2 / 2 = 33.86 \text{ KN-m} / m$$

The detailed calculation of moments for cantilever panels is also attached with the APPENDIX-D₂ part of this document.

3.2.4 Redistribution of support moments and adjustment of span moments.

Support Moment Adjustment

For a continuous support, there two support moments which are different in magnitude and these moments should be adjusted. Therefore, the difference is distributed based on their stiffness on either side of the support to equalize their moments.

There are two cases:

- **Case-1**:- $\Delta M < 20\%$, of the larger moment, the design moment is the average of the two.
- **Case-2**:- If $\Delta M \geq 20\%$, then the unbalanced moment is distributed based on their stiffness.

Unbalanced moment is distributed using the moment distribution method.

Relative stiffness of each panel shall be taken proportional to its gross moment of inertia divided by the smaller span.

In this method, consideration of the effects of changes of support moments is limited to the adjacent spans.

For instance, Support moment adjustment, between Panel -1 and Panel -2

For panel – 1 $M_{sy} = 9.40$ and for panel – 2 $M_{sy} = 7.73$

The difference of the moments is equal to $\Delta M = 9.40 - 7.73 = 1.67$

$$\Delta M\% = 1.67 / 9.40 * 100 = 17.78\% < 20\%$$

Therefore taking the average, $M_{adjusted} = (7.7257243 + 9.3961512) / 2 = 8.565$

For instance, Support moment adjustment, Between Panel -1 and Panel -7

For panel – 1: $M_{sx} = 11.9$ and for panel – 7: $M_{sx} = 5.51 \text{KNm}$

The difference of the moments is equal to $\Delta M = 11.9 - 5.51 = 6.39 \text{KNm}$

$$\Delta M\% = 6.39 / 11.9 * 100 = 53.7\% > 20\% \text{ therefore Moment adjustment needed.}$$

Span moment adjustment

If the moment in the adjusted support decreases, the span moments are increased to compensate for the changes in the support moments. If a support moment is increased, no adjustment shall be made to the span moments.

$$Adjusted = (M_{support} + M_{span}) - M_{new}$$

The detailed moment adjustment is attached with Appendix-D₃

3.2.5 Design for flexure

Generally, Procedures for determining flexural reinforcement are as follows

Determine μ_{sd} , from the formula $\mu_{sd} = \frac{M_{sd}}{fcd * bd^2}$

Compare μ_{sd} with the value μ_{sd}^* so that $\mu_{sd} < \mu_{sd}^*$

If $\mu_{sd} < \mu_{sd}^*$, no compression reinforcement required. But if $\mu_{sd} > \mu_{sd}^*$ compression reinforcement required which is not the case for typical slabs.

Obtain lever arm Kz from table or chart.

Compute Z from the relation $Kz = \frac{z}{d}$

Calculate tension reinforcement required from (Actual): $A_s = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * z}$

Check minimum reinforcement requirement (to be safe): $A_{s,min} = \frac{0.26 f_{ctm} b d}{f_{yk}}$

Check maximum reinforcement requirements (to be economical): $0.031bd$

For instance, for panel-1: effective slab depth Slab depth = 134.66mm $M_{sd} = 10.95 KNm$

$$\mu_{sd} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{cd} * b d^2} = 10.95 * 10^6 / (14.166 * 1000 * 134.66^2) = 0.0267$$

Now read kz from the table given in the ES EN 2004:2015 1-1 Table 2-2: $Kz = 0.98165$

$$K_z * d = 0.98165 * 134.66 = 166.8mm$$

$$A_{s, provided} = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \cdot AS, \max = 0.031bd \\ A_{s, actual} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * z} = 188.9mm^2 \end{array} \right\} = 188,9mm^2$$

Therefore; area of steel required = $A_s = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * Z} = 10.95 * 10^6 / 347.9 * 166.88 = 188.6mm^2$

Check for minimum reinforcement.

$$A_{s,min} = \frac{0.26 f_{ctm} b d}{f_{yk}} = 272mm^2, \text{ take minimum reinforcement.}$$

$$\text{Thus, } A_s, \text{ provided} = \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_{s, \min} = \frac{0.26 f_{ct} m b d}{f_{yk}} = 272 \text{ mm}^2, \\ A_{s, \text{actual}} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * z} = 188.9 \text{ mm}^2 \end{array} \right\} = 272 \text{ mm}^2 \text{ for safety}$$

$$\text{and } A_s, \text{ provided} = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_{s, \max} = 0.031 b d \\ A_{s, \text{actual}} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * z} = 188.9 \text{ mm}^2 \end{array} \right\} = 188.9 \text{ mm}^2 \text{ for economical}$$

Detailed reinforcement provision is given in the APPENDIX-E₁ part of this document.

According to ES EN 2004:2015, the ratio of secondary reinforcement to the main reinforcement for temperature and shrinkage shall be at least equal to 0.2 * transverse reinforcement (Use Ø 8). Or S-300

$$\text{Secondary reinforcement} = 20\% A_{s \text{ main}} = 0.2 * 272 = 55 \text{ mm}^2$$

Thus, Provide Ø8c/c 400

3.2.6 Check shear capacity of the slab

Procedures for design of shear: -

Determine V_{ED} from the coefficient method

$$\text{Determine } K \text{ from } k = 1 + \sqrt{\frac{200}{d}} \leq 2.0 \quad \text{with } d \text{ in mm } \rho = \frac{A_{sl}}{b_w d} \leq 0.02$$

Determine design value for the shear resistance

Determine maximum shear resistance (capacity).

$$V_{RD,C} = \text{Max} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} C_{RD,C} * K (1000 \rho f_{ck})^{\frac{1}{3}} + k_1 \delta_{cp} b_w d \\ V_{\min} + k_1 \delta_{cp} b_w d = V_{RD,\min} \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\text{Where, } V_{\min} = 0.035 K^{\frac{3}{2}} f_{ck}^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ and } k_1 = 0.15 \quad C_{RD,C} = \frac{0.18}{\gamma_c} = \frac{0.18}{1.5} = 0.12$$

Compare result of step-1 and step-3

Taking minimum reinforcement:

$$\rho = \frac{A_s}{bwd} = 0.00168 \quad \text{and} \quad \delta cp = \frac{N_{ED}}{A_s} < 0.2 fcd = 0$$

\emptyset_{10} c/c 260

Thus, maximum shear resistance of slab is

$$V_{RD} = \text{MAX} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_{RD,C} = 0.12K(1000\rho fck)^{\frac{1}{3}}b_w d \\ V_{RD,min} = V_{min} = 0.035 fck^{\frac{1}{2}}k^{\frac{3}{2}}b_w d \end{array} \right\} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_{RD,C} = (0.12 * 2(1000)(1.68 * 10^{-3})(30)^{\frac{1}{3}} * 1m * 0.16) = 67.4 \\ = 87.253 \end{array} \right\} = 87.25 KN$$

And acting (applied) maximum shear force of slab (V_{ED}) are obtained as follows

Figure 3.4: Load distribution pattern of slabs

Since, width of beam ($b_w = 0.4m$) and maximum depth of slab 161mm

The designed load will be $P_d = 1.35D_L + 1.5L_L = 13.13 \text{ KN/m}^2$

$$V_{sd} = P_d(0.5l_n - d)b_w = 13.13 * (.5 * 4.1 - .161) = 25 \text{ KN} \quad \text{and}$$

Effective length $l_n = 4.5 - 0.4 = 4.1m$

$$V_{sd} = 23 \text{ KN}$$

Applied slab shear.

Since $V_{RD,C} > V_{SD}$ the section is adequate!

Shear load calculation

- **Case-1:** two-way slab

The load transfer coefficients are read from ES EN 2004:2015, Table3-3 Shear force coefficients.

Figure 3.5: plan view of panel-1

For uniformly loaded rectangular panels supported on four sides with provision for torsion at corners are used. The design load on a beam determined in the above may be taken as the maximum shear in the slab at the support, which will be distributed on 75% of the span of the beam. This is done by calculation of shear force using co-efficient method and Support conditions –are two adjacent edge discontinuous $ly/lx=4.5/4=1.125<2$ so that panel is treated as two way slab.

Sample of shear calculation-panel-1:

General formula, $V_{sy} = \beta_{vy} * n * Lx$ and $V_{sx} = \beta_{vx} * n * Lx$

Table 3.4: sample of shear computation

load	Factored shear force for dead	Factored shear force for live load
	$V_{sy,c} = \beta_{vy,c} * n * Lx = .445 * 10.04 * 4 = 17.78 KN / m$	$V_{sy,c} = \beta_{vy,c} * n * Lx = .4 * 3 * 4 = 5.34 KN / m$
	$V_{sx,c} = \beta_{vx,c} * n * Lx = .4 * 10.04 * 4 = 16.064 KN / m$	$V_{sx,c} = \beta_{vx,c} * n * Lx = .4 * 3 * 4 = 5.34 KN / m$
	$V_{sx,d} = \beta_{sx,d} * n * Lx = .295 * 10.04 * 4 = 11.88 KN / m$	$V_{sx,d} = \beta_{sx,d} * n * Lx = .295 * 3 * 4 = 3.54 KN / m$
	$V_{sy,d} = \beta_{vy,d} * n * Lx = .26 * 10.04 * 4 = 10.4512 KN / m$	$V_{sy,d} = \beta_{vy,d} * n * Lx = .26 * 3 * 4 = 3.12 KN / m$

- **Case-2:** one-way slab

One-way slabs transmit their load in shorter direction. Whereas in longer direction negligible. Take 1m strip in shorter direction for analyze purpose.

Figure 3.6 : top view for panel -7

Sample of shear calculation in shorter direction-panel-7

Panel-7: Sample of shear for dead load =9.9KN/m²

Figure 3.7: shear force from dead loading for panel -7

Panel-7: Sample of shear for live load=3KN/m²

Figure 3.8: shear force from live loading for panel - 7

Sample of shear for dead load =9.9kN/ m² and Sample of shear for live load=3kN/m²

- **Case-3:** Cantilever-8

Cantilever transmits their load in shorter direction. Whereas in longer direction negligible take 1m strip in shorter direction

Figure 3.9: plan view for cantilever -8

Cantilever-8: Sample of shear for dead load =11.88kN/m

Figure 3.10: Shear force from dead loading for cantilever-8

Cantilever-8: Sample of shear for live load=3.75kN/m

$$V_s(\text{dead}) = (n * lx) = 11.88 * 2.25 = 26.75 \text{KN} / m \text{ and}$$

$$V_s(\text{live}) = (n * lx) = 3.75 * 2.25 = 8.34 \text{KN} / m$$

The details of Load transferred from two way slabs to beams are attached in the Appendix-F₁ part of this document.

Case-2: For one-way slab and cantilever, load is transferred only in shorter direction and in longer direction neglect. However, summary of shear force for two-way slab are as follows

The load transferred to the beams from the cantilever and one way slabs is also attached in the Appendix-F₂ part of this document.

3.3 Design of Ground floor slab

Since, ground floor slab directly rests on ground; no bending moment will be induced. Thus, only minimum reinforcement should be provided in both X and Y direction for purpose of preventing shrinkage of slab. i.e.

Minimum reinforcement requirement: $A_{s,min} = \frac{0.26 f_{ct} m b d}{f_{yk}} < 0.031 b d$ and

$$A_{s,min} = 272 \text{ mm}^2$$

Therefore provided $\varnothing 10$ c/c 260

3.4 Water tanker slab analysis and Design

Since $(L_y / L_x) < 2$ ($L_y / L_x) < 2$ treated as two-way-Simply support slab

Figure 3.11:-tanker slab top view

Procedure of water tanker slab analysis.

- **Step-1:** Determine slab depth: (see 7.1N ES EN 2004:2015-2 -Part1-1-2)

$$D_{Provide} = d + cover + dia / 2 = 183 \text{ mm} \quad \text{Therefore, Take} = 200 \text{ mm}$$

- **Step-2:** Loading
 - a) Determine load (weight) of tanker.

Suppose, number bedroom for typical floor is 12 including ground floor, but, it has been assuming each room occupies 1 or 2 guests, total-Number of guest will be $60 * 2 = 120$

Number of person/day = Average no of staff = 25

Number of cooker and server = 32

Therefore, Total number of person per day = $120 + 25 + 32 = 177$ person/day.

Assuming water consumed per day = 140L/day For cooking, hygiene and drink.

Therefore, water required per day = $177 * 140L = 24780$ l/day.

Water volume taken for safety = 1000l/day

noticed that total number of floor equal to 5.

Generally, from above table, total water volume per day (V_T) = $24780 + 1000 = 25780$ l/day.

For G+4. Since there are two water tanker on top of Building it's assumed in to two part for design purpose by dividing total capacity of volume.

$$\text{That-means, } V_1 = V_T / 2 = V_2 = 12890L = 12.89m^3$$

Where: V_1, V_2 are volume of water tanker to left side and right side respectively.

$$h = V_1 / \pi r^2 = 12.89 / \pi (3.5)^2 = 1.83m$$

Thus, assuming tanker as PVC cylindrical with radius of 1.3m

$$\text{weight of water inside tanker} = \gamma_w * V_w = 9.81 * V_1 = 9.81 * 12.89 = 126.45KN$$

$$\text{Weight of PVC cylindrical} = \gamma_{pvc} * V_1 = 3.36 * 12.89 = 43.31KN$$

Total mass of tanker on slab $=126.45+43.31=169.76\text{KN}$

Distributed load of tanker on slab $=169.76/4.5*4.5=8.383\text{KN/m}^2$.

Dead load

$$DL = DL_{FF} + DL_{CS} + DL_{RCSLAB} + DL_{WATER\ TANKER}$$

$$= (\gamma_{FF} * t_{ff}) + (\gamma_{cs} * t_{cs}) + (\gamma_c * S_{lab}) + 8.383$$

$$=(23*0.03) + (23*0.03) + (25*0.2) + 8.383 = 17\text{KN} / \text{m}^2$$

Live load and wind load:

By comparing value obtained on wind load and live load calculation, maximum shall govern load i.e. live load is governing load where, $LL=0.5\text{KN/m}^2$

Load combination

$$Pd = 1.3GK + 1.5QK = 1.3(17) + 1.5(0.5) = 22.85\text{KN} / \text{m}^2$$

Since, equivalent wall distributed load/design load < 20%, it is better to use coefficient method. Panel-1' (on roof) left tanker

- **Step-3:** Shear load and Moment calculation

Panel-1' (on roof) left tanker

Table 3.5: Load and coefficients on Panel-1' (on roof) left tanker

Ly	Lx	Ly/Lx	Dead load	live load	coefficient		Shear from Dead load	Shear from Live load
4.5	4.4	1.01	17	0.5	0.33	L	24.7	0.73
4.5	4.4	1.01	17	0.5	0.33	B	24.7	0.73
4.5	4.4	1.01	17	0.5	0.33	T	24.7	0.73
4.5	4.4	1.01	17	0.5	0.33	R	24.7	0.73

Table 3.6: load and coefficients on Panel-2' (on roof) Right tanker

Ly	Lx	Ly/Lx	Dead load	Live load	Coefficient	Shear force due Dead load	Shear force Live load
4.5	4.4	1.01	17	0.5	0.33	24.7	0.73
4.5	4.4	1.01	17	0.5	0.33	24.7	0.73
4.5	4.4	1.01	17	0.5	0.33	24.7	0.73
4.5	4.4	1.01	17	0.5	0.33	24.7	0.73

Moment computation and design of roof tank slab is executed as follows:

Figure 3.12: Moment computation

Panel	lx	ly	ly/lx	Factored Dead load	Factored live load	Design load	coefficients	Moment(KN-m)
1'	4.5	4.5	1.125	22.95	0.75	23.7	$\beta_{sx}=0.057$	$M_{sx}=27.1$
	4.5	4.5	1.125	22.95	0.75	13.0	$\beta_{fx}=0.043$	$M_{fx}=11.4$
	4.5	4.5	1.125	22.95	0.75	13.0	$\beta_{sy}=0.045$	$M_{sy}=11.9$
	4.5	4.5	1.125	22.95	0.75	13.0	$\beta_{fy}=0.034$	$M_{fy}=9$

Step-4: Reinforcement Calculation

for support moment $M_{sx}=27.1\text{KNm}$

$$\mu_{sd} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{cd} * b d^2} = \frac{27.1 * 10^6}{(14.166 * 1000 * 164.66^2)} = 0.07567$$

Now corresponding V_{sd} read k_z from the table given in the ES EN 2004:20151-1 Table 2-2: $K_z=0.96165$

$$Z = K_z * d = 0.96165 * 164.66 = 158\text{mm}$$

$$A_{s, provided} = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \cdot A_{s, max} = 0.031bd = 5084\text{mm}^2 \\ A_{s, actual} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * z} = 506\text{mm}^2 \end{array} \right\} = 506\text{mm}^2$$

Therefore; area of steel required = $A_s = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * Z} = \frac{27.1 * 10^6}{347.9 * 164} = 506\text{mm}^2$

Check for minimum reinforcement.

$$A_{s,\min} = \frac{0.26 f_{ct} m b d}{f_{yk}} = 272 \text{ mm}^2, \text{ take minimum reinforcement.}$$

$$\text{Thus, } A_{s,\text{provided}} = \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_{s,\min} = \frac{0.26 f_{ct} m b d}{f_{yk}} = 272 \text{ mm}^2, \\ A_{s,\text{actual}} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * z} = 506 \text{ mm}^2 \end{array} \right\} = 506 \text{ mm}^2 \text{ for safety}$$

$$\text{and } A_{s,\text{provided}} = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_{s,\max} = 0.031 b d \\ A_{s,\text{actual}} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * z} = 506 \text{ mm}^2 \end{array} \right\} = 506 \text{ mm}^2 \text{ for economical}$$

Detailed reinforcement provision is given in the Appendix-E₁ part of this document.

According to ES EN 2004:2015, the ratio of secondary reinforcement to the main reinforcement for temperature and shrinkage shall be at least equal to 0.2 * transverse reinforcement (Use Ø 8).

CHAPTER 4 ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF STAIR –CASE

4.1 Introduction

Stair case analysis and design is similar to slabs. It involves the steps followed when analysis and design slabs. The inclined configuration is analyzed by projecting the loads on a horizontal plane. The stair has three flights. Each has their own dimension and support condition.

The stair from ground level to 1.53m height can be seen as follows.

Figure 4.1: Plan view of the stair

Section A-A Landing to 1st flight up to half building (1.53)

Section B-B Landing to 2nd flight up to half building (3.06)

Figure 4.2: Sectional view of stair A-A

Figure 4.3: Section view of stair B-B

Necessary dimension of staircase and available data are the following

Thickness of porcelain=30mm	Riser height =190mm
number of thread=8	Width of thread=280mm
Material: C-30 OR C-25/30 S-400 Φ 12 bar and 33mm cover	Number of riser=9
Thickness of plastering=15mm	number of thread=10
Thickness of cements screed=30mm	

4.2 Analysis and Design of typical floor stair

- **Step-1:** Design strength:

$$f_{cd} = 0.85 * f_{ck} / \gamma_c = 14.16 \text{MPa} \text{ and } 400 / 1.15 = 347.83 \text{Mpa}$$

- **Step-2:** Depth-determination

$$d \geq l_y / 29.17 = 4.5 / 29.17 = 0.15 \text{m} \quad d \geq 154 \text{mm}$$

$D = d + \text{cover} + \Phi / 2 = 154 + 25 + 12 / 2 = 185 \text{mm}$, for construction ease, take=200mm

$$\text{Thus, } D_{\text{provide}} = D - \text{Cover} - \Phi / 2 = 200 - 33 - 12 / 2 = 161 \text{mm}$$

Case-1: Estimation of Dead load by taking 1m strip. Hence, its analysis is same to one-way slab analysis.

• **Step -3:** Loading

Table 4.1: Dead load of slopping portion

slopping portion	Base plastering	$t_p * \gamma_p * 1m / \cos\theta = 0.02 * 23 * 1 / \cos 34 = 0.556 KN / m$
	Thread: floor-finish (porcelain)	$0.03 * 23 * 1 = 0.69 KN / m$
	Thread: cement screed	$0.02 * 23 * 1 = 0.69 KN / m$
	Riser: floor-finish (porcelain)	$0.03 * 23 * 0.19 * 1 * 9 / 2.24 = 0.526 kN / m$
	Riser: floor-cement screed	$0.02 * 230.19 * 1 * 9 / 2.24 = 0.35 KN / m$
	Due to steps per meter width	$0.5(0.19 * 0.28) * 1 * 25 kN / m^3 / 0.3 = 2.37 KN / m$

Total un-factored dead load on slopping portion

$$= 6.04 + 0.556 + 0.69 + 0.69 + 0.526 + 0.35 + 2.37 = 11.256 KN / m$$

Landing portion (landing- 1 and landing-2)

Table 4.2: Dead load of landing portion

Landing portions	Landing slab	$D * \gamma_c * 1m = 0.2 * 25 * 1 = 5 KN / m$
		$tp * \gamma_p * 1 = 0.03 * 23 * 1 = 0.69 KN / m$
		$tcs * \gamma_{cs} * 1 = 0.03 * 23 * 1 = 0.69 KN / m$
		$tpc * \gamma_{pc} * 1 = 0.03 * 23 * 1 = 0.69 KN / m$

Total un-factored dead-load on slopping portion=7.07KN/m

Case-2: Live load:-stair-category-A, QK is 3KN/m²-ES EN 2004:2015-1991-1-part-6.3.1.21 table 7.2

Thus, Total live load on stair case =3KN/m²*1=3KN/m

Table 4.3: Loading summary

element	Dead load (KN/m)			Live load(KN/m)
	Un-factored	factored	Un-factored	Factored
Soffit	11.25	15.24	3	4.5
landing	7.07	9.54	3	4.5

Design Load: For Flight = $1.35Gk + 1.5Qk = 1.35 * 11.25 + 1.5 * 3 = 19.7 KN / m$

for Landing = $1.35Gk + 1.5Qk = 1.35 * 7.07 + 1.5 * 3 = 14.04 KN / m$

- **Step-4:** Analyze the stair

Case-1-dead load

Figure 4.4: Dead loading

Figure 4.5: Shear force diagram form dead load

Figure 4.6: Bending moment diagram for dead load

Case-2 for live load

Loading

Figure 4.7: Live loading

Figure 4.8: Shear force from live load

Figure 4.9: Bending moment from live loading

- **Step-5:** Moment determination and reinforcement calculation

Design moment (M_{sd} kNm), M_{sd} is calculated using 1m strip width

Table 4.4: Design Moment (Msd) result for corresponding span loading

Element	Msd (KN-m) Due to Dead load.	Msd(KN-m)Due to live load	Total design Span moment	Support moment
Section A-A(fist fight)	34.64	11.34	46	0
SECTIONB-B(second flight)	34.84	11.34	46	0

Thus, it has been concluded that, the above calculation can hold for 1st floor to 4th Floor.

- **Step-6:** Checking the adequacy

Concrete, C-30, f_{cd} (Mpa) = 14.16mpa, b (mm) = 1000, μ_{sd} =0.295, M_{sd} =46kN-m

$$d_{section} = \frac{\sqrt{M_{sd}}}{\sqrt{f_{cd} * b * \nu_{sd}}} = 105mm$$

Since, $D_{provided}$ =161mm greater than minimum depth of section (105mm).

The provided depth is OK!

- **Step-7:** Design for flexural reinforcement

Figure 4.10: Depths d_1 and d_2 in section view

Stair Section A-A on First floor provided depth (D) =200mm and total design Span moment (M_{sd} =46 KN-m)

Reinforcement at span (M_{sd} =46 KN-m)

$$d = D - Cover - \phi / 2 = 200 - 33 - 12 / 2 = 161mm \text{ and } d_2 = D - Cover - \phi / 2 - \phi = 149mm$$

$$a_s = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} = \frac{3.14 * 12 * 12}{4} = 113.04mm^2$$

a) Design for flexural reinforcement longitudinal reinforcement

Section A-A / Section A-B

Reinforcement Grade S-400, Ø (mm) 12, Design reinforcement using design chart
number-1(ES EN 2004:2015 Part-2)

$$\mu_{sd} = M_{sd} / f_{cd} * b * d^2 = 46000N - m / (14.17 * 1m * 161^2) = 0.125$$

since $\mu_{sd} < \mu_{sd, lim} = 0.125 < 0.295$

Note μ_{sd}, lim is depend on grade of concrete. That means $\mu_{sd}, lim = 0.295$ valid for
only C-12/15 up to C-50/60. Therefore, from design chart, $k_z = 0.93$ by interpolation.

$$A_s = M_{sd} / K_z * d * f_{yd} = 882mm^2$$

b) Minimum reinforcement

$$A_{S \min} = \max = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (0.26 f_{ctm} * b * d) / f_{yk} = 231mm^2 \\ 0.031b * d = 5501mm^2 \end{array} \right\} = 231mm^2$$

Check : $A_s > A_{s \min}$ section ok!!!

Calculating spacing (mm):

$$\max = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2D = 2 * 200 = 400 \\ 350mm \\ bas / A_s = (1000 * 113) / 882 = 128.8 \end{array} \right\} = 128.8mm$$

Use Ø 12 c/c 120

According to ES EN 2004:2015, the ratio of secondary reinforcement to the main
reinforcement for temperature and shrinkage shall be at least equal to 0.2.0r transverse
reinforcement (Use Ø 8)

Table 4.5: Reinforcement calculation (Flight A form the ground to landing (G to l))

Section A-A	Ast(mm ²)	Asmin	Use Ast	S(mm)	Use S(mm)
	56	231	231	120	400

Table 4.6: Reinforcement calculation (Flight B from the Landing to flight (L to F))

Section A-A	Ast(mm ²)	Asmin	Use Ast	S(mm)	Use S(mm)
	56	231	231	120	400

- **Step-8:** Detailing

Detailing for stair is done and shown at the eighth chapter of this document.

4.3 Analysis and Design of ground floor stair

The steps followed for design and analysis of ground floor stairs are the same with analysis and design of stair for typical floor.

Design moment (Msd (KN.m), Msd is calculated using 1m strip width

Table 4.7: Moment result for ground stair

Element	Design-moment (Msd K kN.m)Due to Dead load(span--moment	Design-moment (Ms KN.m) Due-to-live-load (span-moment)	Total design Span moment	Support moment
Section Ground stair (fist fight)	16.9	6.29	23.2	0

- **Step-2:** Checking the adequacy

Material properties for C-30

Concrete C-30, f_{cd} (Mpa) = 14.16mpa, b (mm) = 1000, μ_{sd} =0.295, M_{sd} =23.2kN-m

$$d_{section} = \frac{\sqrt{M_{sd}}}{\sqrt{f_{cd} * b * \nu_{sd}}} = 78mm$$

The provided depth is OK!

- **Step-3:** Reinforcement calculation

Reinforcement at span ($M_{sd}=23\text{KN-m}$)

Reinforcement Longitudinal Reinforcement Grade S-400, \emptyset (mm) 12, chart no-1(ES EN 2004:2015 Part-2)

$$\text{since } \mu_{sd} < \mu_{sd, \text{lim}} = 0.125 < 0.295 \text{ ok!!!}$$

Therefore, from design chart, $k_z = 0.9635$ by interpolation

$$A_s = M_{sd} / K_z * d * f_{yd} = 429\text{mm}^2$$

Minimum reinforcement

$$A_{s, \text{min}} = \max = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (0.26 f_{ctm} * b * d) / f_{yk} = 231\text{mm}^2 \\ 0.031b * d = 5501\text{mm}^2 \end{array} \right\} = 231\text{mm}^2$$

Therefore, provided \emptyset 12 c/c 260

Reinforcement calculation (Flight A form the ground to landing (G to l))

Table 4.8: Reinforcement calculation (Flight A form the ground to landing (G to l))

Flight - A	$A_{st}(\text{mm}^2)$	$A_{s, \text{min}}$	Use $A_{s, t}$	S(mm)	Use S(mm)
	47	231	231	231	400

- **Step-5:** Detailing

The number and diameter of bars used for stair are attached in the 8th chapter of this paper.

CHAPTER 5 LATERAL LOAD AND STABILITY ANALYSIS

In designing buildings, different modes of forces should be considered and analyzed. Out of these forces, lateral forces are those that has to be given due attention. Thus, lateral loads to be considered for the design of a building are: -

Earth quake load and

Wind load

NOTE: The analysis for both will be done and the critical load condition will be considered for the Design

5.1 Wind load determination

In simple terms, wind is a moving air having an effect on structures that could be described in terms of pressure or force. The pressure could be applied directly on the external walls of the structure or through the porous spaces of the walls. It could also be applied indirectly on the interior portion of the walls; and is applied in the direction normal to the surfaces. It is crystal clear that wind varies both spatially and seasonally and consequently the pressure resulting from it will also vary.

5.1.1 Method of Analysis

There are two methods of analysis for wind load computation; the first one is Quasi-static analysis, which will not consider dynamic excitation to structural properties. The other one, which is the exact inverse of quasi-static analysis, is dynamic analysis. The choice among the two depends on the shape, height and type of the structure to be built. Dynamic coefficient relates all these parameters. If the structure has a height, less than 200m, then quasi-static method of analysis will come into play.

For this specific project, the total height from ground level to the uppermost element of the structure is measured to be 18.18m, which is excessively, much less than 200m and forcing the analysis to be carried on using quasi-static method of analysis.

General conditions of the site:

Height of building is equals to 181.8m excluding foundation depth

Terrain category; IV (urban areas in which at least 15% of the surface is covered with buildings and their average height exceeds 15m, as per EBCS ES EN 2004:2015 ;2014 part 1-4 table 4.1).

5.1.2 Wind Analysis

Case -1 when wind direction $\theta=180^0$

Wind pressure on building face

The wind pressure on external walls of buildings according to EBCS 1991 part 1-4 4 is given by the following formula:

$$W_e = q_p(z_e) * c p_e \quad \text{ES EN 2004:2015 part 1-4 section 5.2}$$

According to ES EN 2004:2015-2004; 2014; the peak velocity is in turn obtained from the

$$q_p(z_e) = C_e(z) * q_b \quad \text{ES EN 2004:2015 1991 Part 1-4 section 4.5}$$

Assuming a terrain category of class IV, and taking total height of the building to be 18.18m, the exposure factor becomes 1.6.

$$q_b = 1/2 * \rho * V_b^2 \quad \text{ES EN 2004:2015 Part 1-4 equation 4.10}$$

$$V_b = C_{dir} * C_{season} * V_{bo} \quad \text{ES EN 2004 :2015 Part 1-4 section 4.2}$$

By putting all the values, the base wind pressure q_b will be equal to 302.5 N/m^2

The peak wind velocity at reference height z (q_p) from the ground elevation will be equal to $1.6 * 302.5 \text{ N/m}^2 = 484 \text{ N/m}^2 = 0.484 \text{ KN/m}^2$

5.1.3 Wall division

ES EN 2004:2015-1991 part 1-4 prEN1991 1-4 2004 categorizes buildings into three conditions based on height to base ratio.

- | | |
|-------------------------------|--|
| Case-1: when $h < b$ | the building is considered to be one part |
| Case -2: when $b < h \leq 2b$ | the building is considered to be two part |
| Case -3: when $h > 2b$ | the building is considered to be multiple part |

For this specific project, height = 18.18m and $b = 27.20\text{m}$. So the structure falls into case -1 and considered to be one part. Three cases also exist for elevation division according to ES EN 2004:2015 part 1-4 figure 7.5,

Case -1: elevation for $e < d$

Case -2: elevation for $e \geq d$

Case -3: elevation for $e \geq 5d$

For this particular project, $d = 24.10\text{m}$ and $b = 27.20\text{m}$, $e = \min(b = 27.20, 2h = 18.18 * 2 = 36.35\text{m})$ $e = 27.20\text{m}$

Elevation for $e > d$

Figure 5.1: Wind direction for elevation

After inserting the values of, $e/5=5.44$ and $d-e/5=18.6$, $h=18.18\text{m}$

The respective area of zones are calculated

Table 5.1: The respective area of zones

Zones	A	B	C	D
Area (m ²)	98.9	339.24	494.5	494.5

It is very helpful to note that all areas are greater than 10m²

Table 5.2: External wind pressure coefficients on walls

Zone	A	B	C	D	E
h/d	$C_{pe,10}$ $C_{pe,1}$				
5	-2.6	-1.9	-0.5	1.8	-0.7
1	-2.6	-1.9	-0.5	1.8	0.5
≤ 0.25	-2.6	-1.9	-0.5	1.7	-0.3

This structure has h/d ratio =0.75, the external wind pressure coefficients could be determined by interpolating among the values on the above table. According to new code part 1-4 prEN1991, 1-4 2004 Section 7.2.1 recommends the following formula to determine the external pressure coefficient.

$$C_{pe} = C_{pe,1} - (C_{pe,10} - C_{pe,1}) \log A, \text{ where } A \text{ is area in } m^2$$

$$w_e = q_p(z_e) * C_{pe} \text{ and } q_p(z_e) = 484 \text{ N/m}^2.$$

Table 5.3: External wind pressure on walls

Zone	A	B	D
C _{pe,10}	-1.2	-0.8	0.77
C _{pe,1}	-1.4	-0.8	0.77
C _{pe}	-1	-1.4	0.77
We(N/m ²)	-484	-677.6	372.68

5.1.4 Wind force

ES EN 2004:2015 part 1-4 prEN1991 1-4 2004 section 5.3 determines the wind force as;

$$F_{w,e} = w_e * A_{ref}$$

Table 5.4: wind force

Floor	We (kN/m ²)	h(m)	b(m)	Force (KN)
Service				
4th	0.37268	3.06	27.20	31.09
3rd	0.37268	3.06	27.20	31.09
2nd	0.37268	3.06	27.20	31.09
1st	0.37268	3.06	27.20	31.09
Ground	0.37268	3.06	27.20	31.09

5.1.5 Internal wind pressure determination

The internal wind pressure is computed in a similar fashion as the external wind pressure is computed.

ES EN 2004:2015 part 1-4 section 5.2, the internal wind pressure is computed as;

$$W_i = q_p(z_i) * C_{pi} \quad q_p(z_i) = 484 \text{ N/m}^2 \dots \text{already computed}$$

For closed buildings with internal partitions and buildings, the extreme values of internal wind pressure coefficients are 0.2 and -0.3.

Table 5.5: internal pressure on walls

Zone	C_{pi}	$w_i(N/m^2)$
A	-0.3	-145.2
B	-0.3	-145.2
D	-0.2	96.8

5.1.6 Net wind force determination

Net force = external force - internal force

External force

Maximum (+ve) = 31.09KN

Minimum (-ve) = -56.40 KN

Internal force

Maximum (+ve) = 0.0968KN

Minimum (-ve) = -0.145 KN

Net pressure (+ve) = 42.82KN

Net pressure (-ve) = -48.29 KN

5.2 Earth quake analysis and design

5.2.1 Description of the building

The investigated building is a residential reinforced concrete structure. The building is to be constructed in Addis Ababa, which is categorized under zone 3, and building has 4 stories above ground level (level 0). The total height of the building above the ground is 18.18m. The height of the first story (between levels 0 and 1) amounts to 3.06 m. and the heights of other stories are equal to 3.06 m. The dimensions of floors above level 0 are 27.2mx24.2m. The structural system consists of walls and frames. The slab is 0.17 m thick Concrete C25/30 is used.

The corresponding modulus of elasticity amounts to $E_{cm} = 31\text{GPa}$ (EN1992/Table 3.1). Steel S 400 Class B is used. The structure was designed for ductility class low (DCL)

5.2.2 Earthquake Loading

Only horizontal earthquake loads have been accounted for in the analysis since there aren't large-unsupported lengths (example slab with length up to 8m) and hence is not vertical earth quake actions are not governing due to the-stabilizing effects of both permanent and transient gravitational load.

5.2.2.1 Structural regularity

Regularity of the structure (in elevation and in plan) influences the required structural model (planar or spatial), the required method of analysis and the value of the behavior factor q (ES EN 2004:2015-1/4.2.3.1). As shown in this section, the test structure can be categorized as being regular in elevation and in plan.

5.2.2.2 Regularity check in plan

In general, the regularity in plan can be checked when the structural model is defined. The criteria for regularity in plan are described in ES EN 2004:2015-1 (4.2.3.2)

- The slenderness of the test building is smaller than 4.0.

$$\text{i.e Slenderness } (\lambda = L_{max}/L_{min}) = 27.1 \text{ m} / 24 \text{ m} = 1.125 < 4 \text{ OK!}$$

Since assumed frame system lateral stiffness and mass distribution are approximately symmetrical

- Plan configuration is compact since set-back does not affect in-plan stiffness of the floor

5.2.2.3 Regularity check in elevation

Most lateral load resisting systems runs from foundation to top of building and those with set-back are top of relevant zone of the building.

- No abrupt change in both lateral stiffness and mass of floor
- Set-back criteria is satisfied

$$\frac{(L - L_2)}{L} = \frac{(27.1 - 24)}{27.1} = 0.115 < 0.3$$

Limitation: - Even though design ground acceleration (a_g) for Addis Ababa(0.1g) is greater than 0.08g, criteria of DCM or DCH is satisfied, and scope limitation exists on design of such ductility classes , thus, the structure was designed for ductility class for DCL .

ES EN 2004:2015 part-1 is applied for the design and construction of building in seismic region. Lateral force method of analysis is used on the rectangular and vertically straight due to the following reasons:

- Height of building including foundation depth ($h=20.18\text{m}$) less than 200m
- Fundamental period of vibration (T_1): $0.714\text{s} < 2\text{s}$

i.e. regular building

5.2.3 Procedure for lateral force method

Generally, if 'lateral force' method is used, the calculation steps are:

- **Step-1:** Calculation of the seismic mass ($G + \psi E_i Q$) of the structure
- **Step-2:** Evaluation of the period of the structure
- **Step-3:** Evaluations of the resultant base shear F_b and distribution of F_b into lateral forces
- **Step-4:** static analysis under seismic loading ($G + \psi E_i Q$)
- **Step-5:** stability check, considering P- Δ effects (parameter θ) in the seismic loading situation (in which the gravity loading is $G + \psi_2 Q$)

5.2.4 Earthquake Loading

Only horizontal earthquake loads have been accounted for in the analysis since there aren't large-unsupported lengths (example slab with length up to 8m) and hence is not vertical earthquake actions are not governing due to the-stabilizing effects of both permanent and transient gravitational load.

5.2.5 Horizontal seismic action

Seismic action is represented by the elastic response spectrum, and if deep geology is not accounted use of two types of spectra: Type 1 and Type 2.

Type 1 spectrum is used, if the earthquakes that contribute most to the seismic hazard defined for the site for the purpose of probabilistic hazard assessment have a surface-wave magnitude, M_s , greater than 5.5 Reading scale.

Type-2 spectrum is adopted, if the earthquakes that contribute most to the seismic hazard defined for the site for the purpose of probabilistic hazard assessment have a surface-wave magnitude, M_s , not greater than 5.5

Thus, for this case seismic action is represented by the elastic response spectrum, Type - 2($M_s < 5.5$, ES EN 2004:2015-1/3.2.2.2 (2) P) for soil C (ES EN 2004:2015-1/Table 3.1) is used because seismic hazard of probabilistic hazard assessment of Addis Ababa is less than 5.5.

The building is classified as importance class II (ES EN 2004:2015-1/Table 4.3) and the corresponding importance factor amounts to $\gamma I = 1.0$ (ES EN 2004:2015-1/4.2.5 (5) P). Therefore the peak ground acceleration is equal to the reference peak ground acceleration a_g to 0.1g.

5.2.6 Horizontal seismic action

Seismic action is represented by the elastic response spectrum, and If deep geology is not accounted use of two types of spectra: Type 1 and Type 2.

Type 2 spectrum is adopted: If the earthquakes that contribute most to the seismic hazard defined for the site for the purpose of probabilistic hazard assessment have a surface-wave magnitude, M_s , not greater than 5.5

Type 1 spectrum is adopted: If the earthquakes that contribute most to the seismic hazard defined for the site for the purpose of probabilistic hazard assessment have a surface-wave magnitude, M_s , greater than 5.5 Reading scale.

Thus, seismic action is represented by the elastic response spectrum, Type -2($M_s < 5.5$, ES EN 2004:2015-1/3.2.2.2 (2) P) for soil C (ES EN 2004:2015-1/Table 3.1) is used because seismic hazard of probabilistic hazard assessment of Addis Ababa is less than 5.5..

The building is classified as importance class II (ES EN 2004:2015-1/Table 4.3) and the corresponding importance factor amounts to $\gamma I = 1.0$ (ES EN 2004:2015-1/4.2.5 (5) P). Therefore the peak ground acceleration is equal to the reference peak ground acceleration a_g to 0.1g. Using the equation in ES EN 2004:2015-1/3.2.2.2 and the design ground acceleration on the assumed type C ground is $a_g = \gamma I \times a_{gR} = 1.0 \times 0.1g = 0.1g$.

For the design of the building, the design response spectrum is used (i.e. elastic response spectrum reduced by the behavior factor *determination* of the behavior factor *q*, which depends on the type of the structural system, regularity in elevation and plan, and ductility class, thus DCL assumed.

$$q = q_0 k_w \geq 1.50$$

ES EN 2004:2015-8.art/ 5.2.2.2/

Therefore, behavior factor ($q = 1.5$) because ductility class are DCL

5.2.6.1 Evaluation of seismic design shear using the ‘lateral forces ’method

Fundamental period of vibration T_1 :

For the determination of the important property of the structure’s period of vibration, the dynamic analysis result is the most accurate of all. Because, it takes into account mass at every-point in the structure, and most importantly reduced stiffness of the structural members to account for concrete cracking.

For the building with height up to 40m the value of T_1 may be approximated from the following formula: H height of the building= 20.18m and $C_t = 0.075$ for reinforced concrete moment resisting frames and eccentrically braced steel frames

$$T_1 = C_t \cdot H^{3/4}$$

ES EN 2004:2015-part-1-section 4.3.3.2.2

$$T_1 = C_t H^{3/4} = 0.075(20.18)^{3/4} = 0.712s$$

5.2.6.2 Design Spectrum: $S_d(T_1)$

For Lateral force method of analysis, the horizontal components of the seismic action

Design spectrum, $S_d(T)$ normalized by the acceleration of gravity g is defined by the following expression. The values of the periods (T_B , T_C , T_D) and of the soil factor (S), which describe the shape of the elastic response spectrum Amount to: $T_B = 0.1s$, $T_C = 0.25s$, $T_D = 1.2s$ and $S = 1.2$ (EN 1998-1/Table 3.3).

According to ES EN 2004:20 15-1:2003 3.2.2.5 Design spectrum for elastic analysis

$$TC \leq T \leq TD : Sd(T) = \text{Max} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (ag * S * 2.5 * TC / (q * T)) \\ \beta * ag \end{array} \right\} = 0.689s$$

5.2.7 Vertical actions

The investigated building, which is a residential building – category A according to ES EN 2004:2015 Table 6.1, the variable-live load in terms of uniformly distributed load equals to 2KN/m² (ES EN 2004:2015/Table 6.2). The variable-live loads are, in a seismic design situation, reduced with a factor of $\Psi_{2i} = 0.3$ (ES EN 2004:2015/Table A.1.1) whereas, the masses from the variable-live load are reduced using the factor

$$\Psi E_i = \varphi \cdot \Psi_{2i}$$

Factor Ψ_{2i} equals to 0.3 in the case of residential building (ES EN 2004:2015 Table A.1.1). Factor φ is equal to 1.0 for the roof story and 0.5 for other stories (EBCS -EN 1998; 2014 section 4.2.4). Thus variable-live load for floor: $(0.3 \times 5 \times 0.2) = 0.3 \text{ kN/m}$ and
For stair : $(0.3 \times 0.5 \times 3) = 0.45 \text{ kN/m}$

5.2.8 Determination of earth quake force

The seismic base shear force F_b , for each horizontal direction in which the building is analyzed, shall be determined using the following expression:

$$F_b = Sd(T_1) * m * \lambda \quad \text{ES EN 2004:2015-part-1-section 4.3.3.2.2}$$

Where

- $Sd(T_1)$ is the ordinate of the design spectrum at period T
- T_1 is the fundamental period of vibration of the building for lateral motion in the direction considered
- λ is the correction factor, the value of which is equal to: $\lambda = 0.85$ if $T_1 < 2 TC$ and the building has more than two stories, or $\lambda = 1,0$ otherwise. For this case $\lambda = 0.85$ and

5.2.8.1 Evaluation of the seismic mass

The unit used for mass is 'kg' and mass is the total mass of the building, above the foundation or above the top of a rigid-basement. Total mass above the top of the ground floor is equal to 3238.62kg.

5.2.8.2 Estimation of seismic design shear

F_b is the total design seismic shear applied to the building in either the x or y direction this accounted to consider translation effect

$$F_b = S_d(T_1) * m * \lambda = 0.689 * 3238.635 * 0.85 = 1897 \text{KN}$$

Distribution of the horizontal seismic force

When the fundamental mode shape is approximated by horizontal displacements increasing linearly along the height, the horizontal forces F_i should be taken as being given by:

$$F_i = F_b * h_i * m_i / \sum(h_j * m_j)$$

$$F_b = S_d(T_1) * m * \lambda = 0.689 * 3238.635 * 0.85 = 1897 \text{KN}$$

Table 5.6 Base shear distribution over the height of the structure

Floor	height(m)	Mass(Kg)	$m_i * h_i$	Torsional effect $m_i * h_i / \sum(h_j * m_j)$	$F_i = F_b * h_i * m_i / \sum(h_j * m_j)$	V(KN)
Roof	2.88	235	677	0.0686	130	130
4 th	3.06	647	1981	0.2007	381	511
3 rd	3.06	647	1981	0.2007	381	891
2 nd	3.06	647	1981	0.2007	381	1272
1 st	3.06	647	1981	0.2007	381	1652
Ground	3.06	415	1269	0.1286	244	1896
Sum		3239	9869	1	1897	

5.3 Geometric imperfections

Unfavorable effects of possible deviations in the geometry of the structure and the position of loads shall be taken into account in the analysis of members and structures. Imperfections shall be taken into account in ultimate limit states in persistent and accidental design situations.

Imperfections need not be considered for serviceability limit states. The following provisions apply for members with axial compression and structures with vertical load, mainly in buildings. Numerical values are related to normal execution deviations

Imperfections may be represented by an inclination, θ_i , given by

$$\theta_i = \theta_0 \cdot \alpha_h \cdot \alpha_m \quad , \text{ where}$$

θ_0 basic value

α_h reduction factor for height $\alpha_h = 2 / l ; 2 / 3 \leq \alpha_h \leq 1$

α_m reduction factor for number of member $\alpha_m = 0.5 \sqrt{(1 + 1 / m)}$

l length or height [m]

m number of vertical members contributing to the total effect

Note: The value of θ_0 recommended value is $1/200$

Figure 5.2: Effects of geometric imperfections

For structures, the effect of the inclination θ_i may be represented by transverse forces, to be included in the analysis together with other actions.

- Effect on floor diaphragm,

$$H_i = \theta_i (N_b + N_a) / 2$$

- Effect on roof diaphragm,

$$H_i = \theta_i \cdot N_a$$

Where, N_a and N_b are vertical forces contributing to H

NB: Imperfection load act at center of rigidity and obtained only from load of serviceability Limit state (SLS) building.

Table 5.7: calculation of longitudinal forces (imperfection load)

story	Story axial force(P)	ΔP	Theta(θ_i)	N_a (KN)	N_b (KN)	H_i (KN)
Roof	3013.3	3013.325	0.005	3013.325	3013	23.0666225
4th	11614.8	8601.503	0.005	3013.325	8602	50.037068
3rd	20208.9	11607.43	0.005	8601.503	11607	50.5223325
2nd	28838.0	17230.61	0.005	11607.43	17231	50.0951075
1st	37507.3	20276.65	0.005	17230.61	20277	50.76816625
Ground	40442.7	20166.03	0.005	20276.65	20166	101.1067053

5.4 Modeling and stability analysis

5.4.1 Analysis inputs and cases

Modeling: For the analysis of the structure and determination of design action effects, the structure has been modeled with the finite element software ETABS version 2015. Method of Analysis: Response Spectrum Analysis.

Stiffness of Structural Members for Assessing structure's stability and safety:

- **Vertical Members:** In accordance to the code requirements the stiffness of the vertical structural members, columns, are reduced because cracks are expected. For ULS, significant cracks are expected and hence should be accounted for.

Therefore, the analysis has been carried out considering cracked elements with the elastic flexural and shears stiffness properties taken to be equal to 50% of the corresponding stiffness of the un-cracked elements.

- **Beams:** the analysis has been carried out considering cracked elements with the elastic flexural and shears stiffness properties taken to be equal to 50% of the corresponding stiffness of the un-cracked elements.

Modeling assumptions

In modeling, it is tried to represent a building property, loading, distribution of stiffness and mass. Thereby, the structure at hand is modeled to represent the actual building to be constructed to the possible extent.

The architectural design has been properly followed, code recommended loadings have been set and combinations of loading to represent extreme events have been made to represent different ULS scenarios. The structural system at hand consists of number of vertical and lateral load resisting elements connected by horizontal diaphragms.

Floor diaphragms are considered to be rigid after evaluating the deformation of flexible diaphragms with the rigid one since the horizontal displacement nowhere exceeded those resulting from the rigid diaphragm assumption by more than 10% of the corresponding absolute displacement in the seismic design situation.

Table 5.8: comparison between modeling with and with out diaphragms

story	Maximum displacement without diaphragm(mm)	Maximum displacement with diaphragm	Displacement difference in (%)
Story-1	14.56	17	10.1432
Story-2	14.195	16	11.115
Story-3	12.34	15.5	20.268
Story-4	13	15.67	17.19
Story-5	14.89	21	29.281
Story-6	13.4	19	29.242

The major considerations in the 3D ETABS FEM are:

- Vertical and lateral bracing elements are modeled to be fixed at the base level.
- The stiffness of the load bearing elements is evaluated by taking into account the effect of cracking. The elastic flexural and shear stiffness properties are taken to be equal to 50% for columns and 50% for beams of the corresponding stiffness of the un-cracked element as recommended by the Euro Code.
- Column and Beam are modeled as line elements

5.4.1.1 Analysis and load combinations

The followings Load combinations are used.

- Gravitational Load Combinations: 5
- Seismic Load with imperfection load Combinations: 64
- Envelopes: 1

Seismic load combinations: In order to account for uncertainties in the location of masses and in the spatial variation of seismic motion, the calculated center of mass at each floor i shall be considered as being displaced from its nominal location in each direction by an additional eccentricity:

$$e_{ai} = \pm 0.05xL_i$$

Table 5.8: Eccentricities of center of masses of each story

Story	Lx (m)	Ly (m)	ex (m)	ey (m)
Roof	27.1	24.1	± 1.35	± 1.9225
G+4	27.1	24.1	± 1.35	± 1.9225
G+3	27.1	24.1	± 1.35	± 1.9225
G+2	27.1	24.1	± 1.35	± 1.9225
G+1	27.1	24.1	± 1.35	± 1.9225
G+0	27.1	24.1	± 1.35	± 1.9225

Thus, the above table result with four points around the center of mass resulting with 64 different seismic load combinations added with the gravitational load components to account torsional effect.

Table 5.9: Load combinations

Load combination -Id	Load combination Description	Remark
Comb-1	Gk+Qk	Serviceability Limit State(SLS)
Comb-2	1.35Gk+1.5Gk+IMX	Ultimate Limit State(ULS)
Comb-3	1.35Gk+1.5Gk-IMX	Ultimate Limit State(ULS)
Comb-4	1.35Gk+1.5Gk+IMY	Ultimate Limit State(ULS)
Comb-5	1.35Gk+1.5Gk+IMY	Ultimate Limit State(ULS)
Comb-6	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1+0.3EQ,Y1+IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-7	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1+0.3EQ,Y1-IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-8	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1-0.3EQ,Y1+IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-9	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1-0.3EQ,Y1-IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-10	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1+0.3EQ,Y2+IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-11	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1+0.3EQ,Y2-IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-12	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1-0.3EQ,Y2+IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-13	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1-0.3EQ,Y2-IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-14	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2+0.3EQ,Y1+IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-15	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2+0.3EQ,Y1-IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-16	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2-0.3EQ,Y1+IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-17	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2-0.3EQ,Y1-IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-18	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2+0.3EQ,Y2+IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-19	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2+0.3EQ,Y2-IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-20	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2-0.3EQ,Y2+IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-21	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2-0.3EQ,Y2-IMX	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-22	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1+0.3EQ,Y1+IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-23	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1+0.3EQ,Y1-IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-24	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1-0.3EQ,Y1+IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-25	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1-0.3EQ,Y1-IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-26	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1+0.3EQ,Y2+IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-27	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1+0.3EQ,Y2-IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-28	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1-0.3EQ,Y2+IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-29	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X1-0.3EQ,Y2-IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-30	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2+0.3EQ,Y1+IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-31	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2+0.3EQ,Y1-IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-32	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2-0.3EQ,Y1+IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-33	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2-0.3EQ,Y1-IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-34	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2+0.3EQ,Y2+IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-35	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2+0.3EQ,Y2-IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-36	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2-0.3EQ,Y2+IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
Comb-37	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,X2-0.3EQ,Y2-IMY	Seismic combination in X-direction
comb-7-1	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,Y1+0.3EQ,X1+IMX	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-8-1	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,Y1+0.3EQ,X1-IMX	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-9-1	Gk+0.3Qk+EQ,Y1-0.3EQ,X1+IMX	Seismic combination in Y-direction

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

comb-10-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1-0.3EQ, X_1-IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-11-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1+0.3EQ, X_2+IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-12-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1+0.3EQ, X_2-IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-13-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1-0.3EQ, X_2+IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-14-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1-0.3EQ, X_2-IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-15-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2+0.3EQ, X_1+IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-16-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2+0.3EQ, X_1-IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-17-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2-0.3EQ, X_1+IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-18-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2-0.3EQ, X_1-IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-19-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2+0.3EQ, X_2+IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-20-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2+0.3EQ, X_2-IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-21-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2-0.3EQ, X_2+IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-22-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2-0.3EQ, X_2-IMX$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-23-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1+0.3EQ, X_1+IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-24-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1+0.3EQ, X_1-IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-25-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1-0.3EQ, X_1+IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-26-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1-0.3EQ, X_1-IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-27-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1+0.3EQ, X_2+IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-28-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1+0.3EQ, X_2-IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-29-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1-0.3EQ, X_2+IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-30-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_1-0.3EQ, X_2-IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-31-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2+0.3EQ, X_1+IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-32-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2+0.3EQ, X_1-IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-33-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2-0.3EQ, X_1+IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-34-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2-0.3EQ, X_1-IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-35-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2+0.3EQ, X_2+IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-36-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2+0.3EQ, X_2-IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-37-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2-0.3EQ, X_2+IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction
comb-38-1	$G_k+0.3Q_k+EQ, Y_2-0.3EQ, X_2-IMY$	Seismic combination in Y-direction

Figure 5.3: Structural model of the building on ETABS -2015

5.5 Structural system

Structure Classification: According to *ES EN 2004:2015-2003 5.1.2* Terms and definitions; the classification of the structure system as frame, wall, dual or any other is entertained by the distribution of axial forces and base shear between the frame and wall.

As can be easily concluded from the layout of the structural system, all of the gravitational loads are resisted by the column in seismic or any other condition. Therefore, the structure is classified as Frame System.

5.5.1 Centre of mass (CM) and Centre of rigidity (CR)

This property is very important to determine the lateral and rotational stability of the structure. Buildings with close CM and CR are not subjected to high torsional (rotational) action effects and hence can perform much better in seismic condition.

5.5.1.1 Center of mass calculation

The following tables give the mass of each element (column, beam, slab, partition walls, Roof and stair).

Table 5.10: Dimensions used in the building

structure type	Depth(mm)	width(mm)
Beam	450	300
Column	600	600
Slab	170	-
cantilever	220	-
stair case slab	200	-
main hall	-	200
partition wall	--	100

Generally, procedure made for calculation of center mass are as follows

- **Step-1:** Calculation of weight of building element
- **Step-2:** Calculation of centroid for each building element from known reference (Xi, Yi)
- **Step-3:** Determination of center of mass using the following formula

$$X = \frac{\sum W_i * X_i}{\sum W_i} \quad \text{and} \quad Y = \frac{\sum W_i * Y_i}{\sum W_i}$$

They also give the x and y coordinates of each element along with their. In order to not be large we only write here summary.

Roof summary

Table 5.11: Roof center of mass

Structure type	WEIGHT	Xi	Yi	W*Xi	W*Yi
Column	233	13.3	8.9	3086	2050
top tied beam	975	6.98	9.25	13616	9278
Roof load	528	13.9	10.6	7366	5402
Slab	741	14.2	22.3	10448	16388
Shear wall	107	13.76	20.23	1437	2152
summation	2351			32867	33220
		Centroid	X =13.38	y=14.13	

Table 5.12: First floor center of mass

	TOTAL WEIGHT	WEIGHT	W*Xi	W*Yi
	Column	526.32	7053.7896	4870.296
	Floor beam	1252.935	17506.935	11931.33038
	Shear wall	212.364	2873.2788	4303.62684
	Floor Slab	2925.766	38845.71422	27062.86434
	Stair-Case	135.534	1795.38072	3050.853876
	Partition	1419.814	18823.49306	10266.17225
	Σ	6472.733	86898.5914	61485.14367
centroid	X	13.42533		
	Y	9.4991		

Ground floor summary

Table 5.13: Ground floor center of mass

	TOTAL WEIGHT	WEIGHT	W*Xi	W*Yi
	Column	232.56	3112.571	2049.588
	grade beam	1096	15075	10257
	Shear wall	107	1437	2152
	Ground Slab	1866	24513.96	16868
	Stair-Case	135.534	1795.381	3050.853876
	Partition	709.906995	9411.747	5133.086123
	Σ	4147.000995	55345.66	39510.528
centroid	X	13.34594802		
	Y	9.527494217		

Table 5.14: Centre of Mass and Centre of Stiffness of the structure

Story	Weight	XCM	YCM	XCR	YCR
Story6	2351	13.38	14.13	13.7494	13.2879
Story5	6472.733	13.42533	9.4991	13.5957	13.3886
Story4	6472.733	13.42533	9.4991	13.5443	13.405
Story3	6472.733	13.42533	9.4991	13.5366	13.4181
Story2	6472.733	13.42533	9.4991	13.5323	13.4254
Story1	4147.000995	13.34594802	9.527	13.5275	13.4246

5.6 Lateral stability of the structure in ultimate limit state

5.6.1 Inter-story Drift Sensitivity Coefficient

This index gives the lateral stability of the structure. According to the ES EN 2004:2015: 2003, 4.4.2.2 Resistance condition if the index is less than 0.1 the structure is rigid enough to neglect second order effects. If it is between 0.1 and 0.2, second order effects may be approximated θ) and if it lies between 0.2 and 0.3 more accurate second order analysis is required. Structures with an index value of greater than 0.3 are classified as unstable.

Thus, Second order effects (P- Δ -effects) need not to be considered when the following condition is fulfilled in all story as per ES EN 2004:2015: 2003Section 4.4.2.2.

$$\theta(x) = \frac{P_{tot} * dr(x)}{V_{tot,(y)} * h} * q < 0.1 \quad \text{and} \quad \theta(y) = \frac{P_{tot} * dr(y)}{V_{tot,(y)} * h} * q < 0.1$$

$dr(x)$	inter story drift sensitivity coefficient in x direction
$dr(y)$	inter story drift sensitivity coefficient in y-direction
P_{tot}	total gravity load at and above the story considered
$V_{tot}(x)$	total seismic story shear in x direction
$V_{tot}(y)$	total seismic story shear in y direction
h	inter-story height
q	ductility class constant

Table 5.15: Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination

Story	load combination	Drift,y	Drift,x	q	p(KN)	Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ,y	θ,x
Story6	Comb7	0	2.74E-04	1.5	4187.188	145.067			0.044127
Story6	Comb8	0.000095	2.05E-04	1.5	4187.188	114.933			0.033014
Story6	Comb9	0.000095	2.72E-04	1.5	4187.188	145.067			0.043804
Story6	Comb10	0.000125	2.39E-04	1.5	4187.188	130.000			0.027764
Story6	Comb11	0	2.74E-04	1.5	5375.902	-145.067			0.056654
Story6	Comb12	0	2.07E-04	1.5	4187.188	114.933			0.033336
Story6	Comb13	0	2.07E-04	1.5	4187.188	-114.933			0.033336
Story6	Comb14	0	2.74E-04	1.5	4187.188	145.067			0.044127
Story6	Comb15	0.000095	2.72E-04	1.5	4187.188	-145.067			0.043804
Story6	Comb16	0	2.07E-04	1.5	4187.188	-114.933			0.033336
Story6	Comb17	0	2.74E-04	1.5	4187.188	-145.067			0.044127
Story6	Comb18	0	2.07E-04	1.5	4187.188	-114.933			0.033336
Story6	Comb19	0.000095	2.05E-04	1.5	4187.188	-114.933			0.033014
Story6	Comb20	0.000095	2.72E-04	1.5	4187.188	-145.067			0.043804
Story6	Comb21	0	2.74E-04	1.5	4187.188	-145.067			0.044127
Story6	Comb22	0	2.07E-04	1.5	4187.188	-114.933			0.033336
Story6	Comb23	0.000095	2.72E-04	1.5	4187.188	-145.067			0.043804
Story6	Comb24	0.000095	2.05E-04	1.5	4187.188	-114.933			0.033014
Story6	Comb25	0.000166	1.28E-04	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.014869	
Story6	Comb26	0.000164	6.10E-05	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.016008	
Story6	Comb27	0.000164	1.17E-04	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.013592	
Story6	Comb28	0.000164	1.17E-04	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.013592	
Story6	Comb29	0.000165	5.20E-05	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.013646	
Story6	Comb30	0.000166	1.28E-04	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.014869	

Story6	Comb31	0.000165	5.20E-05	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.013646	
Story6	Comb32	0.000164	6.10E-05	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.016008	
Story6	Comb33	0.000164	1.17E-04	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.013592	
Story6	Comb34	0.000166	1.28E-04	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.014869	
Story6	Comb35	0.000166	0.000128	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.014869	
Story6	Comb36	0.000164	0.000117	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.013592	
Story6	Comb37	0.000165	0.000052	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.013646	
Story6	Comb38	0.000166	0.000128	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.014869	
Story6	Comb39	0.000164	0.000061	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.016008	
Story6	Comb40	0.000164	0.000117	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.013592	
Story6	Comb41	0.000165	0.000052	1.5	4187.188		-130.000	0.013646	
Story6	Comb7-1	0	0.000274	1.5	4187.188	-145.067			0.044127
Story6	Comb8-1	0.000125	0.000239	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.027764
Story6	Comb9-1	0.000065	0.000239	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.06272
Story6	Comb10-1	0.000125	2.39E-04	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.027764
Story6	Comb11-1	0.000059	2.40E-04	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.02788
Story6	Comb12-1	0	2.40E-04	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.062983
Story6	Comb13-1	0	2.40E-04	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.062983
Story6	Comb14-1	0.000059	2.40E-04	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.02788
Story6	Comb15-1	0.000065	2.39E-04	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.06272
Story6	Comb16-1	0	2.40E-04	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.062983
Story6	Comb17-1	0.000059	2.40E-04	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.02788
Story6	Comb18-1	0	2.40E-04	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.062983
Story6	Comb19-1	0.000125	0.000239	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.027764
Story6	Comb20-1	0.000065	0.000239	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.06272
Story6	Comb21-1	0.000059	0.00024	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.02788
Story6	Comb22-1	0	0.00024	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.062983

Story6	Comb23-1	0.000065	0.000239	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.06272
Story6	Comb24-1	0.000125	0.000239	1.5	4187.188	-130.000			0.027764
Story6	Comb25-1	0.000195	9.70E-05	1.5	4187.188		-145.067	0.015621	
Story6	Comb26-1	0.000135	9.30E-05	1.5	4187.188		-114.933	0.014977	
Story6	Comb27-1	0.000135	8.30E-05	1.5	4187.188		-114.933	0.013367	
Story6	Comb28-1	0.000135	8.30E-05	1.5	4187.188		-114.933	0.013367	
Story6	Comb29-1	0.000194	8.60E-05	1.5	4187.188		-145.067	0.01385	
Story6	Comb30-1	0.000195	9.70E-05	1.5	4187.188		-145.067	0.015621	
Story6	Comb31-1	0.000194	8.60E-05	1.5	4187.188		-145.067	0.01385	
Story6	Comb32-1	0.000135	9.30E-05	1.5	4187.188		-114.933	0.014977	
Story6	Comb33-1	0.000135	8.30E-05	1.5	4187.188		-114.933	0.013367	
Story6	Comb34-1	0.000195	0.000097	1.5	4187.188		-145.067	0.015621	
Story6	Comb35-1	0.000195	0.000097	1.5	4187.188		-145.067	0.015621	
Story6	Comb36-1	0.000135	0.000083	1.5	4187.188		-114.933	0.013367	
Story6	Comb37-1	0.000194	0.000086	1.5	4187.188		-145.067	0.01385	
Story6	Comb38-1	0.000195	0.000097	1.5	4187.188		-145.067	0.015621	
Story6	Comb39-1	0.000135	0.000093	1.5	4187.188		-114.933	0.014977	
Story6	Comb40-1	0.000135	0.000083	1.5	4187.188		-114.933	0.013367	
Story6	Envelope-ALL Max	0.000195	0.000274	1.5	5375.902		54.067	0.040866	
Story6	Envelope-ALL Min	0.000125	0.000117	1.5	4187.188	-145.067	-145.067	0.005066	
Story6							max	0.04086	0.062983

As shown in the above table, the maximum value is 0.04867 in the x- axis (X-direction) and is 0.0629 in the y-direction .The structure is quite rigid to neglect the effect of second order effects.

The summary of interstorey drift sensitivity coefficient for remaining stories are summarized in the following table.

Story	θ_y	θ_x	$\theta_{allowable}$	status
Story -5	0.082	0.0789	0.1	OK
Story -4	0.0756	0.0776	0.1	OK
Story -3	0.0716	0.0754	0.1	OK
Story -2	0.0436	0.065	0.1	OK
Story -1	0.026	0.0715	0.1	OK

Thus, the structure is quite rigid to neglect the effect of second order effects.

5.6.2 Damage limitation Requirement

The damage limitation requirement is considered, if under a seismic action having a larger probability of occurrence than the design seismic action corresponding to the no-collapse requirement and the interstorey drifts are limited in accordance with section ES EN 2004:2015-4.4.3.2.

This requirement is equivalent to the SLS requirements which require cracks and deflections of elements to be limited.

Taking the requirement for buildings having non-structural elements of brittle materials attached to the structure which is the most critical;

$$dr * v \leq 0,005 h \quad dr * v \leq 0,005 h \quad \text{Safe}$$

Where, dr is the design inter storey drift as defined in 4.4.2.2(2);

h is the storey height;

v is the reduction factor which takes into account the lower return period of the seismic action associated with the damage limitation requirement which is 0.5 (structure importance class II).

The limited deformation requirement is evaluated as follows. Action associated with the damage limitation requirement

Table 5.16: Checking Damage limitation c

storey	Drift(x) /height	Drift(y) /height	h(mm)	q	v	Drift X,mm	Drift Y,mm	0.005h.mm	status
storey-6	0.000274	0.000195	3060	1.5	0.5	0.62883	0.447525	15.3	OK
storey-5	0.0003484	0.000455	3060	1.5	0.5	0.799578	1.044225	15.3	OK
storey-4	0.000407	0.00031	3060	1.5	0.5	0.934065	0.71145	15.3	OK
storey-3	0.00052	0.00052	3060	1.5	0.5	1.1934	1.1934	15.3	OK
storey-2	0.000533	0.000533	3060	1.5	0.5	1.223235	1.223235	15.3	OK
storey-1	0.000285	0.000285	3060	1.5	0.5	0.654075	0.654075	15.3	OK

Therefore, the damage limitation requirement is fully satisfied.

CHAPTER 6 ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF BEAM

6.1 Introduction

Any structural element is designed for resisting the type of action acting on it. Beams are flexural members which transfer the loads from slab to columns. Since beams are structural member that can be subjected to various actions like axial, bending, shear, and torsion, beams are designed for flexure (moment) and checked against torsion and shear. A beam is a structural element that is capable of withstanding load primarily by resisting Bending. The bending force induced into the material of the beam as a result of loads, own weight, span and external reactions to these loads is called a bending moment.

If axial forces are developed in the beam, then it is no longer a beam but designed as a beam column. Beams are usually horizontal. When beams are curved in elevation, they are known as arch beams. Arch beams are not technically beams because they only carry compression force. Since arch beams do not carry moment, they have no deflection, hence having small depths.

6.1.1 Basic Principles and Assumptions in Flexure Theory of Reinforced Concrete

Although the method used in the analysis of RC beams are different from those used in the design of homogenous beam such as structural steel, the fundamental principles are essentially the same. Accordingly, the basic equations for the flexural design of beams and slabs are derived based on the following basic principles and assumptions at ultimate limit state. Derived equations are then used to develop design tables and Charts for Various grades of concrete and steel.

- Internal stress resultants such as bending moments, shear forces etc. at any section of a member are in equilibrium with the external action effects.
- Plane sections before bending remains plane after bending.
- The strain in the reinforcement is equal to the strain in the concrete at the same level.
- . The tensile strength of concrete is neglected.

- The stresses in concrete and reinforcement can be computed from the strains.
- . The stress -strain relationship of the reinforcement is as shown in the figure below

Figure 6.1: Stress-Strain diagram for reinforcing steel

The maximum compressive strain in the concrete is taken to be

0.0035 in bending

0.002 in axial compression

The maximum tensile strain in the reinforcement is taken to be 0.025

According to ES EN 2004:2015-2004; 2014, Part 1, 1 - there are two Limit State Designs.

They are:

- Serviceability Limit State
- Ultimate Limit State

Serviceability Limit State provides minimum depth that satisfies the deflection and Cracking requirement. While Ultimate Limit State provides the reinforcement requirement for:

- Flexure
- Shear

- Bondage

During flexural design, beams can fail in three different mechanisms. These are:

Tension Failure – is where the steel reinforcement yields first before the concrete

Compression Failure – is where the concrete yields before the steel reinforcement

Balanced Failure – is where both the steel reinforcement and concrete yield at the same time.

Of the three failure mechanisms, tension failure is preferred over the other because it shows warning in the structure by the means of deflection. Tension failure is reached when the steel yields. To guarantee tension failure;

Use a max value of $\rho = 0.75$

$$\delta = 0.44 + 1.25x / d$$

During the design of beam, the use of different parameters yields different values with varying effect. Parameters used that cause major effect in beam design are depth of beam, diameter of reinforcement bar used and steel grade of reinforcement bar. Much emphasis is made on the steel bars because it is the weakest element there. Changes made that yields minor change in the beam design are width of the beam and the concrete grade.

6.2 Load on beam

Loads on beam are resulted from the following condition

- Dead load from the wall (partition wall) directly supported on beam.
- Load transferred from slab
- Self-weight of beam
- Load transfer from stair-case
- Special case for top tied beam (i.e. additional load from slab and tanker)
- The following Assumption are made while load on beam from partition wall o are estimated: namely

NB: For beam that has no partition, it's better to assume HCB wall with a thickness of 15cm to be on the safe side.

NB: glazed partition on beam, it's good to replace by wall partition with thickness of 15cm: Engineering decision.

6.2.1 Dead load from walls directly supported on beam

The following are steps of partition wall load calculation on beam

- Identify axis of beam and naming beam axis in easy way
- Calculate effective area covered by wall partition on y-z face of beam
- Calculate all necessary opening area on wall partition from architectural drawing such as window. door and other opening if exist
- Calculate net effective area by subtracting opening area from effective area from
- Estimate concentrated load (kN) on beam by multiplying net effective area with thickness and unit weight oh HCB Respectively.
- Finally, calculate lined load (kN/m) on beam by dividing concentrated load (kN) to effective length of beam (m).

6.2.1.1 Dead load from the (partition wall) directly supported on beam

Generally

$$wallload(kN / m) = \frac{((effective\ area - opening\ area) * thickness * unit\ weight)}{Effective\ length\ of\ beam}$$

NB: Effective length of beam mean length over which wall load will uniformly have distributed across beam length.

Summary of wall load (KN/m) on beam for second floor will be as follows

Figure 6.2: wall load (kN/m) on beam

6.2.2 Load transferred to beam from slab

Finally loads are transferred to beams as shear. The shear is calculated using ES EN 2004:2015.

6.2.2.1 Case-1 two-way slab

The load transfer coefficients are read from ES EN 2004:2015, Table3-3 Shear force coefficients for uniformly loaded rectangular panels supported on four sides with provision for torsion at corners The design load on a beam determined in the above may be taken as

the maximum shear in the slab at the support which will be distributed on 75% of the span of the beam. Shear load calculation.

This is done by calculation of shear force using co-efficient method.

Support condition - two adjacent edges discontinuous $l_y/l_x=4.5/4=1.125 < 2$

Figure 6.3 : Sample Two way slab

General formula, $V_{sy} = \beta_{vy} * n * Lx$ and $V_{sx} = \beta_{vx} * n * Lx$

Where: $V_{sy, c}$ and $V_{sx, c}$ is shear force for continuous Edge and

$V_{sx, d}$ and $V_{sy, d}$ for shear force for discontinuous Ed

Table: 6.1 Sample shear calculation

Sample shear for dead load	shear force for live load
$V_{sy,c} = \beta_{vy,c} * n * Lx = .445 * 10.04 * 4 = 17.78 \text{KN/m}$	$V_{sy,c} = \beta_{vy,c} * n * Lx = .4 * 3 * 4 = 5.34 \text{KN/m}$
$V_{sx,c} = \beta_{vx,c} * n * Lx = .4 * 10.04 * 4 = 16.064 \text{KN/m}$	$V_{sx,c} = \beta_{vx,c} * n * Lx = .4 * 3 * 4 = 5.34 \text{KN/m}$
$V_{sx,d} = \beta_{sx,d} * n * Lx = .295 * 10.04 * 4 = 11.8 \text{KN/m}$	$V_{sx,d} = \beta_{sx,d} * n * Lx = .295 * 3 * 4 = 3.54 \text{KN/m}$
$V_{sy,d} = \beta_{vy,d} * n * Lx = .26 * 10.04 * 4 = 10.04 \text{KN/m}$	$V_{sy,d} = \beta_{vy,d} * n * Lx = .26 * 3 * 4 = 3.12 \text{KN/m}$

Summary load transferred to beam for incase of two. Slab

6.2.2.2 Case-2:one-way slab

One-way slabs transmit their load in shorter direction. Whereas in longer direction negligible. Take 1m strip in shorter direction

Figure 6.4: one way slab

Sample of shear calculation in shorter direction-panel-7

Panel-7: Sample of shear for dead load =9.9KN/m²

Figure 6.5 : dead loading

Panel-7: Sample of shear for live load=3KN/m²

Figure 6.6 : live loading

Sample of shear for dead load =9.9KN/m²

$$V_s = 9.9 * 1.85 / 2 = 9.16 \text{KN/m}$$

Sample of shear for live load=3KN/m²

$$= 2.75 \text{KN/m}$$

6.2.2.3 Case: 3 cantilever-8

Cantilever transmits their load in shorter direction. Whereas in longer direction negligible take 1m strip in shorter direction

Figure 6.7 : cantilever -8

Cantilever-8: Sample of shear for dead load =11.88KN/m

Cantilever-8: Sample of shear for live load=3.75KN/m

$$V_s = (n \cdot l_x) = 11.88 \cdot 2.25$$

$$= 26.75 \text{ KN/m}$$

$$V_s = (n \cdot l_x) = 3.75 \cdot 2.25$$

$$= 8.34 \text{ KN/m}$$

Summary of un factored live Load (KN/m) transferred from one-way, two-way slab and cantilever to beam will be as summarized as follows.

Figure 6.8: Summary of un factored live Load (KN/m) from slab to beam

Summary of un factored Dead load (KN/m) transferred from one-way, two-way slab and cantilever to beam will be as summarized as follows

Figure 6.9 : Summary of un factored Dead load (KN/m) from slab to beam

6.2.3 Load transfer from stair-case

6.2.3.1 Dead load

Dead Load, Shear, Moment and Reaction result for Section A-A stair on ground floor 3rd floor.

Figure 6.10: Dead loading

Figure 6.11: shear force diagram for dead load

6.2.3.2 Live load

Live Load, Shear, Moment and Reaction result for Section A-A stair on ground floor – 3rd floors.

Figure 6.12: Live loading

Figure 6.13: shear force diagram

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

Analysis result

Figure 6.14: Shear force diagram(SFD)

Figure 6.15: Bending moment diagram (BMD)

6.3 Design of Beam

Beams are primarily designed for flexure. Furthermore, it is essential to check and design the beam sections for torsion and shear. But during the analysis output, the torsion was found to be very small (insignificant), so there was no need to check for torsional effect.

NB: Beam is not subjected to torsion because it is loaded as a line load. Therefore, beams were designed for flexure and shear. The beams designed are found on Second floor. The moments used here are acquired from the slab loads transferred.

MS Excel spreadsheet prepared and hand calculation was used for the design of the beam. Also the beam across the span is checked whether if the beam is T or rectangular since the compression zone is at the top. The support is considered as rectangular due to the compression zone being at the bottom.

6.3.1 Design of RC Section for flexure

Design of Beam

Provided data: Class I work

$$f_{ck} = 30\text{Mpa}, f_{yk} = 400\text{Mpa}, f_{cd} = (0.85 * f_{ck}) / 1.5 = 17\text{Mpa}$$

$$f_{yd} = f_{yk} / 1.15 = 348\text{Mpa}$$

Main rebar diameter =16mm	Stirrup diameter =8mm	Concrete cover=35mm
---------------------------	-----------------------	---------------------

Figure 6.16: Typical crosssection

Beams are designed primarily for flexure. Furthermore it is essential to check and design the beam sections for torsion and shear. But in our analysis output the torsion is very small (insignificant); no need to check for torsion effect.

Figure 6.17: Critical moments at beams

1. Negative moment left for support reinforcement at the top
2. Negative moment right for support reinforcement at the top
3. Positive moment middle (but used for whole). Reinforcement at the bottom.

The general procedure to be adopted is as follows:

- Check that the section complies with the requirements for fire resistance
- Check that cover and concrete quality comply with durability requirements, which has been check on the introduction part of the paper.
- Calculate bending moments and shear forces
- Calculate reinforcement required for bending and shear
- Check span/depth ratio.

The procedure for the design of rectangular beams is as follows:

- **Step -1:** Calculate $\mu_{sd} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{cd} * b d^2}$ where $\mu_{sd,lim}$ is the limiting value of μ_{sd} for the amount of the redistribution carried out.
- **Step -2 :** Obtain lever arm Z from table
- **Step -3:** If $\mu_{sd} < \mu_{sd,lim}$ the area of tension reinforcement A_s is calculated from
$$A_s = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * Z}$$
- **Step -4:** If $M > M_u$ then compression reinforcement is needed.

- **Step -5:** Check minimum reinforcement requirement: $A_{s,min} = \frac{0.26A_c f_{ct} m b d}{f_{yk}}$
- **Step -6:** Check maximum reinforcement requirements: $A_{s,min} = 0.045A_c$ for tension or compression reinforcement outside lap locations
- **Step -7:** Check whether the beam is rectangular or T-beam.

Sample calculation for beam AB along axis axis-6

$$M=54.01\text{kNm}$$

$$\mu_{sd} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{cd} * b d^2} \quad \mu_{sd} = \frac{54.01 * 10^6}{17 * 300 * 397} = 0.067$$

Corresponding to the above value one can read Kx and Kz. So that Kx=0.0937

$$X=Kx*d=0.0937*397=37.19 < 170\text{mm (thickness of the flange)}$$

Therefore the beam is rectangular.

Summary for other beams is shown in the following table

span	Mu	μ	Kx	X	check
B-C on axis-6	54.78	0.068	0.0937	37.19	rectangular
C-D on axis-6	54.85	0.068	0.094	37.31	rectangular
D-E on axis-6	59.21	0.074	0.103	40.89	rectangular
E-F on axis-6	59.21	0.074	0.103	40.89	rectangular
F-G on axis-6	56.46	0.07	0.097	38.54	rectangular

2nd floor beam AB on axis 6

- **Case -1 :**At support B

$$M_{sd}=54.01$$

$$\mu_{sd} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{cd} * b d^2} \quad \mu_{sd} = \frac{54.01 * 10^6}{17 * 300 * 397} = 0.067 \quad \text{Which is less than } \mu_{sd,lim} \text{ so that it's}$$

singly reinforced.

From the table given in the ES EN 2004:2015-1-1:2014 read Kz value

For $\mu_{sd} = 0.067$ the Kz value is obtained by interpolation between the values 0.06 and 0.07. The interpolation gives Kz = 0.963

$$Kz = \frac{Z}{d} \Rightarrow Z = Kz * d = 0.963 * 397 = 382.1$$

$$A_s = \frac{Msd}{f_y d * Z} = \frac{54.01 * 10^6}{348 * 382.1} = 406.17 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$\text{No. Of bar, } n = \frac{A_s}{a_s} = \frac{406.17 \text{ mm}^2}{200 \text{ mm}^2} = 2.03 = 3$$

Checking the minimum reinforcement required using the formula

$$A_{s,\min} = \frac{0.26 A_c f_{ctm} b d}{f_{yk}}$$

$f_{ctm} = 2.6$ for C25/30 General design chart and tables for ES EN 2004:2015-1-1-
table 1-1

$$= \frac{0.26 * 2.6 * 300 * 397}{400} = 201.279 \text{ mm}^2 \quad \text{but not less than the value}$$

$0.0013 b d = 154.83 \text{ mm}^2$ ES EN 2004:2015 1-1-2013 section 9.2.1.1

Therefore, use 3 ϕ 16 bars and A_s provided = 600 mm^2

2nd floor beam on axis 6

- **Case -2** : At span A-B

$M_{sd} = 25.37$

$$\mu_{sd} = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{cd} * b d^2} \quad \mu_{sd} = \frac{25.37 * 10^6}{17 * 300 * 397^2} = 0.031, \text{ which is less than } \mu_{sd,\lim} \text{ so that it's}$$

singly reinforced

From the table given in the ES EN 2004:2015-1-1:2014 read K_z value

$$\mu_{sd} = 0.031$$

For the K_z value is obtained by interpolation between the values 0.03 and 0.04. The interpolation gives $K_z = 0.98$

$$K_z = \frac{Z}{d} \Rightarrow Z = K_z * d = 0.98 * 397 = 389.1$$

$$A_s = \frac{M_{sd}}{f_{yd} * Z} = \frac{25.37 * 10^6}{348 * 389.1} = 187.36 \text{ mm}^2$$

Checking the minimum reinforcement required using the formula; $A_{s,\min} = \frac{0.26 A_c f_{ctm} b d}{f_{yk}}$

$f_{ctm} = 2.6$ for C25/30 General design chart and tables for ES EN 2004:2015-1-1-2014 table 1-1

$$= \frac{0.26 * 2.6 * 300 * 397}{400} = 201.279 \text{ mm}^2$$

but not less than the value $0.0013 b t d = 154.83 \text{ mm}^2$ ES EN 2004:2015 1-1-2013 section 9.2.1.1

Therefore use the minimum reinforcement area

$$\text{No. Of bar, } n = \frac{A_s}{a_s} = \frac{201.279 \text{ mm}^2}{200 \text{ mm}^2} = 1.06 = 2$$

Therefore use 2 ϕ 16 bars A_s provided = 400 mm^2

The following table summarize design for flexure of axis '6' and axis 'c' sample beams.

Table 6.2: summary of design of beams

Span on axis 6	condition	moment	b	d	μ_{sd}	Kz	Z(mm)	As(calculated)	a_s (mm ²)	No of \varnothing 16 mm calculated	No of \varnothing 16 mm provided
AB	support	54.01	300	397	0.06	0.963	382.1	406.17	200	2.03	3
AB	span	25.37	300	397	0.031	0.98	389.1	187.36	200	1.06	2
BC	support	54.78	300	397	0.068	0.963	382.1	409.82	200	2.04	3
BC	span	24.57	300	397	0.03	0.98	389	181.4	200	1.06	2
DE	span	29.21	300	397	0.036	0.979	388.66	215.9	200	1.07	2
DE	support	59.28	300	397	0.073	0.96	381.2	446.14	200	2.23	3
On axis C											
6-5'	span	29.13	300	397	0.036	0.988	392.2	213	200	1.06	2
5-4	span	36.52	300	397	0.045	0.974	386.6	271.35	200	1.35	2

6.3.2 Design for Shear

Generally, shear reinforcement in beams are in the form of vertical stirrups spaced at varying intervals along the axis of the beam which depends on the shear force requirements. The stirrups are usually small diameter bars commonly $\phi 6$ and $\phi 8$ formed to fit around the main longitudinal rebar. On the other hand shear reinforcement may be provided by bending up a part of longitudinal steel where it is no longer needed to resist flexural tension

Stirrups are used in RC beams for the following reasons:

- Part of the shear force is resisted
- Restrict growth of diagonal cracks and reduce their penetration into compression zone by improving aggregate interlock in concrete and dowel action of the main steel
- Tie the longitudinal reinforcement
- Maintain the integrity of the concrete compression zone
- Improve member ductility by restraining the growth of inclined cracks;
- provided warning of impending failure

Case -1: 2nd floor beam on axis 6 at beam DE

$$b = 35 + 10 + 8 = 53, \quad b/D/d = 300/450/397$$

Design value (ES EN 2004:2015- 2 Part 1, 1 Section 6.2)

$$X = c/2 + d = 0.5/2 + 0.397 = 0.647$$

Point at which the value shear becomes zero is

$$V_{0,point} \frac{0.5}{2} + \frac{4.5}{2} = 0.25 + 2.25 = 2.5m$$

a) Computing design shear

To find the design shear (V_{Ed}) using similarity of triangle and find at a point 2.5-x

$$\frac{74.34}{2.5} = \frac{V_{Ed}}{2.5 - x}$$

$$V_{Ed} = 54.2kN$$

b) Computing the shear capacity of the concrete

$$V_{rd,max} = 0.6(1 - \frac{*fck}{250}) = 0.528$$

$$Crd,c = \frac{0.18}{\gamma_c} = \frac{0.18}{1.5} = 0.12$$

$$K = 1 + \sqrt{\frac{200}{d}} = 1 + \sqrt{\frac{200}{397}} = 1.7 \leq 2$$

$$\rho_1 = \frac{Ast(tension)}{bd} = \frac{400}{300 * 397} = 0.003 \leq 0.02$$

$$V_{rd,c} = \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.18(100 * 0.003 * 30)^{1/3} * (\frac{2d}{av}) + 0.15 \delta_{cp} = 34.04kN \\ V_{min,bw.d} = 0.035 * 1.7^{3/2} * 30^{1/2} * 300 * 397 = 51kN \end{array} \right.$$

Therefore, take $V_{RD,c}=51kN$

c) Check for diagonal shear force

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{V_1 * f_{cd} * b * z}{\cot \theta + \tan \theta}$$

Check for $\theta < 21.8^\circ$

$$Z = 0.9d = 0.9 * 397 = 357.3$$

$$V_1 = 0.6 \left(1 - \frac{f_{ck}}{250} \right) = 0.528$$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{0.528 * 17 * 300 * 357}{2.5 + 1 / 2.5} = 331.7 \text{ kN} > V_{ed} \dots \text{ok}$$

Since $V_{rd} < V_{ed} \dots$ stirrup is needed

d) Stirrup computation

$$V_{Rd,s} = \frac{A_{sw}}{s} * z * f_{yd} * \cot \theta, \text{ neglecting } V_{Rd}$$

$$S = \frac{100 * 357.3 * 348 * 2.5}{54 * 10^3} = 310 \text{ mm}$$

$$A_{sw} = 2(\text{number of leg}), \pi r^2 = 100 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$S = \frac{100 * 357.3 * 348 * 2.5}{54 * 10^3} = 310 \text{ mm}$$

Therefore Use $\varnothing 8$ c/c 300mm

CHAPTER 7 DESIGN OF COLUMNS

7.1 Introduction

Columns (sometimes named as compression members) are vertical structural members supporting compressive axial loads, with or without moments. The cross sectional dimensions of a column are generally less than its height. Columns support vertical loads from beams and slabs and transmit them down to foundation. The bending forces acting on it are resulted from the eccentricity or continuity of the structure.

Columns may be classified based on the following criteria;

- a) On the basis of composition; composite columns, in filled columns, etc.
- b) On the basis of geometry; rectangular, square, circular, L- shaped, T-shaped etc.
- c) On the basis of degree of slenderness ; slender ,short
- d) On the basis of loading; axially loaded column, columns under uni-axial bending, and columns under bi axial bending.
- e) On the basis of sensitivity to second order effect due to lateral displacements; sway columns, non-sway columns.
- f) On the basis of the manner by which lateral stability is provided; braced columns, un braced columns.

Frames may be classified as non-sway if its response to in plane horizontal forces is sufficiently stiff for it to be acceptably accurate to neglect any additional internal forces or moments arising from horizontal displacement of its nodes. Any other frame shall be classified as a sway frame and the effects of its nodes shall be taken in to account.

A frame shall be classified as non-sway for a given load case if the critical load case ratio;

$$N_{sd}/N_{cr} \leq 0.1$$

Where, N_{sd} - design value of

N_{cr} - Critical value for failure in sway mode.

7.2 Slenderness

Columns are broadly classified as short and slender columns. Short columns are columns for which the strength of column is governed by the strength of the materials and the geometry of the cross-section. In short columns, second order effects are negligible. In this case it is not necessary to consider slenderness effects and compression members can be designed se don forces determined from first order analysis. When the unsupported length of the column is long, lateral deflection could be so high that the moments shall increase and weaken the column. Such column whose axial load carrying capacity is significantly reduced by moments resulting from lateral deflection of the column is referred to as slender column. When slenderness effects cannot be neglected, the design of compression members, restraining beams and other supporting members shall be based on the factored forces and moments from second order analysis.

$$\lambda = \frac{Le}{i} \quad \text{Where,}$$

Le-effective buckling length

i-radius of gyration of the gross concrete section in the plane of buckling.

$$i = \frac{I}{A}$$

7.2.1 Limits of slenderness

$$\lambda_{lim} = \frac{20ABC}{\sqrt{n}}, \text{ where}$$

$$A = \frac{1}{(1 + 0.2\phi_{eff})} \quad (\text{if } \phi_{eff} \text{ is not known take } A=0.7)$$

$$B = (1 + 2\omega)^{0.5} \quad (\text{if } \omega \text{ is not known } B=1.1)$$

$$C = 1.7 - r_m \quad (\text{if } r_m \text{ is not known take } C=0.7)$$

$$\phi_{eff} \text{ is the effective creep ration} = \phi \left(\frac{(\infty, to) MoEqp}{MoEd} \right)$$

M_{oEqp} is the first order moment due to quasi-permanent load combination (SLS)

M_{odEd} is the first order moment due to design load combination (ULS)

ω is the mechanical reinforcement ratio = $\frac{A_s, f_{yd}}{A_c f_{cd}}$

r_m is the moment ratio = $\frac{M_{01}}{M_{02}}$

Where, M_{01}, M_{02} are the first order end moments, $|M_{02}| > |M_{01}|$

M_{01} and M_{02} are first order moments at ends

7.3 Example on design and analysis of columns

For academic purposes, one column is chosen to be analyzed and designed. The column selected is the central column C10, which is running from story -1 to story-2. The combinations used for analysis and design are the same as those used for stability checking. To meet the requirements of safety and reduce the rigorous calculations arising from the load combinations, it was proposed to use load combinations that will give maximum compressive force (P_{max}), maximum bending moment in the x direction (M_{x-max}), maximum bending moment in the y direction ($M_{y,max}$) and the load combination giving the minimum compressive axial force (P_{min}).

- Available data

Non sway column of 600*600 crosssection

Load combination giving maximum compressive axial force – combo4, with corresponding values of $P_{max}=1579.3\text{KN}$ and end moments $M_{01}=0.0314\text{KN-m}$, $M_{02} = -0.1355\text{KN-m}$ in the x-direction, $M_{01}=-9.0923 \text{ KN-m}$, $M_{02}=15.2406 \text{ KN-m}$ in the y-direction.

Load combination giving maximum bending moment in the x-direction – combo9, with corresponding values of $P=1014.45\text{KN}$ and end moments $M_{01}=32.0729\text{KN-m}$, $M_{02} = -18.8974\text{KN-m}$ in the x-direction, $M_{01}=0 \text{ KN-m}$, $M_{02}=-5.5412 \text{ KN-m}$ in the y-direction.

Load combination giving maximum bending moment in the y –direction-combo5, with corresponding values of $P=1558.59\text{KN}$ and end moments $M_{01}=-0.0668\text{KN-m}$, $M_{02} = 0.1402\text{KN-m}$ in the x-direction, $M_{01}=-20.272\text{KN-m}$, $M_{02}=24.43\text{KN-m}$ in the y-direction.

Load combination giving minimum axial compressive force-combo24-1, with corresponding values of $P=1003.43\text{KN}$ and end moments $M_{01}=-15.7\text{KN-m}$, $M_{02} = 27.6\text{KN-m}$ in the x-direction, $M_{01}=-19.273\text{KN-m}$, $M_{02}=19.411\text{KN-m}$ in the y-direction.

Concrete used is C-25/30 and reinforcement steel grade of S-460

Step -1) Material data

$$f_{cd} = \frac{0.85 * 30}{1.5} = 17 \text{ Mpa}$$

$$f_{yd} = \frac{460}{1.15} = 400 \text{ Mpa}$$

$$E_{cm} = 30 \text{ Gpa}$$

$$\epsilon_s = 2\text{‰}$$

Step -2) check slenderness limit

2.1) in the x-direction

Corresponding to values of load combo 4

$$\lambda_{lim} = \frac{20ABC}{\sqrt{n}}$$

Take $A=1.7$, $B=1.1$ and $C=1.7 - r_m$

$$\text{Where } r_m = \frac{M_{01}}{M_{02}} = 0.0314 / -0.1355 = -0.23173$$

$$C = 1.93174$$

$$n = \frac{N_{ed}}{A_c \cdot f_{cd}} = 1579300 / (600 * 600 * 17 \text{N/mm}^2) = 0.2092$$

$$\lambda_{\text{lim}} = \frac{20ABC}{\sqrt{n}}$$

$$= 65.036 \text{ mm}$$

Effective length

2.2.1) for braced member

$$l_o = 0.5l \sqrt{\left[1 + \frac{K_1}{0.5 + K_1}\right] + \left[1 + \frac{K_2}{0.5 + K_2}\right]}$$

$$K = \frac{\text{Column stiffness}}{\sum \text{Beam stiffness}}$$

$$K_i = \frac{(EI/l)_{\text{column}}}{\sum (2EI/L)_{\text{beam}}}$$

$$I_{\text{column}} = \frac{600 * 600^3}{12} = 2400000 \text{ mm}^4$$

$$I_{\text{beam, top}} = \frac{300 * 450^3}{12} = 506250 \text{ mm}^4$$

$$k_1 = \frac{\frac{2400000 \text{ mm}^4}{3006}}{(2 * 506250 \text{ mm}^4 + 2 * 506250 \text{ mm}^4)} = 1.774229319$$

$$I_{\text{column}} = \frac{600 * 600^3}{12} = 2400000 \text{ mm}^4$$

$$I_{\text{beam, bottom}} = \frac{300 * 450^3}{12} = 2278125000 \text{ mm}^4$$

$$l_o = 0.5 * 3006 \sqrt{\left[1 + \frac{1.774229319}{0.5 + 1.774229319}\right]} + \left[1 + \frac{1.774229319}{0.5 + 1.774229319}\right] = 2675.558389 \text{mm}$$

$$\lambda = \frac{l_o}{i}, \quad i = \sqrt{\frac{I}{A}} = \frac{h}{\sqrt{12}} = 173.2050808$$

$$\lambda = 15.44734356$$

$$\lambda < \lambda_{\text{lim}} \dots \dots \dots \text{short column}$$

2.2) in the y direction

$$\lambda_{\text{lim}} = \frac{20ABC}{\sqrt{n}}$$

Take A=1.7, B=1.1 and C=1.7- r_m

Where $r_m = \frac{M_{01}}{M_{02}} = -9.0923 / 15.2406 = -1.69721$

$$n = \frac{N_{ed}}{A_c f_{cd}}$$

$$= 0.2092342$$

$$\lambda_{\text{lim}} = \frac{20ABC}{\sqrt{n}}$$

$$= 65.036 \text{mm}$$

2.2.2) for braced member

$$l_o = 0.5l \sqrt{\left[1 + \frac{K_1}{0.5 + K_1}\right]} + \left[1 + \frac{K_2}{0.5 + K_2}\right]$$

$$K = \frac{\text{Column stiffness}}{\sum \text{Beam stiffness}}$$

$$K_i = \frac{(EI / l)_{column}}{\sum (2EI / L)_{beam}}$$

$$I_{column} = \frac{600 * 600^3}{12} = 2400000 \text{mm}^4$$

$$I_{beam, top} = \frac{450 * 300^3}{12} = 1012500000 \text{mm}^4$$

$$I_{beam, bottom} = \frac{450 * 300^3}{12} = 1012500000 \text{mm}^4$$

$$K_i = \frac{(EI / l)_{column}}{\sum (2EI / L)_{beam}}$$

$$K_1 = 5333.333333$$

$$K_2 = 12000$$

Effective length $l_0 = 3005.949121$

$$\lambda = \frac{l_0}{i}$$

$$= \frac{3005.949121}{173.2050808} = 17.35485534$$

$$\lambda < \lambda_{lim} \dots \dots \dots \text{short column}$$

Step -3) calculation of accidental eccentricity

a) In the x direction

$$e_a = \frac{l_0}{400} = 6.688896$$

b) In the y -direction

$$e_a = \frac{l_o}{400} = 7.514873$$

Step -4) equivalent first order eccentricity

4.1) in the x-direction

$$e_e = \max(0.6e_{02} + 0.4e_{01}, 0.4e_{02})$$

$$e_{02} = \frac{M_{02}}{N_{sd}} = \frac{-18.8974}{1579300} * 10^6 = -11.96568$$

$$e_{01} = \frac{M_{01}}{N_{sd}} = \frac{32.0729}{1579300} * 10^6 = 20.30830115$$

$$e_e = 0.94391186$$

4.2) in the y-direction

$$e_{02} = \frac{M_{02}}{N_{sd}} = \frac{-5.5412}{1579300} * 10^6 = 22.87756192$$

$$e_{01} = \frac{M_{01}}{N_{sd}} = \frac{0}{1579300} * 10^6 = 0$$

$$e_e = \max(0.6e_{02} + 0.4e_{01}, 0.4e_{02}) = -1.403457228$$

Step -5) calculation of second order moment

5.1) in the x-direction

Since the column under consideration is short, $e_2 = 0$

$$e_{tot} = e_a + e_e + e_2 = 6.688896 + 0.94391186 + 0 = 7.632807832 \text{ mm}$$

$$M_{sd, y} = e_{tot} * N_{sd} = 12054493.41 \text{ N-mm}$$

$$\mu_{sd, y} = \frac{M_{sd, y}}{f_{cd} b d^2} = 0.002320609$$

$$\text{Normalized axial force } V_{sd} = \frac{N_{ed}}{f_{cd}bd^2} = 0.209234234$$

5.2) in the y-direction

Since the column under consideration is short, $e_2 = 0$

$$e_{tot} = e_a + e_e + e_2 = 7.514873 + 3.860089913 + 0 = 11.37496272 \text{ mm}$$

$$M_{sd, x} = e_{tot} * N_{sd} = 27108838.62 \text{ N-mm}$$

$$\mu_{sd, x} = \frac{M_{sd, x}}{f_{cd}bd^2} = 0.007382581$$

Using $\frac{h}{h'} = \frac{b}{b'} = 0.1$, read the mechanical steel ratio ω from bi axial interaction charts,

using $V_{sd} = 0.209234234$, $\mu_{sd, x} = 0.0074$, $\mu_{sd, y} = 0.00232$.

$$\omega = 0, A_{s, cal} = \frac{\omega f_{cd}bd}{f_{yd}} = 0$$

Step -6) Check the minimum reinforcement

$$A_{s, min} = \max \left(0.1 * \frac{N_{ed}}{f_{yd}}, 0.002 * A_{column} \right) = 720 \text{ mm}^2.$$

Step -7) check the maximum reinforcement

$$A_{s, max} = 0.008 * A_{column} = 28800 \text{ mm}^2$$

Therefore, provide minimum reinforcement of 720 mm^2 .

Assuming $\emptyset 16$ bars to be used, provide 4 $\emptyset 16$.

The same procedures are followed to design columns for load combinations giving the maximum bending moments in the x-direction, maximum bending moment in the y-direction, and the load combination giving the minimum axial compressive force.

The summary of procedures and results are attached with this document.

7.4 Design data and analysis results for central column (C10)

Table 7.1: Central column (C10) end moments

Story	Combo	End moments			
		X(M3-3)		Y(M2-2)	
		M01(KN-m)	M02(KN-m)	M01(KN-m)	M02(KN-m)
Story -1	Combo-4	0.004	0.1049	0	9.068
	Combo-27	0	-27.76	0	36.025
	Combo-10	0	50.1335	0	-18.04
	Combo-24-1	0	50.1335	0	-18.04
Story -2	Combo-4	0.0314	-0.1355	-9.0923	15.2406
	Combo-9	32.0729	-18.89	0	-5.5412
	Combo-5	-0.0668	0.1402	-20.272	24.43
	Combo -24-1	-15.7	27.6	-19.273	19.411
Story -3	Combo-4	0.1305	-0.305	-33.08	19.032
	Combo-9	-23.680	27.85	17.164	-27.97
	Combo-5	-0.0285	0.184	26.2645	-40.378
	Combo -24-1	-20.354	24.5449	21.188	-31.913
Story -4	Combo-4	-0.2117	0.2983	19.0443	-29.403
	Combo-9	16.98	-21.155	16.88	-24.21
	Combo-5	-0.0577	0.1017	24.185	-33.920
	Combo-24-1	15.0918	-18.489	19.64	-26.49
Story -5	Combo-4	0.0887	0.0916	24.3882	32.9098
	Combo-9	8.2678	-11.272	18.5135	-24.57
	Combo-5	0.1293	-0.1847	27.0314	-35.280
	Combo-24-1	7.33	-9.91	19.85	-25.67
Story -6	combo2	0.8311	-2	11.74	-27.012
	combo5	0.1294	-0.3112	12.5082	-28.673
	combo6	0.1025	-0.2097	8.3894	-17.297
	combo 24-1	-4.8	11.79	10.67	-22.34

Table 7.2 : Compressive axial forces for central column corresponding to load combinations

Story	combo	Axial force(KN)
1	Combo 4	1692.98
1	Combo 27	1201.05
1	Combo 10	1102.46
1	Combo 24-1	1088.07
2	Combo 4	1579.3
2	Combo9	1014.45
2	Combo5	1558.59
2	Combo24-1	1003.43
3	Combo -4	1217.35
3	Combo -9	780.55
3	Combo-5	1205.68
3	Combo -24-1	774.53
4	Combo 4	857.48
4	Combo 9	547.197
4	Combo 5	851.713
4	Combo 24-1	544.385
5	Combo -4	499.457
5	Combo -9	313.602
5	Combo 5	496.88
5	Combo -24-1	312.41
6	Combo 4	142.36
6	Combo 5	106.66
6	Combo -24-1	141.601
6	Combo 4	77.9733

Table 7.3: summary of slenderness ratio for central column

story	X-direction	Y-direction
1	22.1264732	25.9803224
2	15.4473436	17.3548553
3	15.4473436	17.3548553
4	15.4473436	17.3548553
5	15.4473436	17.3548553
6	15.4473436	17.3548553

Table 7.4: Slenderness checking in the x-direction

story	λ	l lim	check
1	22.12647	48.65945	SHORT
1	22.12647	49.77594	SHORT
2	15.44734	58.56141	SHORT
2	15.44734	102.988	SHORT
2	15.44734	65.98045	SHORT
3	15.44734	73.47398	SHORT
3	15.44734	88.0597	SHORT
3	15.44734	64.04824	SHORT
4	15.44734	99.13917	SHORT
4	15.44734	102.9637	SHORT
4	15.44734	93.28331	SHORT
5	15.44734	39.44176	SHORT
5	15.44734	131.1795	SHORT
5	15.44734	129.3804	SHORT
6	15.44734	213.612	SHORT
6	15.44734	213.6383	SHORT
6	15.44734	212.7613	SHORT

Table 7.5: Slenderness checking in the y-direction

story	λ	l lim	check
1	25.98032	49.77594	SHORT
1	25.98032	49.77594	SHORT
2	17.35486	69.622	SHORT
2	17.35486	51.53628	SHORT
2	17.35486	81.63621	SHORT
3	17.35486	118.7163	SHORT
3	17.35486	79.88914	SHORT
3	17.35486	81.62502	SHORT
4	17.35486	96.58864	SHORT
4	17.35486	98.62672	SHORT
4	17.35486	100.4443	SHORT
5	17.35486	51.69374	SHORT
5	17.35486	132.2615	SHORT
5	17.35486	132.9451	SHORT
6	17.35486	215.5378	SHORT
6	17.35486	215.7003	SHORT
6	17.35486	220.6266	SHORT

Table 7.6: Reinforcement provision

Story	As,tot,Ned,max	As,tot,Mx,max	As,tot,My,max	As,tot,Ned,min
1	720	720	720	720
1	720	720	720	720
1	720	720	720	720
1	720	720	720	720
2	720	720	720	720
2	720	720	720	720
2	720	720	720	720
2	720	720	720	720
3	720	720	720	720
3	720	720	720	720
3	720	720	720	720
3	720	720	720	720
4	720	720	720	720
4	720	720	720	720
4	720	720	720	720
4	720	720	720	720
5	720	720	720	720
5	720	720	720	720
5	720	720	720	720
5	720	720	720	720
6	720	720	720	720
6	720	720	720	720
6	720	720	720	720
6	35.59	26.665	35.40025	19.493325

When considering the design of edge and corner columns the same procedures were followed and the same results were also obtained when compared with central column design illustrated above.

7.5 Design of columns for shear

In columns shear values are very small as compared to axial force and the bending moments acting on it. The shear forces may be magnified in value and effect when the structure to be constructed is to be located in seismic regions. When such case happen, the transverse reinforcements should be closely spaced and its advised to place the ties into circular shape with a pitch angle ranging 35-85mm. such types of columns are known to be spiral columns.

7.5.1 Diameter of stirrups

The minimum diameter of transverse reinforcements used for columns should not be less than 6mm or one fourth of the diameter of longitudinal bars used, whichever is greater.

$$\phi_{transverse} = \max \left[6mm, \frac{1}{4} * \phi_{longitudinal} \right]$$
$$= \max (6mm, 16/4) = 6mm$$

Provide 6mm diameter stirrups

7.5.2 Spacing of stirrups

The lesser value of the following distances should be used as spacing for stirrups:

- 20 times the lesser diameter of longitudinal bars
- the lesser dimension of the column
- 400mm

$$\text{Spacing} = \min (20 * 16, 600, 400) = 320$$

Provide $\phi 6$ c/c 320

CHAPTER 8 DETAILING OF DESIGNED MEMBERS

8.1 SLAB DETAILING

8.2 STAIR DETAILING

8.3 BEAM DETAILING

8.4 Column detailing

CHAPTER 9 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

9.1 Conclusion

Structural design of the building was conducted in accordance with the revised Ethiopian building code of standards ES EN 2004:2015. The structure, overall, did not pose, any special condition that requires special attention throughout the design process. The most dominant force as compared to the other forces that act on the structure, is earth quake load acting in the horizontal direction.

In calculating the center of mass of the building, dimensions from the architectural drawings were used but in case of designing these members, the dimensions have been changed. It should be noted that changing these cross section should not affect the overall stability of the structure.

The structure, at its initial stage of design, was observed to have small displacements making it quite rigid and thus second order effects were neglected. Thus the frame as a whole is considered as non-sway frame. Due to this and other factors the structure will not pose wall requirement for its stability. The shear wall induced in the structure is for supporting the lift shaft of the lift that will run from first to last story for movement of people and goods throughout the structure.

Most of the loads on the structure were in a relatively small range and the design of most members has resulted in provision of minimum reinforcement. Especially in the case of column design, the columns selected for design (central, edge and corner columns) has been provided minimum reinforcements. This implies compressive strength of concrete for columns and its crossection are somewhat large making the required steel reinforcement number to be small.

9.2 Recommendation

In dealing with the analysis of earth quake load, for the sake of simplicity in calculation and scope limitation, the structure was designed as ductility class low (DCL). In the actual analysis the structure should be designed for ductility class medium (DCM).

As discussed earlier steel reinforcements that were resulted from the design of members are minimum. Thus the cross sections should be reduced to a reasonable level that will not harm the stability of the overall structure.

Whenever determining the depth for flexural members like beams and slabs, a modifying factor of $310 / \sigma_s$ should be used. This is due to the fact that the code (ES EN 2004: 2015) assumes steel grade of S-500 is to be employed and any depth calculation using steel grade other than it should be modified by the factor.

The structure should be modeled without diaphragm first before rushing into modeling it with diaphragm. The conditions that are resulted from modeling without diaphragm should be checked for exceedance of the limit.

While modeling structures on structural design soft wares like ETABS, it is recommended not to model the slab together the frame elements and run analysis as it will add stiffness to the structure which might lead to faulty results.

REFERENCES

Euro code 0: Basis of Structural Design. Brussels, 2001.

Euro code 1: Actions on Structures - Part 1-1: General Actions Densities, Self-Weight, Imposed Loads for Buildings. Brussels, 2001.

Euro code 1: Actions on Structures - General Actions - Part 1-4: Wind Actions. Brussels, 2004

Euro code 2: Design of Concrete Structures. Part 1-1: General Rules and Rules for Buildings. Brussels, 2004.

Euro code 7: Geotechnical Design — Part 1: General Rules. Brussels, 2001.

Euro code 8: Design of Structures for Earthquake Resistance Part 1: General Rules, Seismic Actions and Rules for Buildings. Brussels, 2003.

Arthur H. Nilsson, David Darwin and Charles W.Dolan, 『Design of concrete structures』, 14th edition,

James K.Wight and James G.MacGregor, 『Reinforced Concrete Mechanics and Design』, 6th Edition

Pillai and Menon, 『Reinforced Concrete Mechanics and Design』

The Institute of Structural Engineers And The Concrete Society, —Standard Method of detailing Structural Concrete』, 3rd Edition

M.Y.H. Bagash, 『Structural detailing In Concrete』, Oxford

Aait letcure notes; 2015

APPENDICES

APPINDEX-A: Analysis results for truss

Frame	P _u	M _u	V _u	Frame	P _u	M _u	V _u
2	-1.791	0	-17.246	42	-155.723	0	-3.847
3	-2.053	0	3.548	43	-172.959	0	1.745
4	-6.052	0	2.097	44	-180.209	0	0.979
5	-8.979	0	1.374	45	-173.812	0	0.688
6	-11.576	0	1.034	46	-165.098	0	0.559
7	-14.055	0	0.854	47	-155.618	0	0.503
8	-16.471	0	0.752	48	-145.776	0	0.482
9	-19.372	0	0.678	49	-135.703	0	0.502
10	-17.203	0	0.638	50	-125.511	0	0.422
11	2.697	0	-0.043	51	-114.116	0	1.458
12	-20.849	0	-0.69	52	-115.033	0	-1.603
13	-19.436	0	-0.675	53	-125.771	0	-0.359
14	-16.448	0	-0.75	54	-135.937	0	-0.512
15	-14.048	0	-0.85	55	-146.004	0	-0.478
16	-11.564	0	-1.028	56	-155.832	0	-0.501
17	-8.966	0	-1.364	57	-165.292	0	-0.556
18	-6.037	0	-2.075	58	-173.973	0	-0.683
19	-2.038	0	-3.485	59	-180.308	0	-0.972
20	-1.76	0	17.491	60	-172.911	0	-1.727
22	150.773	0	-4.282	61	-156.216	0	3.866
23	177.726	0	1.665	62	-10.542	0	0
24	169.181	0	0.903	63	5.92	0	1.41E-17
25	159.133	0	0.633	64	10.421	0	1.87E-17
26	148.732	0	0.519	65	13.146	0	4.68E-18
27	138.144	0	0.475	66	15.448	0	0
28	127.417	0	0.466	67	17.655	0	1.87E-17
29	116.581	0	0.479	68	19.838	0	4.68E-18
30	105.608	0	0.536	69	22.158	0	0
31	96.84	0	1.057	70	19.04	0	0
32	96.882	0	-1.174	71	22.926	0	0
33	107.363	0	-0.522	72	22.237	0	0
34	118.369	0	-0.469	73	19.822	0	4.68E-18
35	129.195	0	-0.466	74	17.643	0	1.87E-17
36	139.912	0	-0.472	75	15.432	0	0
37	150.485	0	-0.516	76	13.126	0	4.68E-18
38	160.861	0	-0.628	77	10.393	0	1.87E-17
39	170.866	0	-0.896	78	5.872	0	1.41E-17
40	179.307	0	-1.646	79	-10.631	0	0
41	152.026	0	4.303				

APPINDEX-B: Depth determination

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

Panel ID	LX(mm)	LY (mm)	span type	L_{eff}	L/d	Adjusted L/d	depth(d_{eff})	Depth (D)	DKM K
1	4000	4500	End span	4000	26	38.22	104.65475	134.6572475	
2	4000	4500	End span	4000	26	38.22	104.67475	139.6572475	
3	4000	4500	End span	4000	26	38.22	104.62475	139.6572475	
4	4000	4500	End span	4000	26	38.22	104.475	139.6572475	
5	4000	4500	End span	4000	26	38.22	104.65775	139.6572475	
6	4000	4500	End span	4000	26	38.22	104.62475	139.6572475	
7	1850	4500	End span	1850	26	38.22	48.407698	83.40397698	
8	1850	4500	Interior span	1850	30	44.1	41.911338	76.95011338	
9	1850	4500	Interior span	1850	30	44.1	41.950113	76.95011338	170
10	1850	4500	Interior span	1850	30	44.1	41.951338	76.95011338	
11	1850	4500	Interior span	1850	30	44.1	41.951338	76.95011338	
12	1850	4500	End span	1850	26	38.22	48.403698	83.40397698	
13	4500	4500	End span	4500	26	38.22	117.73035	152.7394035	
14	4500	4500	End span	4500	30	44.1	102.0463	137.0408163	
15	4500	4500	End span	4500	26	38.22	117.73935	152.7394035	
16	4500	4500	End span	4500	26	38.22	117.73035	152.7394035	
17	4500	4500	Interior span	4500	30	44.1	102.0163	137.0408163	
18	4500	4500	End span	4500	26	38.22	117.73035	152.7394035	
19	4500	4500	End span	4500	26	38.22	117.73935	152.7394035	
20	4500	4500	End span	4500	26	38.22	117.2	152.74	
21	4500	4500	End Span	4500	26	38.22	117.2	152.75	170
22	4500	4500	End span	4500	26	38.22	117.73935	152.7394035	
C-1	2080	4500	cantilever	2080	8	11.76	176.87083	211.8707483	230
C-2	2080	4500	cantilever	2080	8	11.76	176.07483	211.8707483	
C-3	2080	4500	cantilever	2080	8	11.76	176.87483	211.8707483	
C-4	2080	4500	cantilever	2080	8	11.76	176.87483	211.8707483	
C-5	2080	4500	cantilever	2080	8	11.76	176.87083	211.8707483	
C-6	2080	4500	cantilever	2080	8	11.76	176.87483	211.8707483	
C-7	2250	4500	Cantilever	2250	8	11.76	191.32653	226.3265306	230
C-8	2250	4500	Cantilever	2250	8	11.76	191.32506	226.3265306	
C-9	2250	4500	Cantilever	2250	8	11.7647	191.25	226.25	

APPINDEX-C: Design load computation for panels on the slab

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

Panel -ID	Area(m2)	DL _{floor finish}	DL _{RCslab}	DL _{cement screed}	DL _{plastering}	DL partition	Un-factored Total-Dead load(KN/m ²)	Un-factored Total-live load(KN/m ²)
1	18	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.4446	2
2	18	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.4446	2
3	18	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.4446	2
4	18	0.69	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.79	2
5	18	0.69	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.79	2
6	18	0.346	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.446	2
7	8.325	0.69	0.69	4.25	0.69	1	7.32	2
8	8.325	0.69	0.69	4.25	0.69	1	7.32	2
9	8.325	0.69	0.69	4.25	0.69	1	7.32	2
10	8.325	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1	6.9746	2
11	8.325	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1	6.9746	2
12	8.325	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1	6.9746	2
13	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.4446	2
14	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.6	7.5746	2
15	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1	6.9746	2
16	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1	6.97	2
17	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.6	7.5746	2
18	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.4446	2
19	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.4446	2
20	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.4446	2
21	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.4446	2
22	20.25	0.3446	0.69	4.25	0.69	1.5	7.4446	2
C-1	9.36	0.69	0.69	5.75	0.69	1	8.82	2.5
C-2	9.36	0.69	0.69	5.75	0.69	1	8.82	2.5
C-3	9.36	0.69	0.69	5.75	0.69	1	8.82	2.5
C-4	9.36	0.69	0.69	5.75	0.69	1	8.82	2.5
C-5	9.36	0.69	0.69	5.75	0.69	1	8.82	2.5
C-6	9.36	0.69	0.69	5.75	0.69	1	8.82	2.5
c-7	10.125	0.69	0.69	5.75	0.69	1	8.82	2.5
c-8	10.125	0.69	0.69	5.75	0.69	1	8.82	2.5
c-9	10.125	0.69	0.69	5.75	0.69	1	8.82	2.5

APPINDEX-D₁: Moment computation for panels on the slab

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

Panel	lx	Ly	ly/lx	Load		Pd	coefficients		moment	
				DL	LL				Msx	Mfy
1	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{sx} =$	0.057	Msx	11.90179152
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.043	Mfx	8.97854448
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.045	Msy	9.3961512
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.034	Mfy	7.09931424
2	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.05	Msx	10.440168
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.037	Mfx	7.72572432
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.037	Msy	7.72572432
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.028	Mfy	5.84649408
3	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.05	Msx	10.440168
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.037	Mfx	7.72572432
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.037	Msy	7.72572432
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.028	Mfy	5.84649408
4	4	4.5	1.125	7.79	2	13.5165	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.05	Msx	10.8132
	4	4.5	1.125	7.79	2	13.5165	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.037	Mfx	8.001768
	4	4.5	1.125	7.79	2	13.5165	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.037	Msy	8.001768
	4	4.5	1.125	7.79	2	13.5165	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.028	Mfy	6.055392
5	4	4.5	1.125	7.79	2	13.5165	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.05	Msx	10.8132
	4	4.5	1.125	7.79	2	13.5165	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.037	Mfx	8.001768
	4	4.5	1.125	7.79	2	13.5165	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.037	Msy	8.001768
	4	4.5	1.125	7.79	2	13.5165	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.028	Mfy	6.055392
6	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.057	Msx	11.90179152
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.043	Mfx	8.97854448

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.045	$M_{sy} =$	9.3961512
	4	4.5	1.125	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.034	$M_{fy} =$	7.09931424
7	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	-	$M_{sx} =$	5.51
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882	$\beta_{fx} =$	-	$M_{fx} =$	3.1
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882				-
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882				-
8	1.8 5	4.5	2.42	7.32	2	12.882	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	-	$M_{sx} =$	5.51
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882	$\beta_{fx} =$	-	$M_{fx} =$	3.1
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4 2	7.32	2	12.882				-
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882				-
9	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	-	$M_{sx} =$	5.51
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882	$\beta_{fx} =$	-	$M_{fx} =$	3.1
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882				-
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	7.32	2	12.882				-
10	1.8 5	4.5	2.43	6.9746	2	12.41571	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	-	$M_{sx} =$	5.02
	1.8 5	4.5	2.42	6.9746	2	12.41571	$\beta_{fx} =$	-	$M_{fx} =$	2.82
	1.8 5	4.5	2.43	6.9746	2	12.41571				-
	1.8 5	4.5	2.43	6.9746	2	12.41571				-
11	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	6.9746	2	12.41571	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	-	$M_{sx} =$	5.02
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	6.9746	2	12.41571	$\beta_{fx} =$	-	$M_{fx} =$	2.82
	1.8 5	4.5	2.43	6.9746	2	12.41571				-
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	6.9746	2	12.41571				-
12	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	6.9746	2	12.41571	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	-	$M_{sx} =$	5.02

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	6.9746	2	12.41571	$\beta_{fx} =$	-	Mfx =	2.82
	1.8 5	4.5	2.4	6.9746	2	12.41571				-
	1.8 5	4.5	2.432	6.9746	2	12.41571				-
13	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.039	Msx =	10.30640335
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.03	Mfx =	7.928002575
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.037	Msy =	9.777869843
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.028	Mfy =	7.39946907
14	4.5	4.5	1	7.5746	2	13.22571	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.031	Msx =	8.302439453
	4.5	4.5	1	7.5746	2	13.22571	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.024	Mfx =	6.42769506
	4.5	4.5	1	7.5746	2	13.22571	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.032	Msy =	8.57026008
	4.5	4.5	1	7.5746	2	13.22571	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.024	Mfy =	6.42769506
15	4.5	4.5	1	6.97	2	13.22571	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.031	Msx =	8.302439453
	4.5	4.5	1	6.97	2	13.22571	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.024	Mfx =	6.42769506
	4.5	4.5	1	6.97	2	13.22571	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.032	Msy =	8.57026008
	4.5	4.5	1	6.97	2	13.22571	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.024	Mfy =	6.42769506
16	4.5	4.5	1	6.97	2	12.4095	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.031	Msx =	7.790063625
	4.5	4.5	1	6.97	2	12.4095	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.024	Mfx =	6.031017
	4.5	4.5	1	6.97	2	12.4095	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.032	Msy =	8.041356
	4.5	4.5	1	6.97	2	12.4095	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.024	Mfy =	6.031017
17	4.5	4.5	1	7.5746	2	13.22571	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.031	Msx =	8.302439453
	4.5	4.5	1	7.5746	2	13.22571	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.024	Mfx =	6.42769506
	4.5	4.5	1	7.5746	2	13.22571	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.032	Msy =	8.57026008
	4.5	4.5	1	7.5746	2	13.22571	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.024	Mfy =	6.42769506
18	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.039	Msx =	10.30640335

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.03	M _{fx} =	7.928002575
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.037	M _{sy} =	9.777869843
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.028	M _{fy} =	7.39946907
19	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.039	M _{sx} =	10.30640335
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.03	M _{fx} =	7.928002575
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.037	M _{sy} =	9.777869843
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.028	M _{fy} =	7.39946907
20	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{\square\square} =$	0.039	M _{sx} =	10.30640335
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fx} =$	0.03	M _{fx} =	7.928002575
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{sy} =$	0.037	M _{sy} =	9.777869843
	4.5	4.5	1	7.4446	2	13.05021	$\beta_{fy} =$	0.028	M _{fy} =	7.39946907

APPINDEX-D₂: Moment computation for cantilevers

cantilever	Factored Load		Design load(KN/m ²)	Design moment(KN-m/m)
	Dead load	live load		
C-1	8.82	2.5	15.657	33.86
C-2	8.82	2.5	15.657	33.86
C-3	8.82	2.5	15.657	33.86
C-4	8.82	2.5	15.657	33.86
C-5	8.82	2.5	15.657	33.86
C-6	8.82	2.5	15.657	33.86
C-7	8.82	2.5	15.657	39.63
C-8	8.82	2.5	15.657	39.63
C-9	8.82	2.5	15.657	39.63

APPINDEX-D₃: Moment adjustment

	Panel-1	Panel-7
Length	4m	1.85
Stiffness(k)= EI/L	EI/4	EI/1.85
Distribution factor=k ₁ /k ₁ +k ₂	0.32	0.68

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

M adjusted	9.85	9.85
------------	------	------

APPINDEX-E₁: Reinforcement provided for slab

panel	Design moment	d	μ_{sd}	kz	Z	As,calc	As,min	spacing	Ast,prov	S prov	
1	M _{sx} =9.85	161	0.024	0.983	158.263	178.8967323	272.09	288.6537	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fx} =10.95	161	0.026	0.982	158.102	199.077568	272.09	288.65	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{sy} =8.58	161	0.020	0.985	158.585	155.5144514	272.09	288.5	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fy} =7.92	161	0.019	0.99	159.39	142.8267922	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
2	M _{sx} =8.87	161	0.021	0.9845	158.5045	160.8524183	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fx} =9.29	161	0.022	0.984	158.424	168.5544841	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{sy} =7.72	161	0.018	0.9856	158.6816	139.8415731	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fy} =5.84	161	0.014	0.9879	159.0519	105.5405995	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
3	M _{sx} =8.87	161	0.021	0.9845	158.5045	160.8524183	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fx} =9.29	161	0.022	0.9837	158.3757	168.6058884	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{sy} =7.86	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	142.3920074	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fy} =5.84	161	0.014	0.988	159.068	105.5299173	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
4	M _{sx} =8.95	161	0.021	0.9841	158.4401	162.3691431	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fx} =9.86	161	0.024	0.983	158.263	179.0783533	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{sy} =8	161	0.019	0.985	158.585	145.0018195	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fy} =6	161	0.014	0.9843	158.4723	108.8287048	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
5	M _{sx} =8.95	161	0.021	0.9845	158.5045	162.3031729	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fx} =9.86	161	0.024	0.983	158.263	179.0783533	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{sy} =8.7	161	0.021	0.9845	158.5045	157.7695647	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fy} =6	161	0.014	0.988	159.068	108.4211479	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{sx} =9.7	161	0.023	0.9835	158.4	176.08	272.09	288.7	272.09	260	Ø c/c260
	M _{fx} =11.1	161	0.027	0.9815	158.0215	201.9074622	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{sy} =8.7	161	0.021	0.9845	158.5045	157.7695647	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
M _{fy} =7.8	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	141.3050455	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260	
7	M _{sx} =9.85	161	0.024	0.983	158.263	178.8967323	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fx} =3.1	161	0.007	0.987	158.907	56.07434849	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
8	M _{sx} =8.87	161	0.021	0.9845	158.5045	160.8524183	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fx} =3.1	161	0.007	0.987	158.907	56.07434849	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
9	M _{sx} =8.87	161	0.021	0.9845	158.5045	160.8524183	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fx} =3.1	161	0.007	0.987	158.907	56.07434849	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
10	M _{sx} =8.95	161	0.021	0.9845	158.5045	162.3031729	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

	Mfx=2.82	161	0.006	0.986	158.746	51.06130247	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
11	Msx=8.95	161	0.021	0.9845	158.5045	162.3031729	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=2.82	161	0.006	0.986	158.746	51.06130247	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
12	Msx=9.7	161	0.023	0.9835	158.3435	176.0828526	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=2.82	161	0.006	0.986	158.746	51.06130247	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
13	Msx=10.3	161	0.025	0.9825	158.1825	187.1648803	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=7.9	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	143.1166487	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Msy=9.17	161	0.022	0.984	158.424	166.3772465	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfy=7.93	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	143.6601296	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
14	Msx=8.57	161	0.020	0.9845	158.5045	155.4120885	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=6.42	161	0.015	0.9875	158.9875	116.0693678	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Msy=9.17	161	0.022	0.984	158.424	166.3772465	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfy=6.42	161	0.015	0.9875	158.9875	116.0693678	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
15	Msx=8.3	161	0.02	0.985	158.585	150.4393877	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=7.26	161	0.017	0.9865	158.8265	131.3890663	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Msy=8.57	161	0.020	0.9845	158.5045	155.4120885	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfy=6.7	161	0.016	0.987	158.907	121.1929467	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
16	Msx=8.3	161	0.020	0.985	158.585	150.4393877	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=6.03	161	0.014	0.988	159.068	108.9632536	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Msy=8.3	161	0.020	0.985	158.585	150.4393877	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfy=6.03	161	0.014	0.988	159.068	108.9632536	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
17	Msx=9.17	161	0.022	0.984	158.424	166.3772465	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=6.42	161	0.015	0.987	158.987	116.0693678	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Msy=8.3	161	0.020	0.985	158.585	150.4393877	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfy=6.42	161	0.015	0.9875	158.9875	116.0693678	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
18	Msx=10.3	161	0.025	0.9825	158.1825	187.1648803	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=7.9	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	143.1166487	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Msy=9.17	161	0.022	0.984	158.424	166.3772465	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfy=8	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	144.9282518	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
19	Msx=10.3	161	0.025	0.9825	158.1825	187.1648803	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=7.9	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	143.1166487	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Msy=9.17	161	0.022	0.984	158.424	166.3772465	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfy=7.93	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	143.6601296	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
20	Msx=10.3	161	0.025	0.9825	158.1825	187.1648803	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfx=7.9	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	143.1166487	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Msy=9.7	161	0.023	0.9835	158.3435	176.0828526	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	Mfy=7.39	161	0.018	0.986	158.746	133.8095834	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
21	Msx=10.3	161	0.025	0.9825	158.1825	187.1648803	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

	M _{fx} =7.9	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	143.1166487	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{sy} =9.17	161	0.022	0.984	158.424	166.3772465	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fy} =7.93	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	143.6601296	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
22	M _{sx} =10.3	161	0.025	0.9825	158.1825	187.1648803	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fx} =7.9	161	0.019	0.9855	158.6655	143.1166487	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{sy} =9.7	161	0.023	0.9835	158.3435	176.0828526	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260
	M _{fy} =7.39	161	0.018	0.986	158.746	133.8095834	272.09	288.653754	272.09	260	Ø10 c/c 260

APPINDEX-E₂: Reinforcement provided for cantilever

Cantilever	Msd	d	μsd	Kz	Z	As,calc	As,min	spacing	Ast,prov	S prov	
c-1	33.86	192	0.0648666	0.966	185.5	524.752	324.48	149.59	18.561	130	Ø10 c/c 130
c-2	33.86	192	0.0648666	0.966	185.5	524.752	324.48	149.59	18.561	130	Ø10 c/c 130
c-3	33.86	192	0.0648666	0.966	185.5	524.752	324.48	149.59	18.561	130	Ø10 c/c 130
c-4	33.86	192	0.0648666	0.966	185.5	524.752	324.48	149.59	18.561	130	Ø10 c/c 130
c-5	33.86	192	0.0648666	0.966	185.5	524.752	324.48	149.59	18.561	130	Ø10 c/c 130
c-6	33.86	192	0.0648666	0.966	185.5	524.752	324.48	149.59	18.561	130	Ø10 c/c 130
c-7	39.63	192	0.0759204	0.958	183.9	619.303	324.48	126.76	21.724	110	Ø10 c/c 110
c-8,9,10	39.63	192	0.0759204	0.958	183.9	619.303	324.48	126.76	21.724	110	Ø10 c/c 110

APPINDEX-F₁: Load transferred to beam from the two-way slab

Panel	Ly	Lx	factored Dead-Load	factored Live-Load	Shear-co-efficient	Shear force due to(Vs)	
						DL	LL
Panel-1 panel-6	4.5	4	10.04	3	β _{vx,c} =0.445	17.8712	5.34
	4.5	4	10.04	3	β _{vy,c} =0.4	16.064	4.8
	4.5	4	10.04	3	β _{vx,d} =0.295	11.8472	3.54
	4.5	4	10.04	3	β _{vy,d} =0.26	10.4416	3.12
Panel-2 panel-3	4.5	4	10.04	3	β _{vx,c} =0.41	16.4656	4.92
	4.5	4	10.04	3	β _{vy,c} =0.36	14.4576	4.32
	4.5	4	10.04	3	β _{vx,d} =0.275	11.044	3.3
	4.5	4	10.04	3	β _{vy,c} =0.36	10.441	3.12
Panel-4 panel-5	4.5	4.5	10.51	3	β _{vx,c} =0.41	19.4	5.53
	4.5	4.5	10.51	3	β _{vy,c} =0.36	17.026	4.86
	4.5	4.5	10.51	3	β _{vx,d} =0.275	13	3.71

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

	4.5	4.5	10.51	3	$\beta_{vy,c}=0.26$	12.3	3.51
Panel-1 panel-17	4.5	4.5	10.18	3	$\beta_{vx,c}=0.33$	15.1173	4.455
	4.5	4.5	10.18	3	$\beta_{vy,c}=0.33$	15.1173	4.455
	4.5	4.5	10.18	3	$\beta_{vx,c}=0.33$	15.1173	4.455
	4.5	4.5	10.18	3	$\beta_{vy,c}=0.33$	15.1173	4.455
Panel-15 panel-16	4.5	4.5	9.4	3	$\beta_{vx,c}=0.36$	15.228	4.86
	4.5	4.5	9.4	3	$\beta_{vy,c}=0.36$	15.228	4.86
	4.5	4.5	9.4	3	$\beta_{vx,c}=0.36$	15.228	4.86
	4.5	4.5	9.4	3	$\beta_{vx,d}=0.24$	10.152	3.24
Panel-13 panel-18	4.5	4.5	10.04	3	$\beta_{vx,c}=0.36$	16.2648	4.86
	4.5	4.5	10.04	3	$\beta_{vy,c}=0.36$	16.2648	4.86
	4.5	4.5	10.04	3	$\beta_{vx,c}=0.36$	16.2648	4.86
	4.5	4.5	10.04	3	$\beta_{vy,d}=0.24$	10.8432	3.24
Panel-19 panel-20 panel-21 panel-22	4.5	4.5	10.04	3	$\beta_{vx,c}=0.36$	16.2648	4.86
	4.5	4.5	10.04	3	$\beta_{vy,c}=0.36$	16.2648	4.86
	4.5	4.5	10.04	3	$\beta_{vx,c}=0.36$	16.2648	4.86
	4.5	4.5	10.04	3	$\beta_{vy,d}=0.24$	10.8432	3.24

APPINDEX-F₂: Load transferred to beam from cantilever part

Panel	L _y	L _x	Factored Dead load	Factored live load	Shear force due dead load	Shear force due live load
Panel-6 Panel-7	4.5	1.85	9.9	3	9.16	2.75
Panel-8 Panel-9	4.5	1.85	9.9	3	9.16	2.75
Panel-10 Panel-11 Panel-12	4.5	1.85	9.9	3	9.16	2.75
Cantilever-1 Cantilever-2	4.5	2.08	11.88	3.75	26.63	8.34
Cantilever-3 Cantilever-4	4.5	2.08	11.88	3.75	26.63	8.34
Cantilever-5 Cantilever-6	4.5	2.08	11.88	3.75	26.63	8.34
Cantilever-7 Cantilever-8	4.5	2.25	11.88	3.75	26.63	8.34
Cantilever-9	4.5	2.25	11.88	3.75	26.63	8.34

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

APPINDEX-G: Moment computation for tanker slab

Panel	Lx	ly	LL	DL	factored LL	FACTTOE D DL	Moment		
1'	4.5	4.5	0.5	22.95	0.75	23.7	0.057	M _{sx} =	27.355725
	4.5	4.5	0.5	22.95	0.75	13.05021	0.043	M _{fx} =	11.36347036
	4.5	4.5	0.5	22.95	0.75	13.05021	0.045	M _{sy} =	11.89200386
	4.5	4.5	17	0.5	22.95	0.75	M _{fy} =	8.985069585	
2'	4.7	4.8	17	0.5	22.95	0.75	M _{sx} =	29.17944	
	4.7	4.8	17	0.5	22.95	0.75	M _{fx} =	12.12103505	
	4.7	4.8	17	0.5	22.95	0.75	M _{sy} =	12.68480412	
	4.7	4.8	17	0.5	22.95	0.75	M _{fy} =	9.584074224	

APPINDEX-H₁: External wind pressure coefficients on walls

Zone	A		B		C		D		E	
h/d	C _{pe,10}	C _{pe,1}								
5	-2.6		-1.9		-0.5		1.8		-0.7	
1	-2.6		-1.9		-0.5		1.8		0.5	
≤0.25	-2.6		-1.9		-0.5		1.7		-0.3	

APPINDEX-H₂: External pressure coefficients

Zone	A		B		D					
C _{pe,10}	-1.2		-0.8		0.77					
C _{pe,1}	-1.4		-0.8		0.77					
C _{pe}	Floor		W _e (kN/m ²)		h(m)		b(m)		Force (KN)	
We(N)	Service									
	4 th		0.37268		3.06		27.20		31.09	
	3 rd		0.37268		3.06		27.20		31.09	
	2 nd		0.37268		3.06		27.20		31.09	
	1 st		0.37268		3.06		27.20		31.09	
Ground		0.37268		3.06		27.20		31.09		

=APPINDEX-J: Internal wind pressure

Zone	C _{pi}	w _i (N/m ²)
A	-0.3	-145.2
B	-0.3	-145.2
D	-0.2	96.8

APPINDEX-K : Calculation of Center of mass and weight of building for Ground

floor

APPINDEX-K₁: Grade beam

beam-ID	L(m)	b(m)	D(m)	Γ_w	Weigh t	Xi	Yi	W*Xi	W*Yi
B-1	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	2.25	0	40.5	0
B-2	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	6.75	0	121.5	0
B-3	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	11.25	0	202.5	0
B-4	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	15.75	0	283.5	0
B-5	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	20.25	0	364.5	0
B-6	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	22.5	0	405	0
B-7	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	2.25	4	40.5	72
B-8	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	6.75	4	121.5	72
B-9	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	11.25	4	202.5	72
B-10	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	15.75	4	283.5	72
B-11	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	20.25	4	364.5	72
B-12	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	22.5	4	405	72
B-13	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	2.25	5.85	40.5	105.3
B-14	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	6.75	5.85	121.5	105.3
B-15	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	11.25	5.85	202.5	105.3
B-16	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	15.75	5.85	283.5	105.3
B-17	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	20.25	5.85	364.5	105.3
B-18	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	22.5	5.85	405	105.3
B-19	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	2.25	10.3	40.5	186.3
B-20	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	6.75	10.3	121.5	186.3
B-21	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	11.25	10.3	202.5	186.3
B-22	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	15.75	10.3	283.5	186.3
B-23	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	20.25	10.3	364.5	186.3
B-24	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	22.5	10.3	405	186.3
B-25	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	2.25	14.8	40.5	267.3
B-26	2.08	0.4	0.4	25	8.32	5.54	14.8	46.0928	123.55
B-27	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	24.75	14.8	445.5	267.3
B-28	2.08	0.4	0.4	25	8.32	21.46	14.8	178.547	123.55
B-29	4.5	0.4	0.4	0	0	2.25	19.3	0	0
B-30	2.08	0.4	0.4	25	8.32	5.54	19.3	46.0928	160.99
B-31	2.08	0.4	0.4	25	8.32	21.46	19.3	178.547	160.99
B-32	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	24.75	19.3	445.5	348.3
B-33	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	2.25	23.8	40.5	429.3
B-34	2.08	0.4	0.4	25	8.32	5.54	23.8	46.0928	198.43
B-35	2.08	0.4	0.4	25	8.32	21.46	23.8	178.547	198.43
B-36	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	24.75	23.8	445.5	429.3
B-37	4	0.4	0.4	25	16	0	2	0	32

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

B-38	1.85	0.4	0.4	25	7.4	0	4.92	0	36.445
B-39	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	0	8.07	0	145.26
B-40	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	0	12.5	0	226.26
B-41	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	0	17.0	0	307.26
B-42	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	0	19.3	0	347.76
B-43	4	0.4	0.4	25	16	4.5		72	32
B-44	1.85	0.4	0.4	25	7.4	4.5	4.92	33.3	36.445
B-45	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	4.5	8.07	81	145.26
B-46	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	4.5	12.5	81	226.26
B-47	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	4.5	17.0	81	307.26
B-48	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	4.5	19.3	81	347.76
B-49	4	0.4	0.4	25	16	9	2	144	32
B-50	1.85	0.4	0.4	25	7.4	9	4.92	66.6	36.445
B-51	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	9	8.07	162	145.26
B-52	4	0.4	0.4	25	16	13.5	2	216	32
B-53	1.85	0.4	0.4	25	7.4	13.5	4.92	99.9	36.445
B-54	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	13.5	8.07	243	145.26
B-55	4	0.4	0.4	25	16	18	2	288	32
B-56	1.85	0.4	0.4	25	7.4	18	4.92	133.2	36.445
B-57	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	18	8.07	324	145.26
B-58	4	0.4	0.4	25	16	22.5	2	360	32
B-59	1.85	0.4	0.4	25	7.4	22.5	4.92	166.5	36.445
B-60	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	22.5	8.07	405	145.26
B-61	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	22.5	12.5	405	226.26
B-62	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	22.5	17.0	405	307.26
B-63	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	22.5	19.3	405	347.76
B-64	4	0.4	0.4	25	16	27	2	432	32
B-65	1.85	0.4	0.4	25	7.4	27	4.92	199.8	36.445
B-66	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	27	8.07	486	145.26
B-67	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	27	12.5	486	226.26
B-68	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	27	17.0	486	307.26
B-69	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	27	19.3	486	347.76
B-70	4.5	0.4	0.4	25	18	27	19.3 2	486	347.76
				∑	1095.7			15075.7	10257.

APPINDEX-K₂: Partition wall on ground floor

PARTITIO N- ID	L(m)	hi(m)	D(m)	Γ_w	Weight	X_i	Y_i	$W \cdot X_i$	$W \cdot Y_i$
P-1	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	0.85	0	6.19038	0
P-2	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	3.65	0	26.5822	0
P-3	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	5.35	0	38.9629	0
P-4	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	8.15	0	59.3548	0
P-5	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	9.85	0	71.7355	0
P-6	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	12.6	0	92.1274	0
P-7	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	14.3	0	104.508	0
P-8	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	17.1	0	124.900	0
P-9	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	18.3	0	133.639	0
P-10	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	21.6	0	157.672	0
P-11	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	23.3	0	170.053	0
P-12	1.7	1.5	0.2	14	7.2828	26.1	0	190.44	0
P-13	1.3	1.5	0.15	14	4.1769	0.55	4	2.29729	16.7076
P-14	0.98	1.5	0.15	14	3.1487	2.49	4	7.84036	12.5949
P-15	0.42	1.5	0.15	14	1.3655	3.99	4	5.44844	5.4621
P-16	0.42	1.5	0.15	14	1.3655	4.71	4	6.43435	5.4621
P-17	0.98	1.5	0.15	14	3.1487	5.79	4	18.2312	12.5949
P-18	1.4	1.5	0.15	14	4.4982	8.81	4	39.656	17.9928
P-19	1.4	1.5	0.15	14	4.4982	9.7	4	43.6325	17.9928
P-20	0.98	1.5	0.15	14	3.1487	10.8	4	34.2897	12.5949
P-21	0.42	1.5	0.15	14	1.3655	13.3	4	18.1614	5.4621
P-22	0.42	1.5	0.15	14	1.3655	13.7	4	18.7076	5.4621

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

P-23	0.98	1.5	0.15	14	3.1487	15. 3	4	48.3016	12.5949
P-24	1.4	1.5	0.15	14	4.4982	17. 3	4	77.8188	17.9928
P-25	1.4	1.5	0.15	14	4.4982	18. 7	4	84.1163	17.9928
P-26	0.98	1.5	0.15	14	3.1487	20. 7	4	65.4623	12.5949
P-27	0.42	1.5	0.15	14	1.3655	22. 2	4	30.4334	5.4621
P-28	0.42	1.5	0.15	14	1.3655	22. 7	4	31.0110	5.4621
P-29	0.98	1.5	0.15	14	3.1487	23. 4	4	73.7277	12.5949
P-30	1.3	1.5	0.15	14	4.1769	26. 3	4	109.852	16.7076
P-31	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.458	2.2 5	6.35	32.5316	91.8114
P-32	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.458	24. 7	6.35	357.847	91.8114
P-33	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.458	11. 2	6.35	162.513	91.8114
P-34	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	15. 7	6.35	227.721 3	91.8114 7
P-35	1.25	1.53	0.15	14	4.01625	5.3 2	6.35	21.3865 3	25.5031 8
P-36	2.42	1.53	0.15	14	7.77546	19. 4	6.35	150.921 6	49.3741 7
P-37	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	2.2 5	10.3	32.5316	149.645
P-38	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	7.3 7	10.3	106.631	149.645
P-39	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	24. 7	10.3	357.847	149.645
P-40	0.98	1.53	0.15	14	3.14874	19. 5	10.3	61.6838 1	32.5894
P-41	1	1.53	0.15	14	3.213	10	10.3	32.13	33.2545
P-42	1	1.53	0.15	14	3.213	13	10.3	41.769	33.2545
P-43	1	1.53	0.15	14	3.213	14	10.3	44.982	33.254
P-44	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	2.2 5	14.8	32.5316	214.708
P-45	1	1.53	0.15	14	3.213	17. 5	17.5	56.2275	56.2275
P-46	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	24. 7	14.8	357.847	214.708
P-47	2.7	1.53	0.15	14	8.6751	3.1 5	19.3	27.3265	167.863

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

P-48	2.7	1.53	0.15	14	8.6751	23.8	19.3	206.90	167.863
P-49	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	2.25	23.8	32.5316	344.835
P-50	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	21.7	23.8	314.472	344.835
P-51	4	1.53	0.2	14	17.136	0	2	0	34.272
P-52	4	1.53	0.2	14	17.136	4.5	2	77.112	34.272
P-53	4	1.53	0.2	14	17.136	9	2	154.224	34.272
P-54	4	1.53	0.2	14	17.136	13.5	2	231.336	34.272
P-55	4	1.53	0.2	14	17.136	18	2	308.448	34.272
P-56	4	1.53	0.2	14	17.136	22.5	2	385.56	34.272
P-57	4	1.53	0.2	14	17.136	27	2	462.672	34.272
P-58	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	0	6.7	0	36.5960
P-59	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	0	9.5	0	51.8899
P-60	1.15	1.53	0.15	14	3.69495	4.5	6.42	16.6272	23.7400
P-61	0.98	1.53	0.15	14	3.14874	4.5	7.49	14.1693	23.5840
P-62	0.32	1.53	0.15	14	1.02816	4.5	10.1	4.62672	10.4769
P-63	1.15	1.53	0.15	14	3.69495	22.5	6.42	83.136	23.7400
P-64	0.98	1.53	0.15	14	3.14874	22.5	7.49	70.8466	23.5840
P-65	0.32	1.53	0.15	14	1.02816	22.5	10.1	23.1336	10.4769
P-66	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	0	11.2	0	61.1755
P-67	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	0	14	0	76.4694
P-68	0.32	1.53	0.15	14	1.02816	4.5	10.5	4.62672	10.8162
P-69	0.98	1.53	0.15	14	3.14874	4.5	11.1	14.1693	35.1399
P-70	1.15	1.53	0.15	14	3.69495	4.5	14.2	16.6272	52.7454
P-71	0.32	1.53	0.15	14	1.02816	22.5	10.7	23.1336	11.0115
P-72	0.98	1.53	0.15	14	3.14874	22.5	11.1	70.8466	35.1399
P-73	1.15	1.53	0.15	14	3.69495	22.5	14.2	83.1363	52.7454
P-74	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	27	11.2	147.476	61.1755
P-75	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	27	14	147.476	76.4694
P-76	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	0	15.7	0	85.7549
P-77	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	0	18.5	0	101.048
P-78	1.55	1.53	0.15	14	4.98015	4.5	15.5	22.4106	77.5110
P-79	0.98	1.53	0.15	14	3.14874	4.5	18	14.1693	56.6773
P-80	1.55	1.53	0.15	14	4.98015	22.5	15.6	112.053	77.81484

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

P-81	0.98	1.53	0.15	14	3.14874	22. 5	18	70.8466 5	56.6773 2
P-82	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	27	15.7	147.476 7	85.7549 7
P-83	1.7	1.53	0.15	14	5.4621	27	18.5	147.476 7	101.048 8
P-84	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	2.2 9	3.48	7.59505 0	11.5166 7
P-85	2.20	1.53	0.15	14	7.08466	3.3 0	2.27	23.4325 2	16.0218 9
P-86	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	7.8	3.48	25.8132 4	11.5166 7
P-87	2.25	1.53	0.15	14	7.22925	7.8 7	2.27	56.8941 9	16.4103 9
P-88	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	11. 2	3.48	37.1790 2	11.5166 7
P-89	2.25	1.53	0.15	14	7.22925	12. 4	2.27	89.5957 7	16.4103 9
P-90	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	15. 7	3.48	52.1890 8	11.5166 7
P-91	2.25	1.53	0.15	14	7.22925	14. 7	2.27	106.269 9	16.4103 9
P-92	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	20. 7	3.48	68.7360 3	11.5166 7
P-93	2.25	1.53	0.15	14	7.22925	21. 3	2.27	154.452 9	16.4103 9
P-94	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	24. 7	3.48	81.9735 9	11.5166 7
P-95	2.25	1.53	0.15	14	7.22925	23. 6	2.27	170.863 3	16.4103 9
P-96	1.8	1.53	0.1	14	3.8556	2.5	9.45	9.639	36.4354 2
P-97	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	3.9 8	8.55	13.1713 7	28.2952 8
P-98	1.8	1.53	0.1	14	3.8556	2.5	9.45	9.639	36.4354 2
P-99	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	3.9 8	8.55	13.1713 7	28.2952 8
P-100	1.8	1.53	0.1	14	3.8556	3.9 8	11.2	15.3452 8	43.3755
P-101	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	3.4 7	12.5	11.4835 8	41.3673 7
P-102	1.8	1.53	0.1	14	3.8556	25	9.45	96.39	36.4354 2
P-103	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	26. 4	8.55	87.6326 4	28.2952 8
P-104	1.8	1.53	0.1	14	3.8556	25	9.45	96.39	36.4354 2

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

P-105	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	26.4	8.55	87.63264	28.29528
P-106	1.8	1.53	0.1	14	3.8556	25	11.2	96.39	43.3755
P-107	1.03	1.53	0.15	14	3.30939	26.1	12.5	86.63983	41.36737
P-108	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	6.27	5.85	90.65479	84.58222
P-109	4.5	1.53	0.15	14	14.4585	19.6	5.85	284.1095	84.58222
P-110	1.18	1.53	0.15	14	3.79134	17.7	6.44	67.25837	24.41622
P-111	1.18	1.53	0.15	14	3.79134	17.7	9.63	67.22045	36.51060
				Σ	709.9069			9411.7465	5133.0861

APPINDEX-K : Ground Column

Column	d(m)	hi(m)	b(m)	γw	Weight	Xi	Yi	W*Xi	W*Yi
C-1	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	0	0	0
C-2	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	0	27.54	0
C-3	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	9	0	55.08	0
C-4	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	13.5	0	82.62	0
C-5	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	18	0	110.16	0
C-6	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	0	137.7	0
C-7	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	0	165.24	0
C-8	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	4	0	24.48
C-9	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	4	27.54	24.48
C-10	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	9	4	55.08	24.48
C-11	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	13.5	4	82.62	24.48
C-12	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	18	4	110.16	24.48
C-13	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	4	137.7	24.48
C-14	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	4	165.24	24.48
C-15	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	5.85	0	35.802
C-16	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	5.85	27.54	35.802
C-17	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	9	5.85	55.08	35.802
C-18	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	13.5	5.85	82.62	35.802
C-19	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	18	5.85	110.16	35.802
C-20	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	5.85	137.7	35.802
C-21	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	5.85	165.24	35.802
C-22	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	10.35	0	63.342

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

C-23	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	10.35	27.54	63.342
C-24	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	9	10.35	55.08	63.342
C-25	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	13.5	10.35	82.62	63.342
C-26	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	18	10.35	110.16	63.342
C-27	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	10.35	137.7	63.342
C-28	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	10.35	165.24	63.342
C-29	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	14.85	0	90.882
C-30	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	14.85	27.54	90.882
C-31	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	14.85	138.2508	90.882
C-32	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	14.85	27.54	90.882
C-33	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	19.35	137.7	118.422
C-34	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	19.35	137.7	118.422
C-35	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	23.85	0	145.962
C-36	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	23.85	27.54	145.962
C-37	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	23.85	137.7	145.962
C-38	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	23.85	165.24	145.962
				∑	232.56			3112.570	2049.588

APPINDEX-K₄ : **Table D11:Shear Wall**

			shear wall					
shear wall	h(m)	b(m)	d(m)	γ _w	Weight	X _i	Y _i	W*X _i
SWL-1	1.53	1.95	0.2	25	14.917	0.1	20.35	1.49175
SWL-2	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	0.9	19.35	12.393
SWL-3	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	0.9	20.9	12.393
SWL-4	1.53	0.69	0.2	25	5.3167	1.6	21.05	8.5068
SWL-5	1.53	0.69	0.2	25	5.3167	1.6	19.97	8.5068
SWR-1	1.53	1.95	0.2	25	14.917	27	20.35	402.7725
SWR-2	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	26.2	19.35	360.774
SWR-3	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	26.2	20.9	360.774
SWR-4	1.53	0.69	0.2	25	5.3167	25.3	21.05	134.513775
SWR-5	1.53	0.69	0.2	25	5.3167	25.3	19.97	134.513775
				∑	106.18			1436.6394

APPINDEX-K₅ : **Stair Case**

			stair case					
	LX(mm)	LY (mm)	Area(m ²)	Weight	X _i	Y _i	W*X _i	W*Y _i
FLIGHT-L1	2.24	4.5	10.08	25.9	24.1	21.83	624.8	565.3
FLIGHT-L2	2.24	4.5	10.08	25.9	24.1	23.165	624.8	599.8

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

FLIGHT-R1	2.24	4.5	10.08	25.9	1.96	23.165	50.8	599.8
FLIGHT-R2	2.24	4.5	10.08	25.9	1.96	21.83	50.8	565.3
LANDING-L1	0.84	4.5	3.78	5.9	22.9	22.55	136.1	133.9
LANDING-L2	1.42	4.5	6.39	10.0	26.4	22.55	265.7	226.4
LANDING-R2	0.84	4.5	3.78	5.9	0.42	22.55	2.5	133.9
LANDING-R3	1.42	4.5	6.39	10.0	3.97	22.55	39.9	226.4
			∑	135.5			1795.4	3050.9

APPINDEX-L : Calculation of Center of mass and weight of building for Typical floor

APPINDEX-L: Slab floor load

PANEL	Lx	ly	dead load	Weight	Xi	Yi	W*Xi	W*Yi
PANEL-1	4	4.5	6.223	112.014	2.25	2	252.0315	224.028
PANEL-2	4	4.5	6.223	112.014	6.75	2	756.0945	224.028
PANEL-3	4	4.5	6.223	112.014	11.25	2	1260.1575	224.028
PANEL-4	4	4.5	6.223	112.014	15.75	2	1764.2205	224.028
PANEL-5	4	4.5	6.223	112.014	20.25	2	2268.2835	224.028
PANEL-6	4	4.5	6.223	112.014	22.5	2	2520.315	224.028
PANEL-7	1.85	4.5	6.223	51.806475	2.25	4.925	116.564568	255.1468894
PANEL-8	1.85	4.5	6.223	51.806475	6.75	4.925	349.693706	255.1468894
PANEL-9	1.85	4.5	6.223	51.806475	11.25	4.925	582.822843	255.1468894
PANEL-10	1.85	4.5	6.223	51.806475	15.75	4.925	815.951981	255.1468894
PANEL-11	1.85	4.5	6.223	51.806475	20.25	4.925	1049.08111	255.1468894
PANEL-12	1.85	4.5	6.223	51.806475	22.5	4.925	1165.64568	255.1468894
PANEL-13	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	2.25	8.1	283.535437	1020.727575
PANEL-14	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	6.75	8.1	850.606312	1020.727575
PANEL-15	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	11.25	8.1	1417.67718	1020.727575
PANEL-16	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	15.75	8.1	1984.74806	1020.727575
PANEL-17	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	20.25	8.1	2551.81893	1020.727575
PANEL-18	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	22.5	8.1	2835.35437	1020.727575
PANEL-19	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	2.25	12.6	283.535437	1587.79845
PANEL-20	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	2.25	17.1	283.535437	2154.869325
PANEL-21	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	24.75	12.6	3118.88981	1587.79845
PANEL-22	4.5	4.5	6.223	126.01575	24.75	17.1	3118.88981	2154.869325
CANT-1	2.08	4.5	7.82	73.1952	5.54	12.6	405.501408	922.25952
CANT-2	2.08	4.5	7.82	73.1952	5.54	17.1	405.501408	1251.63792
CANT-3	2.08	4.5	7.82	73.1952	5.54	21.6	405.501408	1581.01632
CANT-4	2.08	4.5	7.82	73.1952	21.46	12.6	1570.76899	922.25952

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

CANT-5	2.08	4.5	7.82	73.1952	21.46	17.1	1570.76899	1251.63792
CANT-6	2.08	4.5	7.82	73.1952	21.46	21.6	1570.76899	1581.01632
CANT-7	2.25	2.42	7.82	42.5799	7.79	12.6	331.697421	536.50674
CANT-8	2.25	4.5	7.82	79.1775	11.25	12.6	890.746875	997.6365
CANT-9	2.25	4.5	7.82	79.1775	15.75	12.6	1247.04562	997.6365
CANT-10	2.25	2.42	7.82	42.5799	19.21	12.6	817.959879	536.50674
			∑	2925.7663			38845.7142	27062.86434

APPINDEX-L₂ : floor beam

beam-ID	L(m)	b(m)	D(m)	Γw	Weight	Xi	Yi	W*Xi	W*Yi
B-1	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	2.25	0	45.5625	0
B-2	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	6.75	0	136.6875	0
B-3	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	11.25	0	227.8125	0
B-4	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	15.75	0	318.9375	0
B-5	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	20.25	0	410.0625	0
B-6	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	22.5	0	455.625	0
B-7	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	2.25	4	45.5625	81
B-8	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	6.75	4	136.6875	81
B-9	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	11.25	4	227.8125	81
B-10	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	15.75	4	318.9375	81
B-11	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	20.25	4	410.0625	81
B-12	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	22.5	4	455.625	81
B-13	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	2.25	5.85	45.5625	118.4625
B-14	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	6.75	5.85	136.6875	118.4625
B-15	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	11.25	5.85	227.8125	118.4625
B-16	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	15.75	5.85	318.9375	118.4625
B-17	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	20.25	5.85	410.0625	118.4625
B-18	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	22.5	5.85	455.625	118.4625
B-19	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	2.25	10.35	45.5625	209.5875
B-20	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	6.75	10.35	136.6875	209.5875
B-21	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	11.25	10.35	227.8125	209.5875
B-22	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	15.75	10.35	318.9375	209.5875
B-23	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	20.25	10.35	410.0625	209.5875
B-24	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	22.5	10.35	455.625	209.5875
B-25	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	2.25	14.85	45.5625	300.7125
B-26	2.08	0.4	0.45	25	9.36	5.54	14.85	51.8544	138.996
B-27	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	24.75	14.85	501.1875	300.7125
B-28	2.08	0.4	0.45	25	9.36	21.46	14.85	200.8656	138.996
B-29	4.5	0.4	0.45	0	0	2.25	19.35	0	0
B-30	2.08	0.4	0.45	25	9.36	5.54	19.35	51.8544	181.116

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

B-31	2.08	0.4	0.45	25	9.36	21.46	19.35	200.8656	181.116
B-32	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	24.75	19.35	501.1875	391.8375
B-33	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	2.25	23.85	45.5625	482.9625
B-34	2.08	0.4	0.45	25	9.36	5.54	23.85	51.8544	223.236
B-35	2.08	0.4	0.45	25	9.36	21.46	23.85	200.8656	223.236
B-36	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	24.75	23.85	501.1875	482.9625
B-37	4	0.4	0.45	25	18	0	2	0	36
B-38	1.85	0.4	0.45	25	8.325	0	4.925	0	41.00062
B-39	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	0	8.07	0	163.4175
B-40	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	0	12.57	0	254.5425
B-41	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	0	17.07	0	345.6675
B-42	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	0	19.32	0	391.23
B-43	4	0.4	0.45	25	18	4.5	2	81	36
B-44	1.85	0.4	0.45	25	8.325	4.5	4.925	37.4625	41.00062
B-45	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	4.5	8.07	91.125	163.4175
B-46	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	4.5	12.57	91.125	254.5425
B-47	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	4.5	17.07	91.125	345.6675
B-48	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	4.5	19.32	91.125	391.23
B-49	4	0.4	0.45	25	18	9	2	162	36
B-50	1.85	0.4	0.45	25	8.325	9	4.925	74.925	41.00062
B-51	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	9	8.07	182.25	163.4175
B-52	4	0.4	0.45	25	18	13.5	2	243	36
B-53	1.85	0.4	0.45	25	8.325	13.5	4.925	112.3875	41.00062
B-54	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	13.5	8.07	273.375	163.4175
B-55	4	0.4	0.45	25	18	18	2	324	36
B-56	1.85	0.4	0.45	25	8.325	18	4.925	149.85	41.00062
B-57	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	18	8.07	364.5	163.4175
B-58	4	0.4	0.45	25	18	22.5	2	405	36
B-59	1.85	0.4	0.45	25	8.325	22.5	4.925	187.3125	41.00062
B-60	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	22.5	8.07	455.625	163.4175
B-61	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	22.5	12.57	455.625	254.5425
B-62	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	22.5	17.07	455.625	345.6675
B-63	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	22.5	19.32	455.625	391.23
B-64	4	0.4	0.45	25	18	27	2	486	36
B-65	1.85	0.4	0.45	25	8.325	27	4.925	224.775	41.00062
B-66	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	27	8.07	546.75	163.4175
B-67	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	27	12.57	546.75	254.5425
B-68	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	27	17.07	546.75	345.6675
B-69	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	27	19.32	546.75	391.23
B-70	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	27	19.32	546.75	391.23
B-71	4.5	0.4	0.45	25	20.25	27	19.32	546.75	391.23
				∑	1252.935			17506.935	11931.33

APPINDEX-L₃ : Partition wall

PARTITION-ID	L(m)	hi(m)	D(m)	Γ_w	Weight(KN)	X_i	Y_i	$W \cdot X_i$	$W \cdot Y_i$
P-1	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	0.85	0	12.38076	0
P-2	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	3.65	0	53.16444	0
P-3	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	5.35	0	77.92596	0
P-4	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	8.15	0	118.70964	0
P-5	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	9.85	0	143.47116	0
P-6	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	12.65	0	184.25484	0
P-7	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	14.35	0	209.01636	0
P-8	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	17.15	0	249.80004	0
P-9	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	18.35	0	267.27876	0
P-10	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	21.65	0	315.34524	0
P-11	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	23.35	0	340.10676	0
P-12	1.7	3.06	0.2	14	14.5656	26.15	0	380.89044	0
P-13	1.3	3.06	0.15	14	8.3538	0.55	4	4.59459	33.4152
P-14	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	2.49	4	15.680725	25.18992
P-15	0.42	3.06	0.15	14	2.73105	3.99	4	10.896889	10.9242
P-16	0.42	3.06	0.15	14	2.73105	4.712	4	12.868707	10.9242
P-17	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	5.79	4	36.462409	25.18992
P-18	1.4	3.06	0.15	14	8.9964	8.816	4	79.312262	35.9856
P-19	1.4	3.06	0.15	14	8.9964	9.7	4	87.26508	35.9856
P-20	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	10.89	4	68.579557	25.18992
P-21	0.42	3.06	0.15	14	2.73105	13.3	4	36.322965	10.9242
P-22	0.42	3.06	0.15	14	2.73105	13.7	4	37.415385	10.9242
P-23	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	15.34	4	96.603343	25.18992
P-24	1.4	3.06	0.15	14	8.9964	17.3	4	155.63772	35.9856
P-25	1.4	3.06	0.15	14	8.9964	18.7	4	168.23268	35.9856
P-26	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	20.79	4	130.92460	25.18992
P-27	0.42	3.06	0.15	14	2.73105	22.287	4	60.866911	10.9242
P-28	0.42	3.06	0.15	14	2.73105	22.71	4	62.022145	10.9242
P-29	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	23.415	4	147.45549	25.18992
P-30	1.3	3.06	0.15	14	8.3538	26.3	4	219.70494	33.4152
P-31	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	2.25	6.35	65.06325	183.62295
P-32	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	24.75	6.35	715.69575	183.62295
P-33	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	11.24	6.35	325.02708	183.62295
P-34	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	15.75	6.35	455.44275	183.62295
P-35	1.25	3.06	0.15	14	8.0325	5.325	6.35	42.773062	51.006375
P-36	2.42	3.06	0.15	14	15.55092	19.41	6.35	301.84335	98.748342
P-37	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	2.25	10.35	65.06325	299.29095

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

P-38	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	7.375	10.35	213.26287	299.29095
P-39	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	24.75	10.35	715.69575	299.29095
P-40	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	19.59	10.35	123.36763	65.178918
P-41	1	3.06	0.15	14	6.426	10	10.35	64.26	66.5091
P-42	1	3.06	0.15	14	6.426	13	10.35	83.538	66.5091
P-43	1	3.06	0.15	14	6.426	14	10.35	89.964	66.5091
P-44	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	2.25	14.85	65.06325	429.41745
P-45	1	3.06	0.15	14	6.426	17.5	17.5	112.455	112.455
P-46	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	24.75	14.85	715.69575	429.41745
P-47	2.7	3.06	0.15	14	17.3502	3.15	19.35	54.65313	335.72637
P-48	2.7	3.06	0.15	14	17.3502	23.85	19.35	413.80227	335.72637
P-49	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	2.25	23.85	65.06325	689.67045
P-50	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	21.75	23.85	628.94475	689.67045
P-51	4	3.06	0.2	14	34.272	0	2	0	68.544
P-52	4	3.06	0.2	14	34.272	4.5	2	154.224	68.544
P-53	4	3.06	0.2	14	34.272	9	2	308.448	68.544
P-54	4	3.06	0.2	14	34.272	13.5	2	462.672	68.544
P-55	4	3.06	0.2	14	34.272	18	2	616.896	68.544
P-56	4	3.06	0.2	14	34.272	22.5	2	771.12	68.544
P-57	4	3.06	0.2	14	34.272	27	2	925.344	68.544
P-58	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	0	6.7	0	73.19214
P-59	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	0	9.5	0	103.7799
P-60	1.15	3.06	0.15	14	7.3899	4.5	6.425	33.25455	47.480107
P-61	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	4.5	7.49	28.33866	47.168125
P-62	0.32	3.06	0.15	14	2.05632	4.5	10.19	9.25344	20.953900
P-63	1.15	3.06	0.15	14	7.3899	22.5	6.425	166.27275	47.480107
P-64	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	22.5	7.49	141.6933	47.168125
P-65	0.32	3.06	0.15	14	2.05632	22.5	10.19	46.2672	20.953900
P-66	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	0	11.2	0	122.35104
P-67	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	0	14	0	152.9388
P-68	0.32	3.06	0.15	14	2.05632	4.5	10.52	9.25344	21.632486
P-69	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	4.5	11.16	28.33866	70.279876
P-70	1.15	3.06	0.15	14	7.3899	4.5	14.27	33.25455	105.49082
P-71	0.32	3.06	0.15	14	2.05632	22.5	10.71	46.2672	22.023187
P-72	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	22.5	11.16	141.6933	70.279876
P-73	1.15	3.06	0.15	14	7.3899	22.5	14.27	166.27275	105.49082
P-74	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	27	11.2	294.9534	122.35104
P-75	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	27	14	294.9534	152.9388
P-76	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	0	15.7	0	171.50994
P-77	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	0	18.5	0	202.0977
P-78	1.55	3.06	0.15	14	9.9603	4.5	15.56	44.82135	155.02210
P-79	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	4.5	18	28.33866	113.35464
P-80	1.55	3.06	0.15	14	9.9603	22.5	15.6	224.10675	155.62968
P-81	0.98	3.06	0.15	14	6.29748	22.5	18	141.6933	113.35464

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

P-82	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	27	15.7	294.9534	171.50994
P-83	1.7	3.06	0.15	14	10.9242	27	18.5	294.9534	202.0977
P-84	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	2.295	3.48	15.1901001	23.033354
P-85	2.20	3.06	0.15	14	14.16933	3.307	2.27	46.8650589	32.164379
P-86	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	7.8	3.48	51.626484	23.033354
P-87	2.25	3.06	0.15	14	14.4585	7.87	2.27	113.788395	32.820795
P-88	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	11.22	3.48	74.2958055	23.033354
P-89	2.25	3.06	0.15	14	14.4585	12.43	2.27	179.719155	32.820795
P-90	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	15.77	3.48	104.378160	23.033354
P-91	2.25	3.06	0.15	14	14.4585	14.7	2.27	212.53995	32.820795
P-92	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	20.77	3.48	137.472060	23.033354
P-93	2.25	3.06	0.15	14	14.4585	21.36	2.27	308.905852	32.820795
P-94	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	24.77	3.48	163.947180	23.033354
P-95	2.25	3.06	0.15	14	14.4585	23.63	2.27	341.726647	32.820795
P-96	1.8	3.06	0.1	14	7.7112	2.5	9.45	19.278	72.87084
P-97	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	3.98	8.55	26.3427444	56.590569
P-98	1.8	3.06	0.1	14	7.7112	2.5	9.45	19.278	72.87084
P-99	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	3.98	8.55	26.3427444	56.590569
P-100	1.8	3.06	0.1	14	7.7112	3.98	11.25	30.690576	86.751
P-101	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	3.47	12.5	22.9671666	82.73475
P-102	1.8	3.06	0.1	14	7.7112	25	9.45	192.78	72.87084
P-103	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	26.48	8.55	175.265294	56.590569
P-104	1.8	3.06	0.1	14	7.7112	25	9.45	192.78	72.87084
P-105	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	26.48	8.55	175.265294	56.590569
P-106	1.8	3.06	0.1	14	7.7112	25	11.25	192.78	86.751
P-107	1.03	3.06	0.15	14	6.61878	26.18	12.5	173.279660	82.73475
P-108	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	6.27	5.85	181.30959	169.16445
P-109	4.5	3.06	0.15	14	28.917	19.65	5.85	568.21905	169.16445
P-110	1.18	3.06	0.15	14	7.58268	17.74	6.44	134.516743	48.832459
P-111	1.18	3.06	0.15	14	7.58268	17.73	9.63	134.440916	73.021208
				∑	1419.81399			18823.49306	10266.172

APPINDEX-L4 : Column

column	d(m)		b(m)	γ_w	Weight	X_i	Y_i	$W \cdot X_i$	$W \cdot Y_i$
C-1	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	0	0	0	0
C-2	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	4.5	0	55.08	0
C-3	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	9	0	110.16	0
C-4	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	13.5	0	165.24	0
C-5	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	18	0	220.32	0
C-6	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	22.5	0	275.4	0
C-7	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	27	0	330.48	0

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

C-8	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	0	4	0	48.96
C-9	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	4.5	4	55.08	48.96
C-10	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	9	4	110.16	48.96
C-11	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	13.5	4	165.24	48.96
C-12	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	18	4	220.32	48.96
C-13	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	22.5	4	275.4	48.96
C-14	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	27	4	330.48	48.96
C-15	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	0	5.85	0	71.604
C-16	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	4.5	5.85	55.08	71.604
C-17	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	9	5.85	110.16	71.604
C-18	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	13.5	5.85	165.24	71.604
C-19	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	18	5.85	220.32	71.604
C-20	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	22.5	5.85	275.4	71.604
C-21	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	27	5.85	330.48	71.604
C-22	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	0	10.35	0	126.68
C-23	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	4.5	10.35	55.08	126.68
C-24	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	9	10.35	110.16	126.68
C-25	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	13.5	10.35	165.24	126.68
C-26	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	18	10.35	220.32	126.68
C-27	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	22.5	10.35	275.4	126.68
C-28	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	27	10.35	330.48	126.68
C-29	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	0	14.85	0	181.76
C-30	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	4.5	14.85	55.08	181.76
C-31	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	22.59	14.85	276.5016	181.76
C-32	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	4.5	14.85	55.08	181.76
C-33	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	22.5	19.35	275.4	236.84
C-34	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	22.5	19.35	275.4	236.84
C-35	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	0	23.85	0	291.92
C-36	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	4.5	23.85	55.08	291.92
C-37	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	22.5	23.85	275.4	291.92
C-38	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	27	23.85	330.48	291.92
C'-1	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	6.78	12.6	82.9872	154.22
C'-2	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	9	12.6	110.16	154.22
C'-3	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	13.5	12.6	165.24	154.22
C'-4	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	18	12.6	220.32	154.22
C'-5	0.4	3.06	0.4	25	12.24	20.42	12.6	249.9408	154.22
				∑	526.32			7053.7896	4870.2

			shear wall						
shear wall	h(m)	b(m)	d(m)	Γ_w	Weight	X_i	Y_i	$W \cdot X_i$	$W \cdot Y_i$

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

SWL-1	1.53	1.95	0.2	25	14.9175	0.1	20.35	1.49175	303.57112
SWL-2	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	0.9	19.35	12.393	266.4495
SWL-3	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	0.9	20.9	12.393	287.793
SWL-4	1.53	0.695	0.2	25	5.31675	1.6	21.05	8.5068	111.91758
SWL-5	1.53	0.695	0.2	25	5.31675	1.6	19.97	8.5068	106.17549
SWR-1	1.53	1.95	0.2	25	14.9175	27	20.35	402.7725	303.5711
SWR-2	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	26.2	19.35	360.774	266.4495
SWR-3	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	26.2	20.9	360.774	287.793
SWR-4	1.53	0.695	0.2	25	5.31675	25.3	21.05	134.51377	111.91758
SWR-5	1.53	0.695	0.2	25	5.31675	25.3	19.97	134.5137	106.17549
				Σ	106.182			1436.639	2151.832

APPINDEX-M₁ : Shear wall

APPINDEX-N : Calculation of Center of mass and weight of building for ROOF

APPINDEX-N₁:

	Column								
column	d(m)	h(m)	b(m)	γw	Weigh	Xi	Yi	W*Xi	W*Yi
C-1	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	0	0	0
C-2	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	0	27.54	0
C-3	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	9	0	55.08	0
C-4	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	13.5	0	82.62	0
C-5	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	18	0	110.16	0
C-6	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	0	137.7	0
C-7	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	0	165.24	0
C-8	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	4	0	24.48
C-9	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	4		24.48
C-10	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	9	4	55.08	24.48
C-11	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	13.5	4	82.62	24.48
C-12	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	18	4	110.16	24.48
C-13	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	4	137.7	24.48
C-14	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	4	165.24	24.48
C-15	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	5.85	0	35.802
C-16	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	5.85	27.54	35.802
C-17	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	9	5.85	55.08	35.802
C-18	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	13.5	5.85	82.62	35.802
C-19	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	18	5.85	110.16	35.802
C-20	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	5.85	137.7	35.802
C-21	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	5.85	165.24	35.802
C-22	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	10.35	0	63.342
C-23	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	10.35	27.54	63.342

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

C-24	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	9	10.35	55.08	63.342
C-25	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	13.5	10.35	82.62	63.342
C-26	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	18	10.35	110.16	63.342
C-27	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	10.35	137.7	63.342
C-28	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	10.35	165.24	63.342
C-29	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	14.85	0	90.882
C-30	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	14.85	27.54	90.882
C-31	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	14.85	138.25 0	90.882
C-32	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	14.85	27.54	90.882
C-33	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	19.35	137.7	118.422
C-34	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	19.35	137.7	118.422
C-35	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	0	23.85	0	145.962
C-36	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	4.5	23.85	27.54	145.962
C-37	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	22.5	23.85	137.7	145.962
C-38	0.4	1.53	0.4	25	6.12	27	23.85	165.24	145.962
				SUM	232.5			3085.0 3	2049.58 8

APPINDEX-N₂:TOP TIE BEAM

		TIE BEAM							
beam-ID	L(m)	b(m)	D(m)	γ_w	Weight	X_i	Y_i	$W \cdot X_i$	$W \cdot Y_i$
B-1	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	2.25	0	35.4375	0
B-2	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	6.75	0	106.312	0
B-3	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	11.25	0	177.187	0
B-4	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	15.75	0	248.062	0
B-5	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	20.25	0	318.937	0
B-6	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	22.5	0	354.375	0
B-7	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	2.25	4	35.4375	63
B-8	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	6.75	4	106.312	63
B-9	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	11.25	4	177.187	63
B-10	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	15.75	4	248.062	63
B-11	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	20.25	4	318.937	63
B-12	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	22.5	4	354.375	63
B-13	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	2.25	5.85	35.4375	92.1375
B-14	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	6.75	5.85	106.312	92.1375
B-15	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	11.2	5.85	177.187	92.1375
B-16	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	15.7	5.85	248.062	92.1375
B-17	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	20.2	5.85	318.937	92.1375

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

B-18	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	22.5	5.85	354.375	92.1375
B-19	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	2.25	10.35	35.4375	163.0125
B-20	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	6.75	10.35	106.312	163.0125
B-21	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	11.2	10.35	177.187	163.0125
B-22	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	15.7	10.35	248.062	163.0125
B-23	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	20.2	10.35	318.937	163.0125
B-24	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	22.5	10.35	354.375	163.0125
B-25	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	2.25	14.85	35.4375	233.8875
B-26	2.08	0.4	0.35	25	7.28	5.54	14.85	40.3312	108.108
B-27	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	24.7	14.85	389.812	233.8875
B-28	2.08	0.4	0.35	25	7.28	21.4	14.85	156.228	108.108
B-29	4.5	0.4	0.35	0	0	2.25	19.35	0	0
B-30	2.08	0.4	0.35	25	7.28	5.54	19.35	40.3312	140.868
B-31	2.08	0.4	0.35	25	7.28	21.4	19.35	156.228	140.868
B-32	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	24.7	19.35	389.812	304.7625
B-33	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	2.25	23.85	35.4375	375.6375
B-34	2.08	0.4	0.35	25	7.28	5.54	23.85	40.3312	173.628
B-35	2.08	0.4	0.35	25	7.28	21.4	23.85	156.228	173.628
B-36	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	24.7	23.85	389.812	375.6375
B-37	4	0.4	0.35	25	14	0	2	0	28
B-38	1.85	0.4	0.35	25	6.475	0	4.925	0	31.88937
B-39	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	0	8.07	0	127.1025
B-40	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	0	12.57	0	197.9775
B-41	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	0	17.07	0	268.8525
B-42	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	0	19.32	0	304.29
B-43	4	0.4	0.35	25	14	4.5	2	63	28
B-44	1.85	0.4	0.35	25	6.475	4.5	4.925	29.1375	31.88937
B-45	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	4.5	8.07	70.875	127.1025
B-46	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	4.5	12.57	70.875	197.9775
B-47	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	4.5	17.07	70.875	268.8525
B-48	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	4.5	19.32	70.875	304.29
B-49	4	0.4	0.35	25	14	9	2	126	28
B-50	1.85	0.4	0.35	25	6.475	9	4.925	58.275	31.88937
B-51	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	9	8.07	141.75	127.1025
B-52	4	0.4	0.35	25	14	13.5	2	189	28
B-53	1.85	0.4	0.35	25	6.475	13.5	4.925	87.4125	31.88937
B-54	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	13.5	8.07	212.625	127.1025
B-55	4	0.4	0.35	25	14	18	2	252	28
B-56	1.85	0.4	0.35	25	6.475	18	4.925	116.55	31.88937
B-57	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	18	8.07	283.5	127.1025
B-58	4	0.4	0.35	25	14	22.5	2	315	28
B-59	1.85	0.4	0.35	25	6.475	22.5	4.925	145.687	31.88937

Structural design of a G+4 residential building at Addis Ababa using the revised
Ethiopian building code of standards (ES EN 2004:2015)

B-60	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	22.5	8.07	354.375	127.1025
B-61	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	22.5	12.57	354.375	197.9775
B-62	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	22.5	17.07	354.375	268.8525
B-63	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	22.5	19.32	354.375	304.29
B-64	4	0.4	0.35	25	14	27	2	378	28
B-65	1.85	0.4	0.35	25	6.475	27	4.925	174.825	31.88937
B-66	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	27	8.07	425.25	127.1025
B-67	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	27	12.57	425.25	197.9775
B-68	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	27	17.07	425.25	268.8525
B-69	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	27	19.32	425.25	304.29
B-70	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	27	19.32	425.25	304.29
B-71	4.5	0.4	0.35	25	15.75	27	19.32	425.25	304.29
				sum	974.50			13616.5	9279.923

APPINDEX-N₃: Roof tanker slab

ROOF FLAT SLAB								
PANEL	lx	Ly	dead load	Weight	Xi	Yi	W*Xi	W*Yi
PANEL-1'	4.5	4.5	17.3	350.325	2.25	21.6	788.23125	7567.02
PANEL-2'	4.7	4.8	17.3	390.28	24.75	22.6	9659.62	8820.508
				740.61			10448	16387.52

APPINDEX-N₄: Shear wall

shear wall	h(m)	b(m)	d(m)	γ_w	Weight	Xi	Yi	W*Xi	W*Yi
SWL-1	1.53	1.95	0.2	25	14.9175	0.1	20.35	1.49175	303.571125
SWL-2	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	0.9	19.35	12.393	266.4495
SWL-3	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	0.9	20.9	12.393	287.793
SWL-4	1.53	0.695	0.2	25	5.31675	1.6	21.05	8.5068	111.9175875
SWL-5	1.53	0.695	0.2	25	5.31675	1.6	19.97	8.5068	106.1754975
SWR-1	1.53	1.95	0.2	25	14.9175	27	20.35	402.7725	303.571125
SWR-2	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	26.2	19.35	360.774	266.4495
SWR-3	1.53	1.8	0.2	25	13.77	26.2	20.9	360.774	287.793
SWR-4	1.53	0.695	0.2	25	5.31675	25.3	21.05	134.513775	111.9175875
SWR-5	1.53	0.695	0.2	25	5.31675	25.3	19.97	134.513775	106.1754975
					106.182			1436.6394	2151.81342

APPINDEIX-L: ROOF COMPNENT

Area	wind load (KN/M2)								
Column1	Chumped (KN/m2)	Purlin (KN)	TRUSS (KN)	Total (KN/M2)	WEIGHT (KN)	X8	X9	W*Xi	
area-1	0.218	0.53	0.88	0.8429	32.59	4.8	3.58	156.5	116.7
area-2	0.218	0.585	1.46	0.8452	55.88	13.41	5.125	749.4	286.4
area-3	0.218	0.64	1.46	0.8452	55.93	16.51	5.125	923.6	286.7
area-4	0.218	0.695	2.97	0.8452	113.20	4.5	10.8	509.4	1222.6
area-5	0.218	0.75	0.88	0.8452	32.90	22.02	3.417	724.5	112.4
area-6	0.218	0.805	2.97	0.8452	113.31	23.22	14.75	2631.1	1671.4
area-7	0.218	0.86	0.47	0.8452	18.44	2.25	21.75	41.49	401.1
area-8	0.218	0.915	0.47	0.8452	9.21	20.745	21.75	190.9	200.2
area-9	0.218	0.97	0.47	0.8452	20.50	24.12	21.75	494.5	445.9
area-10	0.218	1.026	0.47	0.8452	9.40	5.625	21.75	52.89	204.5
area-11	0.218	1.081	0.88	0.8452	33.2	24.42	6.83	811.58	226.9
area-12	0.218	1.139	0.88	0.8452	33.2	2.4	6.82	79.9	227.1
					527.91			7365.8	5401.97

APPENDIX-M: Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination for story 5-1

Story	load combination	Drift,x	Drift,y	q	p(KN)	Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ_x	θ_y
Story-5	Dead	0.00E+00	2.90E-05	1.5	12810.7865				
Story-5	Live	0.00E+00	1.50E-05	1.5	1594.419				
Story-5	EQ:X1	0.000239	0.00E+00	1.5	0	-130			
Story-5	EQ:X2	0.000239	0.00E+00	1.5	0	-130			
Story-5	EQ:Y1	0.00E+00	0.000214	1.5	0		-130		
Story-5	EQ:Y2	0.00E+00	0.000214	1.5	0		-130		
Story-5	IMP in X	3.50E-05	0	1.5	0	-15.0666			
Story-5	IMP in Y	0.00E+00	3.30E-05	1.5	0		-15.0666		
Story-5	Comb1	0.00E+00	4.40E-05	1.5	14405.2055				
Story-5	Comb2	4.20E-05	6.10E-05	1.5	19686.1903	15.0666		0.082317	
Story-5	Comb3	4.20E-05	6.10E-05	1.5	19686.1903	-15.0666		0.082317	
Story-5	Comb4	0.00E+00	3.30E-05	1.5	19686.1903		-15.0666	0.064677	
Story-5	Comb5	0.00E+00	9.20E-05	1.5	19686.1903		156	0.017415	
Story-5	Comb6	0.00E+00	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122				
Story-5	Comb7	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb8	0.00021	0.000107	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.05469
Story-5	Comb9	0.000278	0.000109	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.055712
Story-5	Comb10	0.000246	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.051616
Story-5	Comb11	0.00028	0.00E+00	1.5	16654.0224	-145.0666			0

Story-5	Comb12	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867
Story-5	Comb13	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867
Story-5	Comb14	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb15	0.000278	0.000109	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.055712
Story-5	Comb16	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867
Story-5	Comb17	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb18	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867
Story-5	Comb19	0.00021	0.000107	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.05469
Story-5	Comb20	0.000278	0.000109	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.055712
Story-5	Comb21	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb22	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867
Story-5	Comb23	0.000278	0.000109	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.055712
Story-5	Comb24	0.00021	0.000107	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.05469
Story-5	Comb25	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	
Story-5	Comb26	5.90E-05	0.000181	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04914	
Story-5	Comb27	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb28	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb29	5.40E-05	0.000186	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.044976	
Story-5	Comb30	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	
Story-5	Comb31	5.40E-05	0.000186	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.044976	
Story-5	Comb32	5.90E-05	0.000181	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04914	
Story-5	Comb33	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb34	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	
Story-5	Comb35	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	
Story-5	Comb36	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb37	5.40E-05	0.000186	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.044976	
Story-5	Comb38	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	

Story-5	Comb39	5.90E-05	0.000181	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04914	
Story-5	Comb40	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb41	5.40E-05	0.000186	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.044976	
Story-5	Comb7-1	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb8-1	0.000246	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.051616
Story-5	Comb9-1	0.000242	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb10-1	0.000246	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.051616
Story-5	Comb11-1	0.000247	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.023227
Story-5	Comb12-1	0.000243	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.052471
Story-5	Comb13-1	0.000243	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb14-1	0.000247	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.023227
Story-5	Comb15-1	0.000242	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.012462
Story-5	Comb16-1	0.000243	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb17-1	0.000247	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.023227
Story-5	Comb18-1	0.000243	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb19-1	0.000246	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.051616
Story-5	Comb20-1	0.000242	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb21-1	0.000247	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.023227
Story-5	Comb22-1	0.000243	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb23-1	0.000242	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.012084
Story-5	Comb24-1	0.000246	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.078162
Story-5	Comb25-1	9.50E-05	0.000147	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	
Story-5	Comb26-1	9.10E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.046512	
Story-5	Comb27-1	8.60E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Comb28-1	8.60E-05	0.00022	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Comb29-1	8.90E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.04549	
Story-5	Comb30-1	9.50E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	

Story-5	Comb31-1	8.90E-05	0.00022	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.04549	
Story-5	Comb32-1	9.10E-05	0.000147	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.046512	
Story-5	Comb33-1	8.60E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Comb34-1	9.50E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	
Story-5	Comb35-1	9.50E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	
Story-5	Comb36-1	8.60E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Comb37-1	8.90E-05	0.00022	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.04549	
Story-5	Comb38-1	9.50E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	
Story-5	Comb39-1	9.10E-05	0.000147	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.046512	
Story-5	Comb40-1	8.60E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Envlope-ALL Max	0.00028	0.00022	1.5	16654.0224		154.0666	0.0454	
Story-5	Envlope-ALL Min	0.000122	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666	-145.0666	0.016764	0.019237
Story-5							max	0.082317	0.078162

Story	load combination	Drift,y	Drift,x	q	p(KN)	Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ_y	θ_x
Story-4	Dead	2.40E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	21468.01				
Story-4	Live	1.30E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	3015.909				
Story-4	EQ:X1	0.00E+00	0.000348	1.5	0	-511			
Story-4	EQ:X2	0	0.000348	1.5	0	-511			
Story-4	EQ:Y1	0.000279	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-511		
Story-4	EQ:Y2	0.000279	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-511		
Story-4	IMP in X	0	5.20E-05	1.5	0	-65.589			
Story-4	IMP in Y	4.40E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-65.589		
Story-4	Comb1	3.70E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	24483.91				
Story-4	Comb2	5.70E-05	5.10E-05	1.5	33505.67	65.589			0.039079
Story-4	Comb3	5.90E-05	5.20E-05	1.5	33505.67	-65.589			0.039846

Story-4	Comb4	1.20E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	33505.67		-65.589	0.009195	
Story-4	Comb5	9.60E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	33505.67		65.589	0.073561	
Story-4	Comb6	2.80E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	22372.78				
Story-4	Comb7	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874
Story-4	Comb8	0.000153	0.000303	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.022829
Story-4	Comb9	0.000166	0.000407	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.023689
Story-4	Comb10	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb11	9.20E-05	0.000393	1.5	27908.41	-576.589			0.028533
Story-4	Comb12	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb13	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb14	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874
Story-4	Comb15	0.000166	0.000407	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.023689
Story-4	Comb16	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb17	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874
Story-4	Comb18	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb19	0.000153	0.000303	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.022829
Story-4	Comb20	0.000166	0.000407	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.023689
Story-4	Comb21	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874
Story-4	Comb22	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb23	0.000166	0.000407	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.023689
Story-4	Comb24	0.000153	0.000303	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.022829
Story-4	Comb25	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	
Story-4	Comb26	0.000244	6.30E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.016024	
Story-4	Comb27	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb28	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb29	0.000259	7.60E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017009	
Story-4	Comb30	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	

Story-4	Comb31	0.000259	7.60E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017009	
Story-4	Comb32	0.000244	6.30E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.016024	
Story-4	Comb33	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb34	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	
Story-4	Comb35	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	
Story-4	Comb36	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb37	0.000259	7.60E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017009	
Story-4	Comb38	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	
Story-4	Comb39	0.000244	6.30E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.016024	
Story-4	Comb40	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb41	0.000259	7.60E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017009	
Story-4	Comb7-1	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874
Story-4	Comb8-1	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb9-1	0.000116	0.000352	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023117
Story-4	Comb10-1	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb11-1	0.000127	0.000339	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022263
Story-4	Comb12-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526
Story-4	Comb13-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526
Story-4	Comb14-1	0.000127	0.000339	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022263
Story-4	Comb15-1	0.000116	0.000352	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023117
Story-4	Comb16-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526
Story-4	Comb17-1	0.000127	0.000339	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022263
Story-4	Comb18-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526
Story-4	Comb19-1	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb20-1	0.000116	0.000352	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023117
Story-4	Comb21-1	0.000127	0.000339	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022263
Story-4	Comb22-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526

Story-4	Comb23-1	0.000116	0.000352	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023117
Story-4	Comb24-1	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb25-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb26-1	0.000193	0.000101	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.014541	
Story-4	Comb27-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Comb28-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Comb29-1	0.00031	0.00013	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.018043	
Story-4	Comb30-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb31-1	0.00031	0.00013	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.018043	
Story-4	Comb32-1	0.000193	0.000101	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.014541	
Story-4	Comb33-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Comb34-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb35-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb36-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Comb37-1	0.00031	0.00013	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.018043	
Story-4	Comb38-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb39-1	0.000193	0.000101	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.014541	
Story-4	Comb40-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Envelope-ALL Max	0.00031	0.000407	1.5	27908.41		218.889	0.059288	
Story-4	Envelope-ALL Min	0.000204	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.011873	
Story-4							max	0.073561	0.077839

Story	load combination	Drift,y	Drift,x	q	p(KN)	Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ,y	θ,x
Story-3	Dead	2.00E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	30142.58	0			
Story-3	Live	1.10E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	4437.399	0			
Story-3	EQ:X1	0.00E+00	0.000441	1.5	0	-892			
Story-3	EQ:X2	0	0.000441	1.5	0	-892			
Story-3	EQ:Y1	0.000339	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-892		
Story-3	EQ:Y2	0.000339	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-892		
Story-3	IMP in X		7.10E-05	1.5	0	-137.684			
Story-3	IMP in Y	5.90E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-137.684		
Story-3	Comb1	3.00E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	34579.98				
Story-3	Comb2	5.70E-05	7.10E-05	1.5	47348.59	137.6841			0.036625
Story-3	Comb3	5.80E-05	7.10E-05	1.5	47348.59	-137.684			0.036625
Story-3	Comb4	1.70E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	47348.59		-137.684	0.023721	
Story-3	Comb5	0.000102	0.00E+00	1.5	47348.59		137.6841	0.023842	
Story-3	Comb6	2.30E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	31473.8				
Story-3	Comb7	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb8	0.000204	0.000379	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.023721
Story-3	Comb9	0.000234	0.00052	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023842
Story-3	Comb10	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023923
Story-3	Comb11	0.000169	0.000503	1.5	39185.36	-1029.68			0.028713
Story-3	Comb12	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594
Story-3	Comb13	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594
Story-3	Comb14	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb15	0.000234	0.00052	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023842
Story-3	Comb16	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594

Story-3	Comb17	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb18	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594
Story-3	Comb19	0.000204	0.000379	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.023721
Story-3	Comb20	0.000234	0.00052	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023842
Story-3	Comb21	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb22	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594
Story-3	Comb23	0.000234	0.00052	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023842
Story-3	Comb24	0.000204	0.000379	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.023721
Story-3	Comb25	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.035063	
Story-3	Comb26	0.000303	6.20E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb27	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb28	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb29	0.000329	9.00E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb30	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb31	0.000329	9.00E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb32	0.000303	6.20E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb33	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb34	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.035063	
Story-3	Comb35	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.035063	
Story-3	Comb36	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb37	0.000329	9.00E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb38	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.035063	
Story-3	Comb39	0.000303	6.20E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb40	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb41	0.000329	9.00E-05	1.5	31473.8	129.9159			0.032705
Story-3	Comb7-1	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb8-1	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023923

Story-3	Comb9-1	0.00016	0.000447	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023658
Story-3	Comb10-1	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023923
Story-3	Comb11-1	0.000211	0.00043	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.022759
Story-3	Comb12-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb13-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb14-1	0.000211	0.00043	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.022759
Story-3	Comb15-1	0.00016	0.000447	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023658
Story-3	Comb16-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb17-1	0.000211	0.00043	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.022759
Story-3	Comb18-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb19-1	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023923
Story-3	Comb20-1	0.00016	0.000447	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023658
Story-3	Comb21-1	0.000211	0.00043	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.022759
Story-3	Comb22-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb23-1	0.00016	0.000447	1.5	31473.8	-892		0.008468	
Story-3	Comb24-1	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892		0.014714	
Story-3	Comb25-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	
Story-3	Comb26-1	0.000231	0.000106	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.040754	
Story-3	Comb27-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Comb28-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Comb29-1	0.000404	0.000164	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.071275	
Story-3	Comb30-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	
Story-3	Comb31-1	0.000404	0.000164	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.071275	
Story-3	Comb32-1	0.000231	0.000106	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.040754	
Story-3	Comb33-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Comb34-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	
Story-3	Comb35-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	

Story-3	Comb36-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Comb37-1	0.000404	0.000164	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.071275	
Story-3	Comb38-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	
Story-3	Comb39-1	0.000231	0.000106	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.040754	
Story-3	Comb40-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Envelope-ALL Max	0.000404	0.00052	1.5	39185.36		405.2841	0.058592	
Story-3	Envelope-ALL Min	0.000278	0.000232	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68	-1029.68	0.012746	
Story-3							max	0.071275	0.075415

Story	load combination	Drift,y	Drift,x	q	p(KN(Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ,y	θ,x
Story-2	Dead	1.20E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	38811.92				
Story-2	Live	7.00E-06	0.00E+00	1.5	5858.889				
Story-2	EQ:X1	0.00E+00	0.000445	1.5	0	-1273			
Story-2	EQ:X2	0	0.000445	1.5	0	-1273			
Story-2	EQ:Y1	0.000339	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-1273		
Story-2	EQ:Y2	0.000339	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-1273		
Story-2	IMP in X	0	7.90E-05	1.5	0	-231.452			
Story-2	IMP in Y	7.10E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-324.452		
Story-2	Comb1	1.90E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	44670.81				
Story-2	Comb2	4.90E-05	7.90E-05	1.5	61184.42	231.4522			0.031325
Story-2	Comb3	5.00E-05	7.90E-05	1.5	61184.42	-231.452			0.031325
Story-2	Comb4	4.60E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	61184.42		-324.452	0.013012	
Story-2	Comb5	9.80E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	61184.42		324.4522	0.027721	
Story-2	Comb6	1.40E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	40569.58				
Story-2	Comb7	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832

Story-2	Comb8	0.000218	0.000375	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.02191
Story-2	Comb9	0.000265	0.000533	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.02156
Story-2	Comb10	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021655
Story-2	Comb11	0.000221	0.000515	1.5	50455.49	-1504.45			0.025908
Story-2	Comb12	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb13	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb14	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832
Story-2	Comb15	0.000265	0.000533	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.02156
Story-2	Comb16	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb17	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832
Story-2	Comb18	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb19	0.000218	0.000375	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.02191
Story-2	Comb20	0.000265	0.000533	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.02156
Story-2	Comb21	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832
Story-2	Comb22	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb23	0.000265	0.000533	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.02156
Story-2	Comb24	0.000218	0.000375	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55		0.034738	0.02191
Story-2	Comb25	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	
Story-2	Comb26	0.00031	4.70E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.014819	
Story-2	Comb27	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb28	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb29	0.000339	8.50E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.016206	
Story-2	Comb30	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	
Story-2	Comb31	0.000339	8.50E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.016206	
Story-2	Comb32	0.00031	4.70E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.014819	
Story-2	Comb33	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb34	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	

Story-2	Comb35	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	
Story-2	Comb36	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb37	0.000339	8.50E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.016206	
Story-2	Comb38	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	
Story-2	Comb39	0.00031	4.70E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.014819	
Story-2	Comb40	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb41	0.000339	8.50E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.016206	
Story-2	Comb7-1	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832
Story-2	Comb8-1	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021655
Story-2	Comb9-1	0.000171	0.000454	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021703
Story-2	Comb10-1	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021655
Story-2	Comb11-1	0.00027	0.000436	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020843
Story-2	Comb12-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795
Story-2	Comb13-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795
Story-2	Comb14-1	0.00027	0.000436	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020843
Story-2	Comb15-1	0.000171	0.000454	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021703
Story-2	Comb16-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795
Story-2	Comb17-1	0.00027	0.000436	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020843
Story-2	Comb18-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795
Story-2	Comb19-1	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021655
Story-2	Comb20-1	0.000171	0.000454	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021703
Story-2	Comb21-1	0.00027	0.000436	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020843
Story-2	Comb22-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795
Story-2	Comb23-1	0.000171	0.000454	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021703
Story-2	Comb24-1	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273		0.026966	0.021655
Story-2	Comb25-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45	0.014438	
Story-2	Comb26-1	0.000237	0.000103	1.5	40569.58		-948.548	0.015205	

Story-2	Comb27-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548	0.018669	
Story-2	Comb28-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548	0.018669	
Story-2	Comb29-1	0.000433	0.000163	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45	0.016495	
Story-2	Comb30-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45	0.014438	
Story-2	Comb31-1	0.000433	0.000163	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45	0.016495	
Story-2	Comb32-1	0.000237	0.000103	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.016413
Story-2	Comb33-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.026133
Story-2	Comb34-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45		0.016572
Story-2	Comb35-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45		0.016572
Story-2	Comb36-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.026133
Story-2	Comb37-1	0.000433	0.000163	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45		0.025973
Story-2	Comb38-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45		0.016572
Story-2	Comb39-1	0.000237	0.000103	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.016413
Story-2	Comb40-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.026133
Story-2	Envlope-ALL Max	0.000433	0.000533	1.5	50455.49		706.3522		0.065768
Story-2	Envlope-ALL Min	0.000313	0.000242	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45	-1597.45	0.011924	0.009789
Story-2							max	0.046394	0.065768

Storey	load combination	Drift,y	Drift,x	q	p(KN)	Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ_y	θ_x
Story-1	Dead	0.000003	0	1.5	42069.57				
Story-1	Live	0.000002	0	1.5	6019.489				
Story-1	EQ:X1	0	0.000235	1.5	0	1517			
Story-1	EQ:X2	0	0.000235	1.5	0	1517			
Story-1	EQ:Y1	0.000183	0	1.5	0		-1517		
Story-1	EQ:Y2	0.000183	0	1.5	0		-1517		
Story-1	IMP in X	0	0.000046	1.5	0	332.5589			

Story-1	IMP in Y	0.00003	0	1.5	0	-	-425.559		
Story-1	Comb1	0.000005	0	1.5	48089.06	-			
Story-1	Comb2	0.000023	0.000046	1.5	65823.16	332.5589			0.013657
Story-1	Comb3	0.000023	0.000046	1.5	65823.16	332.5589			0.013657
Story-1	Comb4	0.000036	0	1.5	65823.16		425.5589	0.008352	
Story-1	Comb5	0.000051	0	1.5	65823.16		425.5589	0.011833	
Story-1	Comb6	0.000004	0	1.5	43875.42	-			
Story-1	Comb7	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	43875.42	1849.559			0.009821
Story-1	Comb8	0.000119	0.000193	1.5	43875.42	1184.441			0.010724
Story-1	Comb9	0.00015	0.000285	1.5	43875.42	1849.559			0.010141
Story-1	Comb10	0.000178	0.000239	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010369
Story-1	Comb11	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	54690.45	-1849.56			0.012242
Story-1	Comb12	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb13	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb14	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.009821
Story-1	Comb15	0.00015	0.000285	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.010141
Story-1	Comb16	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb17	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.009821
Story-1	Comb18	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb19	0.000119	0.000193	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010724
Story-1	Comb20	0.00015	0.000285	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.010141
Story-1	Comb21	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.009821
Story-1	Comb22	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb23	0.00015	0.000285	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.010141
Story-1	Comb24	0.000119	0.000193	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010724
Story-1	Comb25	0.000191	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.008439
Story-1	Comb26	0.000172	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.07143

Story-1	Comb27	0.000218	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.011113
Story-1	Comb28	0.000218	0.00004	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.003342
Story-1	Comb29	0.000187	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.054244
Story-1	Comb30	0.000191	0.00004	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.003342
Story-1	Comb31	0.000187	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.07143
Story-1	Comb32	0.000172	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.054244
Story-1	Comb33	0.000218	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.008439
Story-1	Comb34	0.000191	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.011113
Story-1	Comb35	0.000191	0.00004	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.003342
Story-1	Comb36	0.000218	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.008439
Story-1	Comb37	0.000187	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.07143
Story-1	Comb38	0.000191	0.00004	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.003342
Story-1	Comb39	0.000172	0.000276	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0
Story-1	Comb40	0.000218	0.000239	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.01997
Story-1	Comb41	0.000187	0.00024	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0
Story-1	Comb7-1	0.000136	0.000239	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56	-	0.019667	
Story-1	Comb8-1	0.000178	0.00023	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009978
Story-1	Comb9-1	0	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935
Story-1	Comb10-1	0.000178	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935
Story-1	Comb11-1	0.000164	0.00023	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009978
Story-1	Comb12-1	0	0.00024	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010412
Story-1	Comb13-1	0	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935
Story-1	Comb14-1	0.000164	0.00023	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009978
Story-1	Comb15-1	0.000065	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935
Story-1	Comb16-1	0	0.000239	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010369
Story-1	Comb17-1	0.000164	0.00024	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010412
Story-1	Comb18-1	0	0.00023	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009978

Story-1	Comb19-1	0	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935
Story-1	Comb20-1	0	0.00024	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010412
Story-1	Comb21-1	0.000164	0.000239	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010369
Story-1	Comb22-1	0	0.000055	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.002386
Story-1	Comb23-1	0.000065	0.000054	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.002343
Story-1	Comb24-1	0.000178	0.000087	1.5	43875.42	-1517		0.013302	
Story-1	Comb25-1	0.000219	0.000087	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb26-1	0.000131	0.000086	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.007899	
Story-1	Comb27-1	0.000159	0.000055	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	
Story-1	Comb28-1	0.000159	0.000086	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	
Story-1	Comb29-1	0.000245	0.000054	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.008301	
Story-1	Comb30-1	0.000219	0.000087	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb31-1	0.000245	0.000055	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.008301	
Story-1	Comb32-1	0.000131	0.000055	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.007899	
Story-1	Comb33-1	0.000159	0.000087	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	
Story-1	Comb34-1	0.000219	0.000086	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb35-1	0.000219	0.000055	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb36-1	0.000159	0.000054	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	
Story-1	Comb37-1	0.000245	0.000087	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.008301	
Story-1	Comb38-1	0.000219	0.000285	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb39-1	0.000131	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.007899	
Story-1	Comb40-1	0.000159	0.000083	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	
Story-1	Envlope-ALL Max	0.000245	0.000274	1.5	54690.45		880.6589	0.022822	
Story-1	Envlope-ALL Min	0.000178	0.000117	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0	
Story-1							max	0.024515	0.07143

Story	load combination	Drift,x	Drift,y	q	p(KN)	Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ_x	θ_y
Story-5	Dead	0.00E+00	2.90E-05	1.5	12810.7865				
Story-5	Live	0.00E+00	1.50E-05	1.5	1594.419				
Story-5	EQ:X1	0.000239	0.00E+00	1.5	0	-130			
Story-5	EQ:X2	0.000239	0.00E+00	1.5	0	-130			
Story-5	EQ:Y1	0.00E+00	0.000214	1.5	0		-130		
Story-5	EQ:Y2	0.00E+00	0.000214	1.5	0		-130		
Story-5	IMP in X	3.50E-05	0	1.5	0	-15.0666			
Story-5	IMP in Y	0.00E+00	3.30E-05	1.5	0		-15.0666		
Story-5	Comb1	0.00E+00	4.40E-05	1.5	14405.2055				
Story-5	Comb2	4.20E-05	6.10E-05	1.5	19686.1903	15.0666		0.082317	
Story-5	Comb3	4.20E-05	6.10E-05	1.5	19686.1903	-15.0666		0.082317	
Story-5	Comb4	0.00E+00	3.30E-05	1.5	19686.1903		-15.0666	0.064677	
Story-5	Comb5	0.00E+00	9.20E-05	1.5	19686.1903		156	0.017415	
Story-5	Comb6	0.00E+00	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122				
Story-5	Comb7	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb8	0.00021	0.000107	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.05469
Story-5	Comb9	0.000278	0.000109	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.055712
Story-5	Comb10	0.000246	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.051616
Story-5	Comb11	0.00028	0.00E+00	1.5	16654.0224	-145.0666			0
Story-5	Comb12	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867
Story-5	Comb13	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867
Story-5	Comb14	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb15	0.000278	0.000109	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.055712
Story-5	Comb16	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867
Story-5	Comb17	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb18	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867

Story-5	Comb19	0.00021	0.000107	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.05469
Story-5	Comb20	0.000278	0.000109	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.055712
Story-5	Comb21	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb22	0.00021	3.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.016867
Story-5	Comb23	0.000278	0.000109	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.055712
Story-5	Comb24	0.00021	0.000107	1.5	13289.1122	-114.9334			0.05469
Story-5	Comb25	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	
Story-5	Comb26	5.90E-05	0.000181	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04914	
Story-5	Comb27	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb28	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb29	5.40E-05	0.000186	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.044976	
Story-5	Comb30	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	
Story-5	Comb31	5.40E-05	0.000186	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.044976	
Story-5	Comb32	5.90E-05	0.000181	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04914	
Story-5	Comb33	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb34	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	
Story-5	Comb35	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	
Story-5	Comb36	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb37	5.40E-05	0.000186	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.044976	
Story-5	Comb38	0.000127	0.000179	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.046823	
Story-5	Comb39	5.90E-05	0.000181	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04914	
Story-5	Comb40	0.000122	0.000188	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.04498	
Story-5	Comb41	5.40E-05	0.000186	1.5	13289.1122		-130	0.044976	
Story-5	Comb7-1	0.00028	3.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666			0.017889
Story-5	Comb8-1	0.000246	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.051616
Story-5	Comb9-1	0.000242	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb10-1	0.000246	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.051616

Story-5	Comb11-1	0.000247	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.023227
Story-5	Comb12-1	0.000243	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.052471
Story-5	Comb13-1	0.000243	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb14-1	0.000247	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.023227
Story-5	Comb15-1	0.000242	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.012462
Story-5	Comb16-1	0.000243	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb17-1	0.000247	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.023227
Story-5	Comb18-1	0.000243	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb19-1	0.000246	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.051616
Story-5	Comb20-1	0.000242	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb21-1	0.000247	6.30E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.023227
Story-5	Comb22-1	0.000243	7.50E-05	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.062466
Story-5	Comb23-1	0.000242	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.012084
Story-5	Comb24-1	0.000246	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122	-130			0.078162
Story-5	Comb25-1	9.50E-05	0.000147	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	
Story-5	Comb26-1	9.10E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.046512	
Story-5	Comb27-1	8.60E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Comb28-1	8.60E-05	0.00022	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Comb29-1	8.90E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.04549	
Story-5	Comb30-1	9.50E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	
Story-5	Comb31-1	8.90E-05	0.00022	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.04549	
Story-5	Comb32-1	9.10E-05	0.000147	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.046512	
Story-5	Comb33-1	8.60E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Comb34-1	9.50E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	
Story-5	Comb35-1	9.50E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	
Story-5	Comb36-1	8.60E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Comb37-1	8.90E-05	0.00022	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.04549	

Story-5	Comb38-1	9.50E-05	0.000212	1.5	13289.1122		-145.0666	0.048556	
Story-5	Comb39-1	9.10E-05	0.000147	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.046512	
Story-5	Comb40-1	8.60E-05	0.000155	1.5	13289.1122		-114.9334	0.043956	
Story-5	Envlope-ALL Max	0.00028	0.00022	1.5	16654.0224		154.0666	0.0454	
Story-5	Envlope-ALL Min	0.000122	0.00014	1.5	13289.1122	-145.0666	-145.0666	0.016764	0.019237
Story-5							max	0.082317	0.078162

Table: Evaluation of Stability index in Seismic Load, ULS. As shown the maximum value is 0.082367 in the x- axis (X-direction) and is 0.0789 in the y-direction .The structure is quite rigid to neglect the effect of second order effects.

Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination

Story	load combination	Drift,y	Drift,x	q	p(KN)	Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ,y	θ,x
Story-4	Dead	2.40E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	21468.01				
Story-4	Live	1.30E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	3015.909				
Story-4	EQ:X1	0.00E+00	0.000348	1.5	0	-511			
Story-4	EQ:X2	0	0.000348	1.5	0	-511			
Story-4	EQ:Y1	0.000279	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-511		
Story-4	EQ:Y2	0.000279	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-511		
Story-4	IMP in X	0	5.20E-05	1.5	0	-65.589			
Story-4	IMP in Y	4.40E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-65.589		
Story-4	Comb1	3.70E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	24483.91				
Story-4	Comb2	5.70E-05	5.10E-05	1.5	33505.67	65.589			0.039079
Story-4	Comb3	5.90E-05	5.20E-05	1.5	33505.67	-65.589			0.039846
Story-4	Comb4	1.20E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	33505.67		-65.589	0.009195	
Story-4	Comb5	9.60E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	33505.67		65.589	0.073561	
Story-4	Comb6	2.80E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	22372.78				
Story-4	Comb7	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874

Story-4	Comb8	0.000153	0.000303	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.022829
Story-4	Comb9	0.000166	0.000407	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.023689
Story-4	Comb10	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb11	9.20E-05	0.000393	1.5	27908.41	-576.589			0.028533
Story-4	Comb12	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb13	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb14	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874
Story-4	Comb15	0.000166	0.000407	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.023689
Story-4	Comb16	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb17	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874
Story-4	Comb18	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb19	0.000153	0.000303	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.022829
Story-4	Comb20	0.000166	0.000407	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.023689
Story-4	Comb21	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874
Story-4	Comb22	8.20E-05	0.000289	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.021774
Story-4	Comb23	0.000166	0.000407	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.023689
Story-4	Comb24	0.000153	0.000303	1.5	22372.78	-445.411			0.022829
Story-4	Comb25	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	
Story-4	Comb26	0.000244	6.30E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.016024	
Story-4	Comb27	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb28	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb29	0.000259	7.60E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017009	
Story-4	Comb30	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	
Story-4	Comb31	0.000259	7.60E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017009	
Story-4	Comb32	0.000244	6.30E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.016024	
Story-4	Comb33	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb34	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	

Story-4	Comb35	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	
Story-4	Comb36	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb37	0.000259	7.60E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017009	
Story-4	Comb38	0.00023	0.000143	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.015105	
Story-4	Comb39	0.000244	6.30E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.016024	
Story-4	Comb40	0.000273	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017929	
Story-4	Comb41	0.000259	7.60E-05	1.5	22372.78		-511	0.017009	
Story-4	Comb7-1	9.50E-05	0.000393	1.5	22372.78	-576.589			0.022874
Story-4	Comb8-1	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb9-1	0.000116	0.000352	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023117
Story-4	Comb10-1	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb11-1	0.000127	0.000339	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022263
Story-4	Comb12-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526
Story-4	Comb13-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526
Story-4	Comb14-1	0.000127	0.000339	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022263
Story-4	Comb15-1	0.000116	0.000352	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023117
Story-4	Comb16-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526
Story-4	Comb17-1	0.000127	0.000339	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022263
Story-4	Comb18-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526
Story-4	Comb19-1	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb20-1	0.000116	0.000352	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023117
Story-4	Comb21-1	0.000127	0.000339	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022263
Story-4	Comb22-1	0	0.000343	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.022526
Story-4	Comb23-1	0.000116	0.000352	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023117
Story-4	Comb24-1	0.000204	0.000357	1.5	22372.78	-511			0.023445
Story-4	Comb25-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb26-1	0.000193	0.000101	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.014541	

Story-4	Comb27-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Comb28-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Comb29-1	0.00031	0.00013	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.018043	
Story-4	Comb30-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb31-1	0.00031	0.00013	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.018043	
Story-4	Comb32-1	0.000193	0.000101	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.014541	
Story-4	Comb33-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Comb34-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb35-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb36-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Comb37-1	0.00031	0.00013	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.018043	
Story-4	Comb38-1	0.000281	0.000106	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.016355	
Story-4	Comb39-1	0.000193	0.000101	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.014541	
Story-4	Comb40-1	0.000222	0.000125	1.5	22372.78		-445.411	0.016726	
Story-4	Envlope-ALL Max	0.00031	0.000407	1.5	27908.41		218.889	0.059288	
Story-4	Envlope-ALL Min	0.000204	0.000179	1.5	22372.78		-576.589	0.011873	
Story-4							max	0.073561	0.077839

Table: Evaluation of Stability index in Seismic Load, ULS. As shown the maximum value is 0.073367 in the x- axis (X-direction) and is 0.0776 in the y-direction .The structure is quite rigid to neglect the effect of second order effects.

Table 9.1: Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination

Story	load combination	Drift,y	Drift,x	q	p(KN)	Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ,y	θ,x
Story-3	Dead	2.00E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	30142.58	0			
Story-3	Live	1.10E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	4437.399	0			
Story-3	EQ:X1	0.00E+00	0.000441	1.5	0	-892			
Story-3	EQ:X2	0	0.000441	1.5	0	-892			
Story-3	EQ:Y1	0.000339	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-892		
Story-3	EQ:Y2	0.000339	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-892		
Story-3	IMP in X		7.10E-05	1.5	0	-137.684			
Story-3	IMP in Y	5.90E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-137.684		
Story-3	Comb1	3.00E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	34579.98				
Story-3	Comb2	5.70E-05	7.10E-05	1.5	47348.59	137.6841			0.036625
Story-3	Comb3	5.80E-05	7.10E-05	1.5	47348.59	-137.684			0.036625
Story-3	Comb4	1.70E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	47348.59		-137.684	0.023721	
Story-3	Comb5	0.000102	0.00E+00	1.5	47348.59		137.6841	0.023842	
Story-3	Comb6	2.30E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	31473.8				
Story-3	Comb7	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb8	0.000204	0.000379	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.023721
Story-3	Comb9	0.000234	0.00052	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023842
Story-3	Comb10	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023923
Story-3	Comb11	0.000169	0.000503	1.5	39185.36	-1029.68			0.028713
Story-3	Comb12	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594
Story-3	Comb13	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594
Story-3	Comb14	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb15	0.000234	0.00052	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023842
Story-3	Comb16	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594

Story-3	Comb17	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb18	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594
Story-3	Comb19	0.000204	0.000379	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.023721
Story-3	Comb20	0.000234	0.00052	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023842
Story-3	Comb21	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb22	0.000141	0.000361	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.022594
Story-3	Comb23	0.000234	0.00052	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023842
Story-3	Comb24	0.000204	0.000379	1.5	31473.8	-754.316			0.023721
Story-3	Comb25	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.035063	
Story-3	Comb26	0.000303	6.20E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb27	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb28	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb29	0.000329	9.00E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb30	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb31	0.000329	9.00E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb32	0.000303	6.20E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb33	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb34	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.035063	
Story-3	Comb35	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.035063	
Story-3	Comb36	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb37	0.000329	9.00E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb38	0.000301	0.000174	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.035063	
Story-3	Comb39	0.000303	6.20E-05	1.5	31473.8		-892	0	
Story-3	Comb40	0.00036	0.000232	1.5	31473.8		-892	0.041936	
Story-3	Comb41	0.000329	9.00E-05	1.5	31473.8	129.9159			0.032705
Story-3	Comb7-1	0.000172	0.000503	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68			0.023062
Story-3	Comb8-1	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023923

Story-3	Comb9-1	0.00016	0.000447	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023658
Story-3	Comb10-1	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023923
Story-3	Comb11-1	0.000211	0.00043	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.022759
Story-3	Comb12-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb13-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb14-1	0.000211	0.00043	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.022759
Story-3	Comb15-1	0.00016	0.000447	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023658
Story-3	Comb16-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb17-1	0.000211	0.00043	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.022759
Story-3	Comb18-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb19-1	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023923
Story-3	Comb20-1	0.00016	0.000447	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023658
Story-3	Comb21-1	0.000211	0.00043	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.022759
Story-3	Comb22-1	0	0.000435	1.5	31473.8	-892			0.023023
Story-3	Comb23-1	0.00016	0.000447	1.5	31473.8	-892		0.008468	
Story-3	Comb24-1	0.000278	0.000452	1.5	31473.8	-892		0.014714	
Story-3	Comb25-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	
Story-3	Comb26-1	0.000231	0.000106	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.040754	
Story-3	Comb27-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Comb28-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Comb29-1	0.000404	0.000164	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.071275	
Story-3	Comb30-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	
Story-3	Comb31-1	0.000404	0.000164	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.071275	
Story-3	Comb32-1	0.000231	0.000106	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.040754	
Story-3	Comb33-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Comb34-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	
Story-3	Comb35-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	

Story-3	Comb36-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Comb37-1	0.000404	0.000164	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.071275	
Story-3	Comb38-1	0.000347	0.000107	1.5	31473.8		-1029.68	0.061219	
Story-3	Comb39-1	0.000231	0.000106	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.040754	
Story-3	Comb40-1	0.000285	0.000159	1.5	31473.8		-754.316	0.05028	
Story-3	Envelope-ALL Max	0.000404	0.00052	1.5	39185.36		405.2841	0.058592	
Story-3	Envelope-ALL Min	0.000278	0.000232	1.5	31473.8	-1029.68	-1029.68	0.012746	
Story-3							max	0.071275	0.075415

Table: Evaluation of Stability index in Seismic Load, ULS. As shown the maximum value is 0.07167 in the x- axis (X-direction) and is 0.0754

in the y-direction .The structure is quite rigid to neglect the effect of second order effects.

Table 9.2: Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination

Story	load combination	Drift,y	Drift,x	q	p(KN(Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ_y	θ_x
Story-2	Dead	1.20E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	38811.92				
Story-2	Live	7.00E-06	0.00E+00	1.5	5858.889				
Story-2	EQ:X1	0.00E+00	0.000445	1.5	0	-1273			
Story-2	EQ:X2	0	0.000445	1.5	0	-1273			
Story-2	EQ:Y1	0.000339	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-1273		
Story-2	EQ:Y2	0.000339	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-1273		
Story-2	IMP in X	0	7.90E-05	1.5	0	-231.452			
Story-2	IMP in Y	7.10E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	0		-324.452		
Story-2	Comb1	1.90E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	44670.81				
Story-2	Comb2	4.90E-05	7.90E-05	1.5	61184.42	231.4522			0.031325
Story-2	Comb3	5.00E-05	7.90E-05	1.5	61184.42	-231.452			0.031325

Story-2	Comb4	4.60E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	61184.42		-324.452	0.013012	
Story-2	Comb5	9.80E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	61184.42		324.4522	0.027721	
Story-2	Comb6	1.40E-05	0.00E+00	1.5	40569.58				
Story-2	Comb7	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832
Story-2	Comb8	0.000218	0.000375	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.02191
Story-2	Comb9	0.000265	0.000533	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.02156
Story-2	Comb10	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021655
Story-2	Comb11	0.000221	0.000515	1.5	50455.49	-1504.45			0.025908
Story-2	Comb12	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb13	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb14	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832
Story-2	Comb15	0.000265	0.000533	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.02156
Story-2	Comb16	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb17	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832
Story-2	Comb18	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb19	0.000218	0.000375	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.02191
Story-2	Comb20	0.000265	0.000533	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.02156
Story-2	Comb21	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832
Story-2	Comb22	0.000176	0.000357	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55			0.020858
Story-2	Comb23	0.000265	0.000533	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.02156
Story-2	Comb24	0.000218	0.000375	1.5	40569.58	-1041.55		0.034738	0.02191
Story-2	Comb25	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	
Story-2	Comb26	0.00031	4.70E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.014819	
Story-2	Comb27	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb28	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb29	0.000339	8.50E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.016206	
Story-2	Comb30	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	

Story-2	Comb31	0.000339	8.50E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.016206	
Story-2	Comb32	0.00031	4.70E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.014819	
Story-2	Comb33	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb34	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	
Story-2	Comb35	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	
Story-2	Comb36	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb37	0.000339	8.50E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.016206	
Story-2	Comb38	0.000331	0.000182	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.015823	
Story-2	Comb39	0.00031	4.70E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.014819	
Story-2	Comb40	0.000386	0.000242	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.018452	
Story-2	Comb41	0.000339	8.50E-05	1.5	40569.58		-1273	0.016206	
Story-2	Comb7-1	0.000223	0.000515	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45			0.020832
Story-2	Comb8-1	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021655
Story-2	Comb9-1	0.000171	0.000454	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021703
Story-2	Comb10-1	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021655
Story-2	Comb11-1	0.00027	0.000436	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020843
Story-2	Comb12-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795
Story-2	Comb13-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795
Story-2	Comb14-1	0.00027	0.000436	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020843
Story-2	Comb15-1	0.000171	0.000454	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021703
Story-2	Comb16-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795
Story-2	Comb17-1	0.00027	0.000436	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020843
Story-2	Comb18-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795
Story-2	Comb19-1	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021655
Story-2	Comb20-1	0.000171	0.000454	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021703
Story-2	Comb21-1	0.00027	0.000436	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020843
Story-2	Comb22-1	0	0.000435	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.020795

Story-2	Comb23-1	0.000171	0.000454	1.5	40569.58	-1273			0.021703
Story-2	Comb24-1	0.000313	0.000453	1.5	40569.58	-1273		0.026966	0.021655
Story-2	Comb25-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45	0.014438	
Story-2	Comb26-1	0.000237	0.000103	1.5	40569.58		-948.548	0.015205	
Story-2	Comb27-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548	0.018669	
Story-2	Comb28-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548	0.018669	
Story-2	Comb29-1	0.000433	0.000163	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45	0.016495	
Story-2	Comb30-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45	0.014438	
Story-2	Comb31-1	0.000433	0.000163	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45	0.016495	
Story-2	Comb32-1	0.000237	0.000103	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.016413
Story-2	Comb33-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.026133
Story-2	Comb34-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45		0.016572
Story-2	Comb35-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45		0.016572
Story-2	Comb36-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.026133
Story-2	Comb37-1	0.000433	0.000163	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45		0.025973
Story-2	Comb38-1	0.000379	0.000104	1.5	40569.58		-1597.45		0.016572
Story-2	Comb39-1	0.000237	0.000103	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.016413
Story-2	Comb40-1	0.000291	0.000164	1.5	40569.58		-948.548		0.026133
Story-2	Envelope-ALL Max	0.000433	0.000533	1.5	50455.49		706.3522		0.065768
Story-2	Envelope-ALL Min	0.000313	0.000242	1.5	40569.58	-1504.45	-1597.45	0.011924	0.009789
Story-2							max	0.046394	0.065768

Table: Evaluation of Stability index in Seismic Load, ULS. As shown the maximum value is 0.046367 in the x- axis (X-direction) and is 0.065 in the y-direction .The structure is quite rigid to neglect the effect of second order effects.

Table 9.3: Evaluation of the index in Seismic Actions with –all combination

Storey	load combination	Drift,y	Drift,x	q	p(KN)	Vx(KN)	Vy(KN)	θ_y	θ_x
Story-1	Dead	0.000003	0	1.5	42069.57				
Story-1	Live	0.000002	0	1.5	6019.489				
Story-1	EQ:X1	0	0.000235	1.5	0	1517			
Story-1	EQ:X2	0	0.000235	1.5	0	1517			
Story-1	EQ:Y1	0.000183	0	1.5	0		-1517		
Story-1	EQ:Y2	0.000183	0	1.5	0		-1517		
Story-1	IMP in X	0	0.000046	1.5	0	332.5589			
Story-1	IMP in Y	0.00003	0	1.5	0	-	-425.559		
Story-1	Comb1	0.000005	0	1.5	48089.06	-			
Story-1	Comb2	0.000023	0.000046	1.5	65823.16	332.5589			0.013657
Story-1	Comb3	0.000023	0.000046	1.5	65823.16	332.5589			0.013657
Story-1	Comb4	0.000036	0	1.5	65823.16		425.5589	0.008352	
Story-1	Comb5	0.000051	0	1.5	65823.16		425.5589	0.011833	
Story-1	Comb6	0.000004	0	1.5	43875.42	-			
Story-1	Comb7	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	43875.42	1849.559			0.009821
Story-1	Comb8	0.000119	0.000193	1.5	43875.42	1184.441			0.010724
Story-1	Comb9	0.00015	0.000285	1.5	43875.42	1849.559			0.010141
Story-1	Comb10	0.000178	0.000239	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010369
Story-1	Comb11	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	54690.45	-1849.56			0.012242
Story-1	Comb12	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb13	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb14	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.009821
Story-1	Comb15	0.00015	0.000285	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.010141
Story-1	Comb16	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb17	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.009821

Story-1	Comb18	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb19	0.000119	0.000193	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010724
Story-1	Comb20	0.00015	0.000285	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.010141
Story-1	Comb21	0.000136	0.000276	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.009821
Story-1	Comb22	0.000105	0.000183	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010168
Story-1	Comb23	0.00015	0.000285	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56			0.010141
Story-1	Comb24	0.000119	0.000193	1.5	43875.42	-1184.44			0.010724
Story-1	Comb25	0.000191	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.008439
Story-1	Comb26	0.000172	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.07143
Story-1	Comb27	0.000218	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.011113
Story-1	Comb28	0.000218	0.00004	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.003342
Story-1	Comb29	0.000187	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.054244
Story-1	Comb30	0.000191	0.00004	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.003342
Story-1	Comb31	0.000187	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.07143
Story-1	Comb32	0.000172	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.054244
Story-1	Comb33	0.000218	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.008439
Story-1	Comb34	0.000191	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.011113
Story-1	Comb35	0.000191	0.00004	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.003342
Story-1	Comb36	0.000218	0.000101	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.008439
Story-1	Comb37	0.000187	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.07143
Story-1	Comb38	0.000191	0.00004	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.003342
Story-1	Comb39	0.000172	0.000276	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0
Story-1	Comb40	0.000218	0.000239	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0.01997
Story-1	Comb41	0.000187	0.00024	1.5	43875.42		-1517		0
Story-1	Comb7-1	0.000136	0.000239	1.5	43875.42	-1849.56	-	0.019667	
Story-1	Comb8-1	0.000178	0.00023	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009978
Story-1	Comb9-1	0	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935

Story-1	Comb10-1	0.000178	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935
Story-1	Comb11-1	0.000164	0.00023	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009978
Story-1	Comb12-1	0	0.00024	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010412
Story-1	Comb13-1	0	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935
Story-1	Comb14-1	0.000164	0.00023	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009978
Story-1	Comb15-1	0.000065	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935
Story-1	Comb16-1	0	0.000239	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010369
Story-1	Comb17-1	0.000164	0.00024	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010412
Story-1	Comb18-1	0	0.00023	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009978
Story-1	Comb19-1	0	0.000229	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.009935
Story-1	Comb20-1	0	0.00024	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010412
Story-1	Comb21-1	0.000164	0.000239	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.010369
Story-1	Comb22-1	0	0.000055	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.002386
Story-1	Comb23-1	0.000065	0.000054	1.5	43875.42	-1517			0.002343
Story-1	Comb24-1	0.000178	0.000087	1.5	43875.42	-1517		0.013302	
Story-1	Comb25-1	0.000219	0.000087	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb26-1	0.000131	0.000086	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.007899	
Story-1	Comb27-1	0.000159	0.000055	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	
Story-1	Comb28-1	0.000159	0.000086	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	
Story-1	Comb29-1	0.000245	0.000054	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.008301	
Story-1	Comb30-1	0.000219	0.000087	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb31-1	0.000245	0.000055	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.008301	
Story-1	Comb32-1	0.000131	0.000055	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.007899	
Story-1	Comb33-1	0.000159	0.000087	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	
Story-1	Comb34-1	0.000219	0.000086	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb35-1	0.000219	0.000055	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb36-1	0.000159	0.000054	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	

Story-1	Comb37-1	0.000245	0.000087	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.008301	
Story-1	Comb38-1	0.000219	0.000285	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0.00742	
Story-1	Comb39-1	0.000131	0.000133	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.007899	
Story-1	Comb40-1	0.000159	0.000083	1.5	43875.42		-1091.44	0.009588	
Story-1	Envelope-ALL Max	0.000245	0.000274	1.5	54690.45		880.6589	0.022822	
Story-1	Envelope-ALL Min	0.000178	0.000117	1.5	43875.42		-1942.56	0	
Story-1							max	0.024515	0.07143

